

Polymorphic Coverage Types*

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Abstract

Test input generators are an important part of property-based testing (PBT) frameworks. Because PBT is intended to test deep semantic and structural properties of a program, the outputs produced by these generators can be complex data structures, constrained to satisfy properties the developer believes is most relevant to testing the function of interest. An important feature expected of these generators is that they be capable of producing *all* acceptable elements that satisfy the function’s input type and generator-provided constraints. However, it is not readily apparent how we might validate whether a particular generator’s output satisfies this *coverage* requirement. Typically, developers must rely on manual inspection and post-mortem analysis of test runs to determine if the generator is providing sufficient coverage; these approaches are error-prone and difficult to scale as generators become more complex. To address this important concern, we present a new refinement type-based verification procedure for validating the coverage provided by input test generators, based on a novel interpretation of types that embeds “*must-style*” underapproximate reasoning principles as a fundamental part of the type system. The types associated with expressions now capture the set of values *guaranteed* to be produced by the expression, rather than the typical formulation that uses types to represent the set of values an expression *may* produce. We have formalized the notion of *coverage types* in a rich core language that supports higher-order functions and inductive datatypes. To better support checking coverage properties of real-world test generators, we extend this type system with type and qualifier polymorphism. These extensions enable our system to statically verify coverage guarantees of test input generators constructed using the sort of monadic combinators found in most PBT frameworks. We have implemented a coverage type checker for OCaml programs based on this core calculus, and present a detailed evaluation of the utility of our ideas using a corpus of benchmarks drawn from both the PBT literature and open source projects.

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1 Introduction

Property-based testing (PBT) is a popular technique for automatically testing deep semantic and structural properties of programs. Originally pioneered by the QuickCheck [3] library for Haskell, PBT frameworks now exist for many programming languages, including QCheck [7], JavaScript [15], Rust [55], Python [27], Scala [56], and Rocq/Coq [36]. The PBT methodology rests on two key components: *executable properties* that capture the expected input-output behaviors of the program under test, and *test input generators* that generate random values of the input types needed to validate these behaviors. In contrast to unit tests, which rely on single examples of inputs and outputs, generators are meant to provide a *family* of inputs against which programs can be tested, with the goal of ensuring the set of generated tests provide good coverage of all possible inputs. In order to prune out irrelevant inputs, PBT frameworks allow users to define custom generators that reflect the specific shape of data that the developer believes is most likely to trigger interesting (aka faulty) behavior. As one simple example, to test a tree compression or balancing function, the developer may want to use a generator that produces n -ary trees with randomly chosen height and arity but whose leaves are ordered according to a user-provided ordering relation.

Given the critical role they play in the assurance case provided by PBT frameworks, it is reasonable to ask what constitutes a “good” specification for a test generator. For our example, one answer could be that it should only produce ordered trees. Of course, this is not a very satisfactory characterization of the behavior we desire: the “constant” generator that always produces trees of height one trivially meets this specification, but it is unlikely to produce useful tests for a compression function! Ideally, we would like a generator to intelligently enumerate the space of *all* possible ordered trees, thereby helping to maximize the likelihood of finding bugs in the function under test. Because defining such an enumeration procedure for arbitrary datatypes can be hard, even when complete enumeration is computationally feasible, PBT frameworks instead give developers the ability to assemble generators for complex data structures *compositionally*, building on generators for simpler types where randomly sampling elements of the type is straightforward and sufficient. For example, we could implement an ordered tree generator in terms of a primitive random number generator that is used to non-deterministically select the height, arity, and elements of a candidate tree, checking (or enforcing) the orderliness of the tree before returning it as a feasible test input. Although the random number generator might provide a guarantee that its underlying probability density function (PDF) is always non-zero on all elements in its sample space, determining that a tree generator that is built using it can actually enumerate all the ordered trees desired is a substantially harder problem. Even if we know the generator is capable of eventually yielding all trees, constraints imposed by the function’s precondition might require the generator to perform further filtering or transformations over generated trees. However, proving that any filtering operations the generator uses do not mistakenly prune out valid ordered trees or that any transformations the generator performs over candidate trees preserve the elements of the random tree being transformed, pose additional challenges. In other words, verifying that the generator is *complete* with respect to our desired orderliness property entails reasoning that is independent of the behavior of the primitive generators used to build the tree. Consequently, we require some alternative mechanism to help qualify the part of the target function’s input space the generator is actually guaranteed to cover. Devising such a mechanism is challenging precisely because the properties that need to be tested may

103 impose complex structural and semantic constraints on the generated output (e.g., requiring
 104 that an output tree be a binary search tree, or that it satisfies a red-black property, etc.); the
 105 complexity of these constraints is directly correlated to the sparseness of the function’s input
 106 space preconditions.

```

107
108 1 type 'a tree =
109 2   | Leaf
110 3   | Node of ('a * 'a tree * 'a tree)
111 4 let rec bst_gen (lo: int) (hi: int): int tree =
112 5   if lo + 1 >= hi then Leaf else
113 6   (* Leaf  $\oplus$  *)
114 7   (let (x: int) = int_range (lo + 1, hi - 1) in
115 8     Node (x, bst_gen lo x, bst_gen x hi))

```

116 Fig. 1. A BST generator. Failing to uncomment line 6 results in the generator never producing trees
 117 that contain only a subset of the elements in the interval between `lo` and `hi`, which is inconsistent with
 118 the developer’s intent.

119
 120 To illustrate this distinction more concretely, consider the input test generator shown in
 121 Figure 1 that is intended to generate all binary search trees (BSTs) whose elements are
 122 between the interval `lo` and `hi`. If we ignore the comment on line 6, we can conclude this
 123 generator always produces a non-empty BST whenever `lo < hi`. While the generator is
 124 correct - it always generates a well-formed BST - it is also incomplete; the call `bst_gen`
 125 `0 10`, for example, will never produce a tree containing just `Leaf` or a tree with a shape
 126 like `Node(1, Leaf, Leaf)`, even though these instances are valid trees consistent with the
 127 constraints imposed by the generator’s argument bounds. In fact, this implementation *never*
 128 generates a BST that only contains a proper subset of the elements that reside within the
 129 interval defined by `lo` and `hi`. By uncommenting line 6, however, we allow the generator
 130 to non-deterministically choose (via operator \oplus) to either return a `Leaf` or left and right
 131 BST subtrees based on value returned by the `int_range` generator, enabling it to potentially
 132 produce BSTs containing all valid subsets of the provided interval, thus satisfying our desired
 133 desired completeness behavior. The subtleties involved in reasoning about such coverage
 134 properties is clearly non-trivial. We reiterate that recognizing the distinction between these
 135 two implementations is not merely a matter of providing a precise output type capturing
 136 the desired sortedness property of a BST: the incomplete implementation clearly satisfies
 137 such a type! Furthermore, simply knowing that the underlying `int_range` generator used in
 138 the implementation samples all elements within the range of the arguments it is provided
 139 is also insufficient to conclude that the BST generator can yield *all* possible BSTs within
 140 the supplied interval. Similar observations have led prior work to consider ways to improve
 141 a generator’s coverage through mechanisms such as fuzzing [10, 34], or to automatically
 142 generate complete-by-construction generators for certain classes of datatypes [35].

143
 144 In contrast to these approaches, this paper embeds the notion of coverage as an integral part
 145 of a test input generator’s *type* specification. By doing so, a generator’s type now specifies
 146 the set of behaviors the generator is *guaranteed* to exhibit; a well-typed generator is thus
 147 guaranteed to produce *every possible* value satisfying a desired structural property, e.g.,
 148 that the repaired (complete) version of `bst_gen` is capable of producing every valid BST.
 149 By framing the notion of coverage in type-theoretic terms, our approach neither requires
 150 instrumentation of the target program to assess the coverage effectiveness of a candidate
 151
 152
 153

generator (as in Lampropoulos et al. [34]) nor does it depend on a specific compilation strategy for producing generators (as in Lampropoulos et al. [35]). Instead, our approach can automatically verify the coverage properties of an *arbitrary* test input generator, regardless of whether it was hand-written or automatically synthesized.

Key to our approach is a novel formulation of a *must*-style analysis [19, 20, 28] of a test input generator's behavior in type-theoretic terms. In our proposed type system, we say an expression e has *coverage type* τ if every value contained in τ *must* be producible by e . Note how this definition differs from our usual notion of what a type represents: ordinarily, if e has type τ then we are allowed to conclude only that any value contained in τ *may* be produced by e . Informally, types interpreted in this usual way define an *overapproximation* of the values an expression e can yield, without obligating e to produce any specific such value. In contrast, coverage types define an *underapproximation* - they characterize the values an expression e has to produce, potentially eliding other values that e may also evaluate to. When the set of elements denoted by a generator's (underapproximate) coverage type matches that of its (overapproximate) normal type, however, we can soundly assert that the generator is complete. As we illustrate in the remainder of the paper, this characterization allows us to reason about a program's coverage behavior on the same formal footing as its safety properties.

In this sense, our solution can be seen a type-theoretic interpretation of recently proposed Incorrectness Logics (IL) [37, 45, 53], in much the same way that refinement-type systems like Liquid Types [29, 62] relate to traditional program logics [25]. Despite the philosophical similarities with IL, however, we use underapproximate reasoning for a very different goal. While IL has been primarily used to precisely capture the conditions that will lead a program to fault, this work explores how type-based underapproximate reasoning can be used to verify the completeness properties of a test generator in the context of PBT.

This interpretation leads to a fundamental recasting of how types relate to one another: ordinarily, we are always allowed to assert that $\tau <: \top$. This means that any typing context that admits an expression with type τ can also admit that expression at a type with a logically weaker structure. In contrast, the subtyping relation for coverage types inverts this relation, so that $\top <: \tau$. Intuitively, \top represents the coverage type that obligates an expression ascribed this type to be capable of producing *all* elements in τ . But, any context that requires an expression to produce all such elements can always guarantee that the expression will also produce a subset of these elements. In other words, we are always allowed to weaken an overapproximation (i.e., grow the set of values an expression may evaluate to), and strengthen an underapproximation (i.e., shrink the set of values an expression must evaluate to). Thus, in our setting, a random number generator over the integers has coverage type \top under the mild assumption that its underlying PDF provides a non-zero likelihood of returning every integer. In contrast, a faulty computation like `1 div 0` has coverage type \perp since there are no guarantees provided by the computation on the value(s) it must return. Here, \perp represents a type that defines a degenerate underapproximation, imposing no constraints on the values an expression ascribed this type must produce.

In practice, developers often implement input generators using *test generator combinators* using combinators provided by the PBT framework. In this setting, generators are defined in terms of a monad that facilitates the compositional construction of complex generators from simpler ones in a modular way. The OCaml PBT framework QCheck [7], for example, ascribes the type `'a Gen.t` to such generators, as can be seen in the signature for the binary

```

205 1   val return: 'a -> 'a Gen.t
206 2   val bind: 'a -> ('a -> 'b Gen.t) -> 'b Gen.t
207 3   val frequency: (int -> (int * 'a Gen.t)) -> 'a Gen.t
208 4   val fix: (int -> (int -> 'a -> 'a Gen.t) -> 'a Gen.t) -> int -> 'a Gen.t
209 5
210 6   type 'a tree = Leaf of 'a | Node of 'a tree * 'a tree
211 7   let tree_gen : int -> int tree Gen.t = fix
212 8     (fun n self -> match n with
213 9       | 0 -> return err
214 10      | 1 -> bind nat_gen (fun x -> return (Leaf x))
215 11      | n ->
216 12        frequency
217 13          (function
218 14            | 0 -> (1, bind nat_gen (fun x -> return (Leaf x)))
219 15            | _ -> (2, bind (self n/2) (fun tr1 ->
220 16              bind (self n/2) (fun tr2 ->
221 17                return (Node (tr1, tr2))))))
222 18    )

```

Fig. 2. A tree generator expressed using QCheck.

tree generator `tree_gen` shown in Fig. 2. This generator is implemented by 4 combinators: in addition to the basic monad operators (`return` and `bind`), `tree_gen` also uses the `frequency` combinator to sample from multiple generators according to the given weights, as well as the `fix` combinator to recursively construct trees of greater height from smaller ones. Extending coverage types to support monadic combinators and type polymorphism (on both types and qualifiers) requires significant extensions over the core monomorphic, non-monadic formulation.

In summary, this article makes the following contributions:

- (1) Introduces the notion of *coverage types*, types that characterize the values that an input test generator is guaranteed to produce.
- (2) Formalizes the semantics of coverage types in an ML-like functional language with support for higher-order functions and inductive datatypes.¹
- (3) Develops a bi-directional type-checking algorithm for coverage types in this language.
- (4) Extends this core calculus and typing algorithm to support coverage type polymorphism and monadic composition.
- (5) Incorporates these ideas in a tool (Poirot) that operates over OCaml programs equipped with input generators and typed using coverage types.
- (6) Presents an extensive empirical evaluation justifying the utility of coverage types, by using Poirot to verify the coverage properties of both hand-written generators drawn from real-world open source PBT applications and automatically synthesized generators, covering a rich class of datatypes and their structural properties.

The remainder of this article is structured as follows. In the next section, we present an informal overview of the key features of our type system. Section 3 presents the syntax and semantics for a core call-by-value higher-order functional language with inductive datatypes that we use to formalize our approach. Section 4 describes our coverage type system, and its

¹A Rocq formalization of this calculus, its type system, and its metatheory (i.e., Theorem 5.3) is provided on Zenodo [69].

Table 1. Examples of overapproximate and underapproximate (coverage) typings. We use \vdash and $\not\vdash$ to identify whether a term can or cannot be assigned the corresponding type, resp. The constant `err` represents a special error value, which causes the program to halt when encountered.

<code>int_gen()</code>	$\vdash [v: \text{int} \mid \top]$ $\vdash \{v: \text{int} \mid \top\}$	$\not\vdash [v: \text{int} \mid v = 1 \vee 2]$ $\not\vdash \{v: \text{int} \mid v = 1 \vee 2\}$	$\vdash [v: \text{int} \mid v = 1]$ $\not\vdash \{v: \text{int} \mid v = 1\}$	$\vdash [v: \text{int} \mid \perp]$ $\not\vdash \{v: \text{int} \mid \perp\}$
<code>1</code>	$\vdash [v: \text{int} \mid v = 1]$ $\vdash \{v: \text{int} \mid v = 1\}$	$\vdash [v: \text{int} \mid \perp]$ $\not\vdash \{v: \text{int} \mid \top\}$	$\vdash \{v: \text{int} \mid \top\}$ $\not\vdash [v: \text{int} \mid v = 1 \vee 2]$	$\vdash [v: \text{int} \mid v = 1 \vee 2]$ $\not\vdash \{v: \text{int} \mid \perp\}$
<code>err</code>	$\vdash [v: \text{int} \mid \perp]$ $\not\vdash \{v: \text{int} \mid \top\}$	$\not\vdash [v: \text{int} \mid \top]$ $\not\vdash \{v: \text{int} \mid v = 1 \vee 2\}$	$\not\vdash [v: \text{int} \mid v = 1 \vee 2]$ $\not\vdash \{v: \text{int} \mid v = 1\}$	$\not\vdash [v: \text{int} \mid v = 1]$ $\not\vdash \{v: \text{int} \mid \perp\}$

metatheory is given in Section 5. A bidirectional typing algorithm is then given in Section 6. We describe details about the implementation of Poirot and provide benchmark results in Section 9. Related work and conclusions are given in Sections 10 and 11.

2 Overview

Before presenting the full details of our type system, we begin with an informal overview of its key features.

Base types. In the following, we write $[v: b \mid \phi]$ to denote the coverage type that qualifies the base type b using the predicate ϕ . As described in the previous section, an application of the primitive built-in generator for random numbers: `int_gen` : `unit` \rightarrow `int` has the coverage type `int_gen ()` : $[v: \text{int} \mid \top]$. We use brackets [...] to emphasize that a coverage type has a different meaning from the types typically found in other refinement type systems [29, 62] where a qualified type b , written as $\{v: b \mid \phi\}$, uses a predicate ϕ to constrain the set of values a program *might* evaluate to. To illustrate this distinction, consider the combinations of expressions and types shown in Table 1. These examples demonstrate the previous observation that it is always possible to strengthen the refinement predicate used in an underapproximate type and weaken such a predicate in an overapproximate type. A similar phenomena appears in IL’s rule of consequence, which inverts the direction of the implications on pre- and postconditions in the overapproximate version of the rule. As a result, the bottom type $[v: \text{int} \mid \perp]$ is the universal supertype in our type hierarchy, as it places no restrictions on the values a term *must* produce. Thus, we sometimes abbreviate $[v: \text{int} \mid \perp]$ as `int`, since the information provided by both types is the same. Importantly, the coverage type for the error term (`err`) can *only* be qualified with \perp , since an erroneous computation is unconstrained with the respect to the values it is obligated to produce.

Coverage types can also qualify inductive datatypes, like lists and trees. In particular, the complete generator for BSTs presented in the introduction can be successfully type-checked using the following result type:

$$[v: \text{int tree} \mid bst(v) \wedge \forall u, mem(v, u) \implies lo < u < hi]$$

where $bst(v)$ and $mem(v, u)$ are *uninterpreted predicates* used to encode semantic properties of the datatype. In the type given above, the qualifier requires that `bst_gen`’s result is a BST (encoded by the predicate $bst(v)$) and that every element u stored in the tree (encoded by the predicate $mem(v, u)$) is between `lo` and `hi`; the coverage type thus constrains the implementation to produce *all* trees that satisfy this qualifier predicate. In contrast, the incomplete version of the generator (i.e., the implementation that does not allow prematurely

```

307 let even_gen () =
308   let (n: int) = int_gen () in
309   let (b: bool) = n mod 2 == 0 in
310   if b then n else err

```

Fig. 3. An even number generator defined in terms of an integer number generator.

terminating tree generation with a `Leaf` node) could only be type-checked using the following (stronger) type:

$$[\nu: \text{int tree} \mid \text{bst}(\nu) \wedge \forall u, \text{mem}(\nu, u) \iff \text{lo} < u < \text{hi}]$$

This signature asserts that all trees produced by the generator are BSTs, that any element contained in the tree is within the interval bounded by `lo` and `hi`, and moreover, any element in that interval *must* be included in the tree. The subtle difference between the two implementations, reflected in the different implication constraints expressed in their respective refinements, precisely captures how their coverage properties differ.

Control Flow. Just as underapproximate coverage types invert the standard overapproximate subtyping relationship, they also invert the standard relationship between a control flow construct and its subexpressions. To see how, consider the simple generator for even numbers shown in Fig. 3. When the integer generator, `int_gen()`, yields an odd number, `even_gen` faults; otherwise it simply returns the generated number. Consider the following type judgment that arises when type checking this program:

$$\begin{aligned} & n: [\nu: \text{int} \mid \top], b: [\nu: \text{bool} \mid \nu \iff n \bmod 2 = 0] \\ & \vdash \text{if } b \text{ then } n \text{ else err} : [\nu: \text{int} \mid \nu \bmod 2 = 0] \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Intuitively, this judgment asserts that the `if` expression covers all even numbers (i.e., has the type $[\nu: \text{int} \mid \nu \bmod 2 = 0]$) assuming that the *local variable* `n` can be instantiated with an arbitrary number, and that the variable `b` is true precisely when `n` is even. Notice how the typing context encodes the potential control-flow path that *must* reach the non-faulting branch of the conditional expression. Enforcing the requirement that the conditional be able to return all even numbers does *not* require each of its branches to be a subtype of the expected type, in contrast to standard type systems. Our type system must instead establish that, *in total*, the values produced by each of the branches cover the even numbers. Because the `false` branch of the conditional faults, it is only typeable at the universal supertype, i.e., $[\nu: \text{int} \mid \perp]$. Thus, if the standard subtyping relationship between this conditional and its branches held, it could only be typed at $[\nu: \text{int} \mid \perp]$! This is not the case in our setting, as the `true` branch contributes all the desired outputs. Formally, this property is checked by the following assumption of the coverage typing rule for conditionals:

$$\begin{aligned} & n: [\nu: \text{int} \mid \top], b: [\nu: \text{bool} \mid \nu \iff n \bmod 2 = 0] \\ & \vdash [\nu: \text{int} \mid (b \wedge \nu = n) \vee (\neg b \wedge \perp)] <: [\nu: \text{int} \mid \nu \bmod 2 == 0] \end{aligned}$$

The $b \wedge \nu = n$ and $\neg b \wedge \perp$ subformulas correspond to the types of the true and false branches², respectively. Taking the disjunction of these two formulas describes the set of

²As is standard in dependent type systems, the types of both branches have been refined to reflect the path conditions under which they will be executed.

values that can be produced by either branch³; this subtyping relationship guarantees this type is at least as large as the type expected by the entire conditional. To check that this subtyping relationship holds, our type checker generates the following formula:

$$\forall v, (v \bmod 2 = 0) \implies (\exists n, \top \wedge \exists b, b \iff n \bmod 2 = 0 \wedge (b \wedge v = n) \vee (\neg b \wedge \perp)) \quad (2)$$

This formula aligns with the intuitive meaning of (1): in our type system, coverage types of variables in the typing context tell us what values they must (at least) produce. When checking whether a particular subtyping or typing relationship holds, we are free to choose *any* instantiation of the variables that entails the desired property. Accordingly, in (2), the variables n and b are *existentially* quantified to indicate there exists an execution path that instantiates these local variables in a way that produces the output v , instead of being universally quantified as they would be in a standard refinement type system.

Function types. To type functions, most refinement type systems add a restricted form of the *dependent function types* found in full-spectrum dependent type systems. Such types allow the qualifiers in the result type of a function to refer to its parameters, enabling the expression of rich safety conditions governing the arguments that may be supplied to the function. To see how this capability might be useful in our setting, consider the test generator `bst_gen` from the introduction. The complete version of this function produces all BSTs whose elements fall between the range specified by its two parameters, `lo` and `hi`. For the bounds `0` and `3`, the application `bst_gen 0 3` can be typed as: $[v: \text{int} \mid \text{bst}(v) \wedge \forall u, \text{mem}(v, u) \implies 0 < u < 3]$. Using the standard typing rule for functions, the only way to encode this relationship in the type of `bst_gen` is:

$$\text{lo}: [v: \text{int} \mid v = 0] \rightarrow \text{hi}: [v: \text{int} \mid v = 3] \rightarrow \\ [v: \text{int tree} \mid \text{bst}(v) \wedge \forall u, \text{mem}(v, u) \implies 0 < u < 3]$$

Of course, this specification fails to account for the behaviors of `bst_gen` when supplied with different bounds: for example, the application `bst_gen 2 7` will fail to typecheck against this type.

Since the desired coverage property of `bst_gen` fundamentally depends on the kinds of inputs given to it, our type system includes dependent products of the form:

$$\text{lo}: \{v: \text{int} \mid \top\} \rightarrow \text{hi}: \{v: \text{int} \mid \text{lo} \leq v\} \rightarrow \\ [v: \text{int tree} \mid \text{bst}(v) \wedge \forall u, \text{mem}(v, u) \implies \text{lo} < u < \text{hi}]$$

We use the notation $\{\dots\}$ to emphasize that the argument types of a dependent arrow have a similar purpose and interpretation as in standard refinement type systems. Thus, the above type can be read as “if the inputs `lo` and `hi` are *any* number such that $\text{lo} \leq \text{hi}$, then the output *must* cover all possible BSTs whose elements are between `lo` and `hi`”. Using this type for `bst_gen` allows our system to seamlessly type-check both `(bst_gen 0 3)` and `(bst_gen 2 7)`. Our typing algorithm will furthermore flag the call `(bst_gen 3 1)` as being ill-typed, since the function’s type dictates that the generator’s second argument (1) *may* only be greater than or equal to its first (3).

³This is similar to how the derived rule of choice in IL uses disjunction to reason about both branches of a nondeterministic choice statement.

```

409 let bst_gen_low_bound (low: int) =
410     let (high: int) = int_gen () in
411     bst_gen low high

```

Fig. 4. This function generates a BST with a supplied lower bound, low.

Function Application. Since the type of a function parameter is interpreted as a normal (overapproximate, “may”) refinement type, while arguments in an application may be typed using (underapproximate, “must”) coverage types, we need to be able to bridge the gap between may and must types when typing function applications. Intuitively, our type system does so by ensuring that the set of values in the coverage type of the argument has a nonempty overlap with the set of possible values expected by the function. We establish this connection by using the fact that the typing context captures the control flow paths that may and must exist when the function is called. To illustrate this intuition concretely, consider the function `bst_gen_low_bound` shown in Fig. 4. This function generates all non-empty BSTs whose elements are integers with the lower bound given by its parameter. The judgment we need to check is of the form:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{bst_gen} : \text{lo} : \{v : \text{int} \mid \top\} \rightarrow \text{hi} : \{v : \text{int} \mid \text{lo} \leq v\} \rightarrow [v : \text{int tree} \mid \dots], \\
 & \text{low} : \{v : \text{int} \mid \top\}, \text{high} : [v : \text{int} \mid \top] \\
 & \vdash \text{bst_gen low high} : \dots
 \end{aligned}$$

Note that the type for `low` is a normal refinement type that specifies a safety condition for function `bst_gen_low_bound`, namely that `low` may be any number. In contrast, the type for `high` is a coverage type, representing the result of `int_gen()` that indicates that it *must* (i.e., guaranteed to) be any possible integer. However, the signature for `bst_gen` demands that parameter `hi` only be supplied values greater than its first argument (`lo`); we incorporate this requirement by *strengthening* `high`’s type (via a subsumption rule) to reflect this additional constraint when typing the body of the `let` expression in which `high` is bound. This strengthening, which is tantamount to a more refined underapproximation, allows us to typecheck the application (`bst_gen low high`) in the following context:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{bst_gen} : \text{lo} : \{v : \text{int} \mid \top\} \rightarrow \text{hi} : \{v : \text{int} \mid \text{lo} \leq v\} \rightarrow [v : \text{int tree} \mid \dots], \\
 & \text{low} : \{v : \text{int} \mid \top\}, \text{high} : [v : \text{int} \mid \text{low} \leq v] \\
 & \vdash \text{bst_gen low high} : \dots
 \end{aligned}$$

The coverage type associated with `high` guarantees that `int_gen()` must produce values greater than `low` (along with possibly other values). To ensure that the result type of the call reflects the underapproximate (coverage) dependences that exist between `low` and `high`, we introduce existential quantifiers in the type’s qualifier:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \dots, \text{low} : \{v : \text{int} \mid \top\} \\
 & \vdash [v : \text{int tree} \mid \text{bst}(v) \wedge \exists \text{high}, \text{low} \leq \text{high} \wedge \forall u, \text{mem}(v, u) \implies \text{low} < u < \text{high}]
 \end{aligned}$$

This type properly captures the behavior of the generator: it is guaranteed to generate all BSTs characterized by a lower bound given `low` such that there exists an upper bound `high` where `low` \leq `high` and in which every element in the tree is contained within these bounds.

460	Variables	x, y, z, f, u, \dots
461	Data constructors	$d ::= () \mid \text{true} \mid \text{false} \mid 0 \mid \text{S} \mid \text{Cons} \mid \text{Nil} \mid \text{Leaf} \mid \text{Node}$
462	Constants	$c ::= \mathbb{B} \mid \mathbb{N} \mid \mathbb{Z} \mid \dots \mid d \bar{c}$
463	Operators	$op ::= d \mid + \mid == \mid < \mid \text{mod} \mid \text{nat_gen} \mid \text{int_gen} \mid \dots$
464	Values	$v ::= c \mid op \mid x \mid \text{fun } (x:\tau) \rightarrow e \mid \text{fix } (f:\tau) \text{ fun } (x:\tau) \rightarrow e$
465	Terms	$e ::= v \mid \text{err} \mid \text{let } x = e \text{ in } e \mid \text{let } x = op \bar{v} \text{ in } e$
466		$\mid \text{let } x = v \text{ in } e \mid \text{match } v \text{ with } \overline{d \bar{y}} \rightarrow e$
467	Base Types	$b ::= \text{unit} \mid \text{bool} \mid \text{nat} \mid \text{int} \mid \text{float} \mid \text{char} \mid \text{string}$
468		$\mid b \times b \mid \{\overline{x:b}\} \mid b \text{ option} \mid b \text{ list} \mid b \text{ tree} \mid \dots$
469	Basic Types	$t ::= b \mid t \rightarrow t$
470	Uninterpreted Functions	$up ::= emp \mid hd \mid mem \mid \dots$
471	Literals	$l ::= c \mid x$
472	Propositions	$\phi ::= l \mid \perp \mid \top \mid op(\bar{l}) \mid up(\bar{x})$
473		$\mid \neg \phi \mid \phi \wedge \phi \mid \phi \vee \phi \mid \phi \implies \phi \mid \forall u:b. \phi \mid \exists u:b. \phi$
474	Refinement Types	$\tau ::= [v: b \mid \phi] \mid \{v: b \mid \phi\} \mid x:\tau \rightarrow \tau$
475	Type Contexts	$\Gamma ::= \emptyset \mid \Gamma, x:\tau$

Fig. 5. λ^U syntax.

485 *Summary.* Coverage types invert many of the expected relationships that are found in a normal
486 refinement type system. Here, qualifiers provide an *underapproximation* of the values that an
487 expression may evaluate to, in contrast to the typically provided *overapproximation*. This,
488 in turn, causes the subtyping relation to invert the standard relationship entailed by logical
489 implication between type qualifiers. Our coverage analysis also considers the *disjunction* of
490 the coverage guarantees provided by the branches of control-flow constructs, instead of their
491 *conjunction*. Finally, when applying a function with a dependent arrow type to a coverage type,
492 we check semantic inclusion between the overapproximate and underapproximate constraints
493 provided by the two types, and manifest the paths that witness the elements guaranteed to be
494 produced by the coverage type through existentially-quantified variables in the application's
495 result type.

497 3 Language

499 *Terms.* In order to formalize our typed-based verification approach of input test generators, we
500 introduce a core calculus for test generators, λ^U . The language, whose syntax is summarized
501 in Fig. 5, is a call-by-value lambda-calculus with pattern-matching, inductive datatypes, and
502 well-founded (i.e., terminating) recursive functions whose argument must be structurally
503 decreasing in all recursive calls made in the function's body. The syntax of λ^U is expressed
504 in monadic normal-form (MNF) [24], a variant of A-Normal Form (ANF) [17] that allows
505 nested let-bindings. Terms in a standard lambda-calculus can be expressed as syntax sugar in
506 ANF, e.g., an application $(e_1 e_2)$ can be defined as:

$$507 e_1 e_2 \doteq \text{let } f = e_1 \text{ in let } x = e_2 \text{ in let } y = f x \text{ in } y$$

To enable type-checking, the parameters of lambda function (i.e. **fun** $(x:\tau) \rightarrow e$) and fixpoint functions (i.e. **fix** $(f:\tau)$ **fun** $(x:\tau) \rightarrow e$) are also notated with coverage types. The language additionally allows faulty programs to be expressed using the error term **err**. As discussed in Sec. 2, this term is important in our investigation because coverage types capture an expression’s reachability properties, and we need to ensure the guarantees offered by such types are robust even in the presence of stuck computations induced by statements like **err**. The language is also equipped with primitive operators to generate natural numbers, integers, etc. (**nat_gen** (), **int_gen** (), ...) that can be used to express various kinds of non-deterministic behavior relevant to test input generation. As an example, the \oplus choice operator used in Fig. 1 can be defined as:

$$e_1 \oplus e_2 \doteq \mathbf{let} \ n = \mathbf{int_gen} \ () \ \mathbf{mod} \ 2 \ \mathbf{in} \ \mathbf{match} \ n \ \mathbf{with} \ 0 \rightarrow e_1 \mid _ \rightarrow e_2$$

Note that the primitive generators of λ^U are completely agnostic to the specific sampling strategy they employ, as long as they ensure every value in their range has a nonzero likelihood of being generated. λ^U has a completely standard small-step operational semantics.

Types. Like other refinement type systems [29], λ^U supports three classes of types: *base types*, *basic types*, and *refinement types*. Base types (b) include primitive types such as **unit**, **bool**, **nat**, etc., product types ($b \times b$), record types $\{\overline{x:b}\}$, and inductive datatypes (e.g., **int list**, **bool tree**, **int list list**, etc.). Basic types (t) extend base types with function types. Refinement types (τ) qualify base types with both underapproximate and overapproximate propositions, expressed as predicates defined in first-order logic (FOL). Function parameters can also be qualified with overapproximate refinements that specify when it is safe to apply this function. In contrast, the return type of a function can only be qualified using an underapproximate refinement, reflecting the coverage property of the function’s result and thus characterizing the values the function is guaranteed to produce. The type context is defined normally, i.e., as a sequence of variable-type bindings consisting of overapproximate refinement types, underapproximate coverage types, and arrow (function) types.

Qualifiers. To express rich shape properties over inductive datatypes, we allow propositions to reference uninterpreted predicates, as it is straightforward to generate verification conditions using these uninterpreted predicates that can be handled by an off-the-shelf theorem prover like Z3 [8]. As we describe in Section 6, our typechecking algorithm imposes additional constraints on the form propositions can take, in order to ensure that its validity is decidable. In particular, we require that uninterpreted predicates in our language are stratified and that the Z3 queries generated by our typechecker to check refinement validity are always over effectively propositional (EPR) sentences (i.e., prenex-quantified formulae of the form $\exists^* \forall^* \varphi$ where φ is quantifier-free).

4 Type System

Similar to other contemporary refinement type systems [29], our type system assumes all terms are well-typed in a basic (aka non-refined) type system⁴, i.e., $\emptyset \vdash_t e : t$. For example, a term e that has refinement type τ has basic type $\lfloor \tau \rfloor$ where $\lfloor \dots \rfloor$ is a type erasure function, as shown in Fig. 6, which erases all qualifiers from refinement types and type contexts.

⁴The basic typing rules, proofs of theorems, and the details of our evaluation are provided in technical report [70].

Type Erasure

$$\boxed{[\tau] \quad [\Gamma]}$$

$$[\{v: b \mid \phi\}] \doteq b \quad [v: b \mid \phi] \doteq b \quad [x:t \rightarrow \tau] \doteq [t] \rightarrow [\tau] \quad [\emptyset] \doteq \emptyset \quad [x:\tau, \Gamma] \doteq x:[\tau], [\Gamma]$$

Well-Formedness

$$\boxed{\vdash^{\text{WF}} \Gamma \quad \Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} \tau}$$

$$\frac{\vdash^{\text{WF}} \Gamma \quad [\Gamma], v:b \vdash_t \phi : \text{bool}}{\Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} [v: b \mid \phi]} \text{WFBASE} \quad \frac{\Gamma, x:\{v: b \mid \phi\} \vdash^{\text{WF}} \tau}{\Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} x:\{v: b \mid \phi\} \rightarrow \tau} \text{WFARG}$$

$$\frac{\Gamma, x:(y:\tau_y \rightarrow \tau) \vdash^{\text{WF}} \tau}{\Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} x:(y:\tau_y \rightarrow \tau) \rightarrow \tau} \text{WFRRES}$$

$$\frac{}{\vdash^{\text{WF}} \emptyset} \text{WFCTXEMP} \quad \frac{\vdash^{\text{WF}} \Gamma \quad \Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} [v: b \mid \phi]}{\vdash^{\text{WF}} \Gamma, x:\{v: b \mid \phi\}} \text{WFCTXOBASE}$$

$$\frac{\vdash^{\text{WF}} \Gamma \quad \Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} [v: b \mid \phi] \quad \text{err} \notin \llbracket [v: b \mid \phi] \rrbracket_{\Gamma}}{\vdash^{\text{WF}} \Gamma, x:\{v: b \mid \phi\}} \text{WFCTXUBASE} \quad \frac{\vdash^{\text{WF}} \Gamma \quad \Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} y:\tau_y \rightarrow \tau}{\vdash^{\text{WF}} \Gamma, x:(y:\tau_y \rightarrow \tau)} \text{WFCTXARR}$$

Subtyping

$$\boxed{\Gamma \vdash \tau_1 <: \tau_2}$$

$$\frac{\llbracket [v: b \mid \phi_1] \rrbracket_{\Gamma} \subseteq \llbracket [v: b \mid \phi_2] \rrbracket_{\Gamma}}{\Gamma \vdash [v: b \mid \phi_1] <: [v: b \mid \phi_2]} \text{SUBUBASE} \quad \frac{\llbracket \{v:b \mid \phi_1\} \rrbracket_{\Gamma} \subseteq \llbracket \{v:b \mid \phi_2\} \rrbracket_{\Gamma}}{\Gamma \vdash \{v:b \mid \phi_1\} <: \{v:b \mid \phi_2\}} \text{SUBOBASE}$$

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash \tau_{21} <: \tau_{11} \quad \Gamma, x:\tau_{21} \vdash \tau_{12} <: \tau_{22}}{\Gamma \vdash x:\tau_{11} \rightarrow \tau_{12} <: x:\tau_{21} \rightarrow \tau_{22}} \text{SUBARR}$$

Disjunction

$$\boxed{\Gamma \vdash \tau_1 \vee \tau_2 = \tau_3}$$

$$\frac{\llbracket [\tau_1] \rrbracket_{\Gamma} \cap \llbracket [\tau_2] \rrbracket_{\Gamma} = \llbracket [\tau_3] \rrbracket_{\Gamma}}{\Gamma \vdash \tau_1 \vee \tau_2 = \tau_3} \text{DISJUNCTION}$$

Fig. 6. Auxiliary typing relations

Despite superficial similarities to other contemporary type systems, the typing rules of λ^U differ in significant ways from those of its peers, due to the fundamental semantic distinction that arises when viewing types as an underapproximation and not overapproximation of program behavior.

Our type system depends on three auxiliary relations shown in Fig. 6. The first group defines well-formedness conditions on type contexts ($\vdash^{\text{WF}} \Gamma$) as well as refinement types under a particular type context ($\Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} \tau$). A type τ that is well-formed under a well-formed type context Γ needs to meet three criteria: (1) the qualifier in τ needs to be well-typed under the erasure of the current typing context in the basic type system (e.g., requirement $[\Gamma], v:b \vdash_t \phi : \text{bool}$ in WFBASE), (2) overapproximate types may only appear in the domain of a function type (WFARG); and, (3) underapproximate coverage types may only appear in the range of a function type (only underapproximate and function type are allowed as parameter type in WFARG and WFRRES respectively). A type context is well-formed when all types in a type context are well-formed under the context derived from the former's bindings, moreover, the denotations⁵ of coverage base types ($[v: b \mid \phi]$) should not include err (WFCTXUBASE).

⁵The definition of a type's denotation is given in Sec. 5.

Table 2. Example typings for λ^U primitives

Constants	$\mathbf{T}_y(\text{true}) = [\nu: \text{bool} \mid \nu]$ $\mathbf{T}_y(8) = [\nu: \text{nat} \mid \nu = 8]...$
Data Constructors	$\mathbf{T}_y([]) = [\nu: b \text{ list} \mid \text{emp}(\nu)]$ $\mathbf{T}_y(\text{Cons}) = x:\{\nu: b \mid \top\} \rightarrow y:\{\nu: b \text{ list} \mid \top\} \rightarrow [\nu: b \text{ list} \mid \text{hd}(\nu, x) \wedge \text{tl}(\nu, y)]...$
Operators	$\mathbf{T}_y(\text{nat_gen}) = [\nu: \text{unit} \mid \top] \rightarrow [\nu: \text{int} \mid 0 \leq \nu]$ $\mathbf{T}_y(+) = x:\{\nu: \text{int} \mid \top\} \rightarrow y:\{\nu: \text{int} \mid \top\} \rightarrow [\nu: \text{int} \mid \nu = x + y]...$

To understand the motivation for this constraint, observe that a type context in our setting provides a witness to feasible execution paths in the form of bindings to local variables. Accordingly, the type context $x:\{\nu: \text{nat} \mid \perp\}$ or $x:\{\nu: \text{nat} \mid \nu > 0\}$, $y:\{\nu: \text{nat} \mid x = 0 \wedge \nu = 2\}$ are not well-formed, as neither context corresponds to a valid manifest execution path. On the other hand, a well-formed type is allowed to include an error term in its denotation, e.g., type $[\nu: \text{nat} \mid \perp]$ is well-formed under type context $x:\{\nu: \text{nat} \mid \nu > 0\}$ as it always corresponds to a valid underapproximation.

Our second set of judgments defines a largely standard subtyping relation based on the underlying denotation of the types being related. In general, an overapproximate type and an underapproximate type are inhabited by incomparable sets of terms, even when they share a qualifier. A non-singleton underapproximate type can only be assigned to nondeterministic terms, while the corresponding overapproximate type can be given to many possible deterministic terms. On the other hand, the unconstrained generator for a base type, e.g., `int_gen()` or `tree_gen()`, can be checked against an underapproximate type qualified with any predicate, but it can only be assigned the overapproximate type qualified with \top . As a consequence, our subtyping relation does not relate overapproximate and underapproximate types, and our typing rules tightly control when one can be treated as another.

The disjunction rule (DISJUNCTION), which was informally introduced in Sec. 2, merges the coverage types found along distinct control paths. Intuitively, the type $[\nu: \text{nat} \mid \nu = 1 \vee \nu = 2]$ is the disjunction of the types $[\nu: \text{nat} \mid \nu = 1]$ and $[\nu: \text{nat} \mid \nu = 2]$. Notice that only an inhabitant of both $[\nu: \text{nat} \mid \nu = 1]$ and $[\nu: \text{nat} \mid \nu = 2]$ should be included in their disjunction: e.g., the term $1 \oplus 2$ is one such inhabitant. Thus, we formally define this relation as the *intersection* of the denotations of two types.

The rules of our type system are defined in Fig. 7, and include typing judgments for terms ($\Gamma \vdash e : \tau$), primitive operators ($\Gamma \vdash op : \tau$), and data constructors ($\Gamma \vdash d : \tau$). All our typing rules assume that terms are well-typed according to the basic type system; the basic type system is completely standard and we omit it here. The rules collectively maintain the invariant that terms can only be assigned a well-formed type. The rules for constants (TCONST), operators (TOP), and data constructors (TD \top) are straightforward. It relies on an auxiliary function, \mathbf{T}_y , to assign types to the primitives of λ^U . Table 2 presents some examples of the typings provided by \mathbf{T}_y . We use uninterpreted predicates in the types of constructors: the types for list constructors, for example, use *emp*, *hd* and *tl*, to precisely capture that `[]` constructs an empty list, and that `(Cons x y)` builds a list containing *x* as its head and *y* as its tail.

The typing rules for function abstraction (TFUN) and error (TERR) are similarly straightforward. In a λ -abstraction, the type of the bound variable (τ_x) is explicitly given. The error term can be assigned an arbitrary bottom coverage base type. The variable rule (TVARBASE)

Typing

$$\begin{array}{c}
\boxed{\Gamma \vdash e : \tau \quad \Gamma \vdash op : \tau \quad \Gamma \vdash d : \tau} \\
\frac{\Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} [v: b \mid \perp]}{\Gamma \vdash \text{err} : [v: b \mid \perp]} \text{TErr} \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} \mathbf{T}y(c)}{\Gamma \vdash c : \mathbf{T}y(c)} \text{TConst} \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} \mathbf{T}y(d)}{\Gamma \vdash d : \mathbf{T}y(d)} \text{TDT} \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} \mathbf{T}y(op)}{\Gamma \vdash op : \mathbf{T}y(op)} \text{TOP} \\
\frac{\Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} [v: b \mid v = x]}{\Gamma \vdash x : [v: b \mid v = x]} \text{TVARBASE} \quad \frac{\Gamma(x) = (a:\tau_a \rightarrow \tau_b) \quad \Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} a:\tau_a \rightarrow \tau_b}{\Gamma \vdash x : (a:\tau_a \rightarrow \tau_b)} \text{TVARFUN} \\
\frac{\Gamma, x:\tau_x \vdash e : \tau \quad \Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} x:\tau_x \rightarrow \tau}{\Gamma \vdash \mathbf{fun} (x:\tau_x) \rightarrow e : (x:\tau_x \rightarrow \tau)} \text{TFUN} \\
\frac{\Gamma, x:\{v:b \mid \phi\}, f:(x:\{v:b \mid v < x \wedge \phi\} \rightarrow \tau) \vdash e : \tau \quad \Gamma \vdash x:\{v:b \mid \phi\} \rightarrow \tau}{\Gamma \vdash \mathbf{fix} (f:(x:\{v:b \mid \phi\} \rightarrow \tau)) \mathbf{fun} (x:\{v:b \mid \phi\}) \rightarrow e : x:\{v:b \mid \phi\} \rightarrow \tau} \text{TFIX} \\
\frac{\emptyset \vdash \tau <: \tau'}{\emptyset \vdash e : \tau \quad \Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} \tau'} \text{TSUB} \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash \tau' <: \tau \quad \Gamma \vdash \tau <: \tau'}{\Gamma \vdash e : \tau \quad \Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} \tau'} \text{TEQ} \\
\frac{\Gamma \vdash e : \tau_1 \quad \Gamma \vdash e : \tau_2}{\Gamma \vdash \tau_1 \vee \tau_2 = \tau \quad \Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} \tau} \text{TMERGE} \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash e_x : \tau_x \quad \Gamma, x:\tau_x \vdash e : \tau}{\Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} \tau} \text{TLETE} \\
\frac{\Gamma \vdash op : a_i:\{v: b_i \mid \phi_i\} \rightarrow \tau_x \quad \forall i, \Gamma \vdash v_i : [v: b_i \mid \phi_i] \quad \Gamma, x:\tau_x [a_i \mapsto v_i] \vdash e : \tau}{\Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} \tau} \text{TAPPOP} \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash v_1 : (\tau_1 \rightarrow \tau_2) \rightarrow \tau_x \quad \Gamma \vdash v_2 : \tau_1 \rightarrow \tau_2 \quad \Gamma, x:\tau_x \vdash e : \tau}{\Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} \tau} \text{TAPPFUN} \\
\frac{\Gamma \vdash v_1 : a:\{v: b \mid \phi\} \rightarrow \tau_x \quad \Gamma \vdash v_2 : [v: b \mid \phi] \quad \Gamma, x:\tau_x [a \mapsto v_2] \vdash e : \tau}{\Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} \tau} \text{TAPP} \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash v : \tau_v \quad \Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} \tau \quad \Gamma, \overline{y:\tau_y} \vdash d_i(\overline{y}) : \tau_v}{\Gamma, \overline{y:\tau_y} \vdash e_i : \tau} \text{TMATCH} \\
\Gamma \vdash \mathbf{let} x = op \overline{v_i} \mathbf{in} e : \tau \quad \Gamma \vdash (\mathbf{match} v \mathbf{with} \overline{d_i \overline{y} \rightarrow e_i}) : \tau
\end{array}$$

Fig. 7. Typing rules

establishes that the variable x in the type context with a base type can also be typed with the tautological qualifier $v = x$ (the rule's well-formedness assumption ensures that x is not free). This judgment allows us to, for example, type the function $\lambda x : \text{nat}.x$ with the type $x:\{v: \text{nat} \mid \top\} \rightarrow [v: \text{nat} \mid v = x]$, indicating that the return value is guaranteed to be exactly equal to the input x . Observe that the type of x under the type context $x:\{v: \text{nat} \mid \top\}$ (generated by the function rule `TFUN`) is *not* $[v: \text{nat} \mid \top]$. We cannot simply duplicate the qualifier for x from the type context here, as this is only sound when types characterize an overapproximation of program behavior. As an example, $\{v: \text{nat} \mid \top\}$ is a subtype of $\{v: \text{nat} \mid v = x\}$ under the type context $x:\{v: \text{nat} \mid \top\}$; in our underapproximate coverage type system, in contrast, $[v: \text{nat} \mid \top]$ is not a subtype of $[v: \text{nat} \mid v = x]$ under the type context $x:\{v: \text{nat} \mid \top\}$.

In a call-by-value language, a variable must refer to the same value throughout its scope; this property extends to the guarantees provided by its coverage type. Consider the following example:

```

 $\nu$  let x = int_gen () in let y = 3 / x in x : [v: int | v = 0]

```

Although x may be bound any to any integer, this program will never evaluate to 0, as the evaluation of the second `let` expression will raise a division-by-zero exception when x is 0. Our type system enforces the invariant that the coverage type of a variable is fixed when it is bound, ensuring that the variable provides consistent coverage guarantees whenever it is subsequently used. In the example above, to ensure safe execution, `int_gen ()` must be assigned a coverage type that excludes 0, i.e., $[v: \text{int} \mid v \neq 0]$. To achieve this, our subsumption rule (TSUB) is restricted to closed terms, permitting us to strengthen the coverage guarantee only when a closed generator like `int_gen ()` is introduced; and disallowing any coverage changes of variable x at the places where it is used.

The typing rule for application (TAPP) requires both its underapproximate argument type and the overapproximate parameter type to have the same qualifier, and furthermore requires that the type of the body (τ) is well-formed under the original type context Γ , enforcing that x (the result of the application) does not appear free in τ . When argument and parameter qualifiers are not identical, a subsumption rule is typically used to bring the two types into alignment. Recall the following example from [Sec. 2](#), suitably modified to conform to λ^U 's syntax:

```
bst_gen : lo:{v: int |  $\top$ }  $\rightarrow$  hi:{v: int |  $lo \leq v$ }  $\rightarrow$  [v: int tree | ...], low : {v: int |  $\top$ }  $\vdash$ 
  let (g: unit  $\rightarrow$  int) = int_gen in let (x: unit) = () in
  let (high: int) = g x in let (y: int tree) = bst_gen low high in y
```

Here, the type of `high`, $[v: \text{int} \mid \top]$ is stronger than the type expected for the second parameter of `bst_gen`, $[v: \text{int} \mid lo \leq v]$. The subsumption rule (TSUB), that would normally allow us to strengthen the type of `high` to align with the required parameter type, is applicable to only closed terms, which `high` is not. For the same reason, we cannot use TSUB to strengthen the type of `high` when it is bound to `g x`. Thankfully, we can strengthen `g` when it is bound to `int_gen`: according to [Table 2](#), the operator `int_gen` has type $\{v: \text{unit} \mid \top\} \rightarrow [v: \text{int} \mid \top]$ and is also closed, and can thus be strengthened via TSUB , allowing us to type the call to `bst_gen` under the following, stronger type context:

```
bst_gen : lo:{v: int |  $\top$ }  $\rightarrow$  hi:{v: int |  $lo \leq v$ }  $\rightarrow$  [v: int tree | ...], low : {v: int |  $\top$ },
g : [v: unit |  $\top$ ][v: int | low  $\leq$  v], x : [v: unit |  $\top$ ], high : [v: int | low  $\leq$  v]  $\vdash$ 
  let (y: int tree) = bst_gen low high in y
```

The subsumption rule allows us to use `int_gen` in a context that requires *fewer* guarantees than `int_gen` actually provides, namely those values of `high` required by the signature of `bst_gen`. Intuitively, since our notion of coverage types records feasible executions in the type context in the form of existentials that serve as witnesses to an underapproximation, the strengthening provided by the subsumption rule establishes an invariant that all bindings introduced into a type context only characterize valid behaviors in a program execution. When coupled with TMERGE , this allows us to *split* a typing derivation into multiple plausible strengthenings when a variable is introduced into the typing context and then *combine* the resulting types to reason about multiple feasible paths.

Now, using TAPP to type `bst_gen low high`, and TVARBASE to type the body of the `let` gives us:

```
bst_gen : lo:{v: int |  $\top$ }  $\rightarrow$  hi:{v: int |  $lo \leq v$ }  $\rightarrow$  [v: int tree | ...],
low : {v: int |  $\top$ }, high : [v: int | low  $\leq$  v],
y : [v: int tree |  $bst(v) \wedge \forall u, mem(v, u) \implies lo < u < hi$ ][ $lo \mapsto low$ ][ $hi \mapsto high$ ]
 $\vdash$  y : [v: int tree |  $v = y$ ]
```

Observe that TVARBASE types the body as: $[v: \text{int tree} \mid v = y]$, which is not closed. To construct a well-formed term, we need a formula equivalent to this type that accounts for the type of y in the current type context. The TEQ rule allows us to interchange formulae that are equivalent under a given type context to ensure the well-formedness of the types constructed. Unlike T_{SUB}, it simply changes the form of a type’s qualifiers, *without altering* the scope of feasible behaviors under the current context. In this example, such an equivalent closed type, given the binding for y in the type context under which the expression is being type-checked, would be:

```
let (y: int tree) = bst_gen low high in y :
  [v: int tree | ∃y, (bst(y) ∧ ∀u, mem(y, u) ⇒ low < u < high) ∧ v = y]
```

With these pieces in hand, we can see that the typing rule for `match` is a straightforward adaptation of the components we have already seen, where the type of matched variable v is assumed to have been strengthened by the rule T_{SUB} to fit the type required to take the i th branch $\Gamma, \overline{y:\tau_y} \vdash d_i(\overline{y}) : \tau_v$. We can also safely assume the type of the branch τ_i is closed under original type context Γ , relying on TEQ to meet this requirement. While T_{MATCH} only allows for a single branch to be typechecked, applying T_{MERGE} allows us to reason about the coverage provided by multiple branches, which have all been typed according to this rule.

As in T_{FUN}, the typing rule for recursive functions (T_{FIX}) requires the types of the self-reference to f and the function parameter x to be explicitly given. Since types in our language serve as witnesses to feasible executions, the result type of any recursive procedure must characterize the set of values the procedure can plausibly return. Thus, the T_{FIX} rule forces its first argument to always decrease according to some well-founded relation \prec . To see why we impose this restriction, consider the function `loop`:

```
let rec loop (n: nat) = loop n
```

Without our termination check, this function can be assigned the following type:

$$\{v: \text{nat} \mid \top\} \rightarrow [v: \text{nat} \mid v = 3]$$

despite the fact that this function never returns 3— or any value at all! The body of this expression can be type-checked under the following type context (via T_{FIX} and T_{FUN}):

$$n: \{v: \text{nat} \mid \top\}, \text{loop}: (n: \{v: \text{nat} \mid \top\} \rightarrow [v: \text{nat} \mid v = 3]) \vdash \text{loop } n : [v: \text{nat} \mid v = 3]$$

This judgment reflects an infinitely looping execution, however. Indeed, the same reasoning allows us to type this function with any result type. Constraining `loop`’s argument type to be decreasing according to \prec yields the following typing obligation:

$$n: \{v: \text{nat} \mid \top\}, \text{loop}: (n: \{v: \text{nat} \mid v \prec n\} \rightarrow [v: \text{nat} \mid v = 3]) \vdash n : [v: \text{nat} \mid v = n]$$

where the qualifiers $v \prec n$ and $v = n$ conflict, raising a type error, and preventing `loop` from being recursively applied to n .

5 Type Soundness

Type Denotations. Assuming a standard typing judgement for basic types, $\emptyset \vdash_{\tau} e : t$, a type denotation for a type τ , $\llbracket \tau \rrbracket$, is a set of closed expressions:

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket \{v: b \mid \phi\} \rrbracket &\doteq \{v \mid \emptyset \vdash_{\tau} v : b \wedge \phi[v \mapsto v]\} \\ \llbracket [v: b \mid \phi] \rrbracket &\doteq \{e \mid \emptyset \vdash_{\tau} e : b \wedge \forall v: b, \phi[v \mapsto v] \implies e \hookrightarrow^* v\} \\ \llbracket [x: \tau_x \rightarrow \tau] \rrbracket &\doteq \{f \mid \emptyset \vdash_{\tau} f : [\tau_x \rightarrow \tau] \wedge \forall v_x \in \llbracket \tau_x \rrbracket \implies f \ v_x \in \llbracket \tau[x \mapsto v_x] \rrbracket\} \end{aligned}$$

817 In the case of an overapproximate refinement type, $\{v:b \mid \phi\}$, the denotation is simply the
 818 set of all values of type b whose elements satisfy the type's refinement predicate (ϕ), when
 819 substituted for all free occurrences of v in ϕ .⁶ Dually, the denotation of an underapproximate
 820 coverage type is the set of expressions that evaluate to v whenever $\phi[v \mapsto v]$ holds, where ϕ
 821 is the type's refinement predicate. Thus, every expression in such a denotation serves as a
 822 witness to a feasible, type-correct, execution. The denotation for a function type is defined in
 823 terms of the denotations of the function's argument and result in the usual way, ensuring that
 824 our type denotation is a logical predicate.
 825

826 *Type Denotations under a Type Context.* The denotation of a refinement type τ under a type
 827 context Γ (written $\llbracket \tau \rrbracket_{\Gamma}$) is:^{7,8}

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \llbracket \tau \rrbracket_{\emptyset} \doteq \llbracket \tau \rrbracket \\
 & \llbracket \tau \rrbracket_{x:\tau_x, \Gamma} \doteq \{e \mid \forall v_x \in \llbracket \tau_x \rrbracket. \mathbf{let} \ x = v_x \ \mathbf{in} \ e \in \llbracket \tau[x \mapsto v_x] \rrbracket_{\Gamma[x \mapsto v_x]}\} && \text{if } \tau \equiv \{v:b \mid \phi\} \\
 & \llbracket \tau \rrbracket_{x:\tau_x, \Gamma} \doteq \{e \mid \exists \hat{e}_x \in \llbracket \tau_x \rrbracket. \forall e_x \in \llbracket \tau_x \rrbracket. \\
 & \qquad \mathbf{let} \ x = e_x \ \mathbf{in} \ e \in \bigcap_{\hat{e}_x \mapsto^* v_x} \llbracket \tau[x \mapsto v_x] \rrbracket_{\Gamma[x \mapsto v_x]}\} && \text{otherwise}
 \end{aligned}$$

835 The denotation of an overapproximate refinement type under a type context is mostly
 836 unsurprising, other than our presentation choice to use a let-binding, rather than substitution,
 837 to construct the expressions included in the denotations.

838 For a coverage type, however, the definition precisely captures our notion of a reachability
 839 witness by explicitly constructing an execution path as a sequence of let-bindings that justifies
 840 the inhabitant of the target type τ . Using let-bindings forces expressions in the denotation to
 841 make consistent choices when evaluated. The existential introduced in the definition captures
 842 the notion of an underapproximation, while the use of set intersection allows us to reason
 843 about non-determinism introduced by primitive generators like `nat_gen ()`.
 844

845 **Example 5.1.** The term $x + 1$ is included in the denotation of the following type:

$$846 \quad [v: \mathbf{nat} \mid v = x + 1 \vee v = x + x]$$

848 under the type context $x : [v: \mathbf{nat} \mid v = 1]$. This is justified by picking 1 for \hat{e}_x , which yields
 849 a set intersection that is equivalent to $\llbracket [v: \mathbf{nat} \mid v = 2] \rrbracket$. Observe that *any* expression in
 850 $\llbracket [v: \mathbf{nat} \mid v = 1] \rrbracket$, e.g. $0 \oplus 1$ and $1 \oplus 2$, yields an expression, $\mathbf{let} \ x = 0 \oplus 1 \ \mathbf{in} \ x + 1$ or
 851 $\mathbf{let} \ x = 1 \oplus 2 \ \mathbf{in} \ x + 1$, included in this intersection.
 852

853 **Example 5.2.** On the other hand, the term x is not a member of the denotation of the type
 854 $[v: \mathbf{nat} \mid v = x + 1 \vee v = x + x]$. To see why, let us pick `nat_gen()` for \hat{e}_x . This yields a set
 855 intersection that is equivalent to $\llbracket [v: \mathbf{nat} \mid \top] \rrbracket$. While specific choices for e_x , e.g., `nat_gen()`,
 856 are included in this denotation, it does not work for all terms $e_x \in \llbracket [v: \mathbf{nat} \mid v = 1] \rrbracket$. As one
 857 example, $0 \oplus 1 \oplus 2$ is an element of this set, but $\mathbf{let} \ x = 0 \oplus 1 \oplus 2 \ \mathbf{in} \ x$ is clearly not a member
 858 of $\llbracket [v: \mathbf{nat} \mid \top] \rrbracket$. Suppose instead that we picked a more restrictive expression for \hat{e}_x , like
 859

860 ⁶The denotation of an overapproximate refinement type is more generally $\{e:b \mid \emptyset \vdash e : b \wedge \forall v:b, e \mapsto^* v \implies \phi[x \mapsto v]\}$. However, because such types are only used for function parameters, and our language syntax
 861 only admits values as arguments, our denotation uses the simpler form.
 862

863 ⁷In the last case, since \hat{e}_x may nondeterministically reduce to multiple values, we employ intersection (not union),
 864 similar to the DISJUNCTION rule.

865 ⁸When reasoning about a subset relation between the denotations of two types under a type context $\llbracket [v: b \mid \phi_1] \rrbracket_{\Gamma} \subseteq \llbracket [v: b \mid \phi_2] \rrbracket_{\Gamma}$
 866 we require that the denotations be computed using the same Γ ; details are provided in the technical
 867 report [70].

the literal 1 from the previous example. Here, it is easy to choose $e_x \in \llbracket [v: \text{nat} \mid v = 1] \rrbracket$ (e.g., the literal 1) such that $\mathbf{let} \ x = e_x \ \mathbf{in} \ x \notin \llbracket [v: \text{nat} \mid v = 2] \rrbracket$.

Our main soundness result establishes the correctness of type-checking in the presence of coverage types with respect to a type's denotation:

Theorem 5.3. [Type Soundness] For all type contexts Γ , terms e and coverage types τ , $\Gamma \vdash e : \tau \implies e \in \llbracket \tau \rrbracket_{\Gamma}$.

It immediately follows that a closed input generator e with coverage type $[v: b \mid \phi]$ must produce every value satisfying ϕ , as desired.

6 Typing Algorithm

The declarative typing rules are highly nondeterministic, relying on a combination of the `TMERGE` and `TSUB` rules to both explore and combine the executions needed to establish the desired coverage properties. In addition, each of the auxiliary typing relations depend on logical properties of the semantic interpretation of types. Any effective type checking algorithm based on these rules must address both of these issues. Our solution to the first problem is to implement a bidirectional type checker [11] whose type synthesis phase characterizes a set of feasible paths and whose type checking phase ensures those paths produce the desired results. Our solution to the second is to encode the logical properties into a *decidable* fragment of first order logic that can be effectively discharged by an SMT solver.

6.1 Bidirectional Typing Algorithm

As is standard in bidirectional type systems, our typing algorithm consists of a type synthesis judgment ($\Gamma \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau$) and a type checking judgment ($\Gamma \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau$) as presented in Fig. 8. Most of rules are similar to the declarative typing rules, e.g., the type synthesis rule `SYNVARBASE` has the same premise as the declarative typing rule `TVARBASE` shown in Fig. 7. We use one type checking rule `CHKMATCH` and one synthesis rule `SYNAPBASE` as examples to illustrate how we convert declarative typing rules into a typing algorithm.

Typing match. As we saw in Sec. 4, applying the declarative typing rule for `match` expressions typically requires first using several other rules to get things into the right form: `TMERGE` is required to analyze and combine the types of each branch, `TSUB` is used to equip each branch with the right typing context, and `TEQ` is used to remove any local or pattern variables from the type of a branch. Our bidirectional type system combines all of these into the single `CHKMATCH` rule shown in Fig. 8. At a high level, this rule synthesizes a type for all the branches and then ensures that, in combination, they cover the desired type.

Similarly to other refinement type systems, when synthesizing the type for the branch for constructor d_i , we use a ghost variable $a: [v: b \mid v = v_a \wedge \psi_i]$ to ensure that the types of any pattern variables \bar{y} are consistent with the parameters of d_i . This strategy allows us to avoid having to apply `TSUB` to focus on a particular branch: instead, we simply infer a type for *each* branch, and then combine them using our disjunction operation. In order for the inferred type of a branch to make sense, we need to remove any occurrences of pattern variables or the ghost variable a . To do, we use the `Ex` function, which intuitively allows us to embed information from the typing context into a type. This function takes as input a typing context Γ and type τ and produces an equivalent type in which pattern and ghost variables do not

Type Synthesis	$\boxed{\Gamma \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau}$	Type Check	$\boxed{\Gamma \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau}$
$\frac{\Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} \mathbf{Ty}(c)}{\Gamma \vdash c \Rightarrow \mathbf{Ty}(c)}$	$\text{SYNCONST} \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} [v: b \mid \perp]}{\Gamma \vdash \text{err} \Rightarrow [v: b \mid \perp]}$	$\frac{\Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} [v: b \mid v = x]}{\Gamma \vdash x \Rightarrow [v: b \mid v = x]}$	SYNVARBASE
$\frac{\Gamma(x) = a: \tau_a \rightarrow \tau_b \quad \Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} a: \tau_a \rightarrow \tau_b}{\Gamma \vdash x \Rightarrow a: \tau_a \rightarrow \tau_b}$	SYNVARFUN	$\frac{\Gamma, x: \{v: b \mid \top\} \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau \quad \Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} x: \{v: b \mid \top\} \rightarrow \tau}{\Gamma \vdash \lambda x: b. e \Rightarrow x: \{v: b \mid \top\} \rightarrow \tau}$	CHKFUN
$\frac{\Gamma \vdash v_1 \Rightarrow \tau_2 \rightarrow \tau_x \quad [\tau_2] \notin b \quad \Gamma \vdash v_2 \Leftarrow \tau_2 \quad \Gamma' = x: \tau_x \quad \Gamma, \Gamma' \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau \quad \tau' = \mathbf{Ex}(\Gamma', \tau)}{\Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} \tau'}$	SYNAPPFUN	$\frac{\Gamma \vdash v_1 \Rightarrow a: \{v: b \mid \phi\} \rightarrow \tau_x \quad \Gamma' = a: [v: b \mid v = v_2 \wedge \phi], x: \tau_x \quad \Gamma, \Gamma' \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau \quad \tau' = \mathbf{Ex}(\Gamma', \tau)}{\Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} \tau'}$	SYNAPPBASE
$\frac{\mathbf{Ty}(op) \Rightarrow \overline{a_i: \{v: b_i \mid \phi_i\}} \rightarrow \tau_x \quad \Gamma' = a_i: [v: b_i \mid v = v_i \wedge \phi_i], x: \tau_x \quad \Gamma, \Gamma' \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau \quad \tau' = \mathbf{Ex}(\Gamma', \tau)}{\Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} \tau'}$	SYNAPPOP	$\frac{\Gamma \vdash e_x \Rightarrow \tau_x \quad \Gamma' = x: \tau_x \quad \Gamma, \Gamma' \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau \quad \tau' = \mathbf{Ex}(\Gamma', \tau)}{\Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} \tau'}$	SYNLETE
$\frac{\forall i, \mathbf{Ty}(d_i) = \overline{y: \{v: b_y \mid \theta_y\}} \rightarrow [v: b \mid \psi_i] \quad \Gamma'_i = \overline{y: [v: b_y \mid \theta_y], a: [v: b \mid v = v_a \wedge \psi_i]} \quad \Gamma, \Gamma'_i \vdash e_i \Rightarrow \tau_i \quad \tau'_i = \mathbf{Ex}(\Gamma'_i, \tau_i) \quad \Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} \mathbf{Disj}(\overline{\tau'_i})}{\Gamma \vdash \mathbf{match} \ v_a \ \mathbf{with} \ \overline{d_i \ \bar{y} \rightarrow e_i} \Rightarrow \mathbf{Disj}(\overline{\tau'_i})}$	SYNMATCH	$\frac{\emptyset \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau \quad \Gamma \vdash \tau <: \tau' \quad \Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} \tau'}{\Gamma \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau'}$	CHKSUB
$\frac{\forall i, \mathbf{Ty}(d_i) = \overline{y: \{v: b_y \mid \theta_y\}} \rightarrow [v: b \mid \psi_i] \quad \Gamma'_i = \overline{y: [v: b_y \mid \theta_y], a: [v: b \mid v = v_a \wedge \psi_i]} \quad \Gamma, \Gamma'_i \vdash e_i \Rightarrow \tau_i \quad \tau'_i = \mathbf{Ex}(\Gamma'_i, \tau_i) \quad \Gamma \vdash \mathbf{Disj}(\overline{\tau'_i}) <: \tau' \quad \Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} \tau'}{\Gamma \vdash \mathbf{match} \ v_a \ \mathbf{with} \ \overline{d_i \ \bar{y} \rightarrow e_i} \Leftarrow \tau'}$	CHKMATCH	$\frac{\Gamma, x: \tau_x \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau \quad \Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} x: \tau_x \rightarrow \tau}{\Gamma \vdash \lambda x: [\tau_x]. e \Leftarrow (x: \tau_x \rightarrow \tau)}$	CHKFUN
$\frac{\Gamma \vdash \lambda x: b. \lambda f: (b \rightarrow [\tau]). e \Leftarrow (x: \{v: b \mid \phi\}) \rightarrow f: (x: \{v: b \mid v \prec x \wedge \phi\} \rightarrow \tau) \rightarrow \tau}{\Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} x: \{v: b \mid \phi\} \rightarrow \tau}$	CHKFIX	$\frac{\Gamma \vdash \mathbf{fix} f: (b \rightarrow [\tau]). \lambda x: b. e \Leftarrow (x: \{v: b \mid \phi\}) \rightarrow \tau}{\Gamma \vdash \mathbf{fix} f: (b \rightarrow [\tau]). \lambda x: b. e \Leftarrow (x: \{v: b \mid \phi\}) \rightarrow \tau}$	CHKFIX

Fig. 8. Bidirectional Typing Rules

appear free. Finally, CHKMATCH uses \mathbf{Disj} to ensure that the combination of the types of all the branches cover the required type $\Gamma \vdash \mathbf{Disj}(\overline{\tau'_i}) <: \tau$.

Example 6.1. Consider how we might check that the body of the generator for even numbers introduced in Sec. 2 has the expected type $[v: \text{int} \mid v \bmod 2 = 0]$:⁹

```

int_gen: {v: unit | T} → [v: int | T] ⊢
  let (n: int) = int_gen() in let (b: bool) = n mod 2 == 0 in
  match b with true -> err | false -> n ← [v: int | v mod 2 = 0]

```

Our typing algorithm first adds the local variable n and b to the type context, and then checks the pattern-matching expression against the given type:

⁹We have replaced the `if` from the original example with a `match` expression, to be consistent with the syntax of λ^U .

970 $\text{int_gen}:\{\nu: \text{unit} \mid \top\} \rightarrow [\nu: \text{int} \mid \top], n: [\nu: \text{int} \mid \top], b: [\nu: \text{bool} \mid \nu \iff n \bmod 2 = 0] \vdash$
 971 $\text{match } b \text{ with true } \rightarrow \text{err} \mid \text{false } \rightarrow n \Leftarrow [\nu: \text{int} \mid \nu \bmod 2 = 0]$

972 The `CHKMATCH` rule first synthesizes types for the two branches separately. Inferring a type
 973 of the first branch using the existing type context:
 974

975 $\dots, b: [\nu: \text{bool} \mid \nu \iff n \bmod 2 = 0], b': [\nu: \text{bool} \mid \nu = b \wedge \nu] \vdash \text{err} \Rightarrow [\nu: \text{int} \mid \perp]$

976 adds a ghost variable b' to reflect the fact that $n \bmod 2$ must be equal to 0 in this branch. By
 977 next applying the `TERR` rule, our algorithm infers the type $[\nu: \text{int} \mid \perp]$ for this branch. The
 978 rule next uses `Ex` to manifest b' in the inferred type, encoding the path constraints under
 979 which this type holds (i.e. b is true).
 980

981 $\dots, b: [\nu: \text{bool} \mid \nu \iff n \bmod 2 = 0], b': [\nu: \text{bool} \mid \nu = b \wedge \nu] \vdash$
 982 $\text{err} \Rightarrow [\nu: \text{int} \mid \exists b', b' = b \wedge b' \wedge \perp]$

983 Thus, the synthesized type for the first branch is $[\nu: \text{int} \mid b \wedge \perp]$ modulo some trivial
 984 simplification. The type of the second branch provides a better demonstration of why `Ex` is
 985 needed:
 986

987 $\dots, b: [\nu: \text{bool} \mid \nu \iff n \bmod 2 = 0], b': [\nu: \text{bool} \mid \nu = b \wedge \neg \nu] \vdash$
 988 $n \Rightarrow [\nu: \text{int} \mid \nu = n]$

989 After applying `Ex`, the inferred type is $[\nu: \text{int} \mid \exists b', b' = b \wedge \neg b' \wedge \nu = n]$; after simplifica-
 990 tion, this becomes $[\nu: \text{int} \mid \neg b \wedge \nu = n]$. The disjunction of these two types:
 991

992 $\text{Disj}([\nu: \text{int} \mid b \wedge \perp], [\nu: \text{int} \mid \neg b \wedge \nu = n]) = [\nu: \text{int} \mid (b \wedge \perp) \vee (\neg b \wedge \nu = n)]$
 993

994 results in exactly the type shown in [Sec. 2](#). This can be then successfully checked against the
 995 target type $[\nu: \text{nat} \mid \nu \bmod 2 = 0]$.
 996

997 *Application.* Our type synthesis rules for function application adopt a strategy similar to
 998 `CHKMATCH`'s, trying to infer the strongest type possible for an expression that uses the result
 999 of a function application. The rule for a function whose parameter is an overapproximate
 1000 refinement type (`SYNAPPBASE`) is most interesting, since it has to bridge the gap with an
 1001 argument that has an underapproximate coverage type. When typing e , the expression that
 1002 uses the result of the function call, the rule augments the typing context with a ghost variable
 1003 a . This variable records that the coverage type of the argument must overlap with the type
 1004 expected by the function (both must satisfy the refinement predicate ϕ): if this intersection is
 1005 empty, i.e., the type of a is equivalent to \perp , we will fail to infer a type for e , as no type will
 1006 be well-formed in this context. As with `CHKMATCH`, `SYNAPPBASE` uses `Ex` to ensure that it
 1007 does not infer a type that depends on a .
 1008

1009

6.2 Auxiliary Typing Functions

1010

1011 The auxillary `Disj` and `Ex` operations are a straightforward syntactic transformations; their
 1012 full definitions can be found in the technical report [70]. More interesting is how we algorithmically
 1013 check well-formedness and subtyping. Our type checking algorithm translates both
 1014 obligations into logical formulae that can be discharged by a SMT solver. Both obligations are
 1015 encoded by the `Subtyping` subroutine shown in [Algo 1](#). `Subtyping`($\Gamma, [\nu: b \mid \phi_1], [\nu: b \mid \phi_2]$)
 1016 encodes the bindings in Γ in the typing context from right to left, before checking whether ϕ_1
 1017 implies ϕ_2 . Variables with function types, on the other hand, are omitted entirely, as qualifiers
 1018 cannot have function variables in FOL. Variables with an overapproximate (underapproximate)
 1019
 1020

Algorithm 1: Subtyping Query Encoding

Inputs : A type context Γ , and two base coverage types $[v: b \mid \phi_1]$ and $[v: b \mid \phi_2]$.
Output : A FOL formula that can be automated checked by SMT solver.

```

1 Procedure Subtyping( $\Gamma, [v: b \mid \phi_1], [v: b \mid \phi_2]$ ) :=
2   match  $\Gamma$ :
3     case  $\emptyset$  do
4       return  $\forall v: b, \phi_2 \implies \phi_1$ ;
5     case  $\Gamma, x: (a: \tau_a \rightarrow \tau)$  do
6        $\phi \leftarrow$  Subtyping( $(\Gamma, [v: b \mid \phi_1], [v: b \mid \phi_2])$ );
7       return  $\phi$ ;
8     case  $\Gamma, x: \{v: b_x \mid \phi_x\}$  do
9        $\tau_1 \leftarrow [v: b \mid \forall x: b_x, \phi_x [v \mapsto x] \implies \phi_1]$ ;
10       $\tau_2 \leftarrow [v: b \mid \forall x: b_x, \phi_x [v \mapsto x] \implies \phi_2]$ ;
11      return Subtyping( $\Gamma, [v: b \mid \tau_1], [v: b \mid \tau_2]$ );
12     case  $\Gamma, x: [v: b_x \mid \phi_x]$  do
13        $\tau_1 \leftarrow [v: b \mid \exists x: b_x, \phi_x [v \mapsto x] \wedge \phi_1]$ ;
14        $\tau_2 \leftarrow [v: b \mid \exists x: b_x, \phi_x [v \mapsto x] \wedge \phi_2]$ ;
15       return Subtyping( $\Gamma, [v: b \mid \tau_1], [v: b \mid \tau_2]$ );

```

type are translated as a universally (existential) quantified variable, and are encoded into the refinement of both coverage types.

Example 6.2. Consider the subtyping obligation generated by Example 6.1 above:

$$\text{int_gen}: \{v: \text{unit} \mid \top\} \rightarrow [v: \text{int} \mid \top], n: [v: \text{int} \mid \top], b: [v: \text{bool} \mid v \iff n \bmod 2 = 0] \vdash \\ [v: \text{int} \mid (b \wedge \perp) \vee (\neg b \wedge v = n)] <: [v: \text{int} \mid v \geq 0]$$

This obligation is encoded by the following call to **Subtyping**

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Subtyping}(\\ & \quad \text{int_gen}: \{v: \text{unit} \mid \top\} \rightarrow [v: \text{int} \mid \top], n: [v: \text{int} \mid \top], b: [v: \text{bool} \mid v \iff n \bmod 2 = 0], \\ & \quad [v: \text{int} \mid (b \wedge \perp) \vee (\neg b \wedge v = n)], [v: \text{int} \mid v \geq 0] \\ & \equiv \text{Subtyping}(\text{int_gen}: \{v: \text{unit} \mid \top\} \rightarrow [v: \text{int} \mid \top], n: [v: \text{int} \mid \top], \\ & \quad [v: \text{int} \mid \exists b, b \iff n \bmod 2 = 0 \wedge (b \wedge \perp) \vee (\neg b \wedge v = n)], \\ & \quad [v: \text{int} \mid \exists b, b \iff n \bmod 2 = 0 \wedge v \geq 0]) \\ & \equiv \text{Subtyping}(\text{int_gen}: \{v: \text{unit} \mid \top\} \rightarrow [v: \text{int} \mid \top], \\ & \quad [v: \text{int} \mid \exists n, \top \wedge \exists b, b \iff n \bmod 2 = 0 \wedge (b \wedge \perp) \vee (\neg b \wedge v = n)], \\ & \quad [v: \text{int} \mid \exists n, \top \wedge \exists b, b \iff n \bmod 2 = 0 \wedge v \geq 0]) \\ & \equiv \text{Subtyping}(\emptyset, [v: \text{int} \mid \exists n, \top \wedge \exists b, b \iff n \bmod 2 = 0 \wedge (b \wedge \perp) \vee (\neg b \wedge v = n)], \\ & \quad [v: \text{int} \mid \exists n, \top \wedge \exists b, b \iff n \bmod 2 = 0 \wedge v \geq 0]) \\ & \equiv \forall v, \exists n, \top \wedge \exists b, b \iff n \bmod 2 = 0 \wedge v \geq 0 \implies \\ & \quad \exists n, \top \wedge \exists b, b \iff n \bmod 2 = 0 \wedge (b \wedge \perp) \vee (\neg b \wedge v = n) \end{aligned}$$

This is equivalent to formula (2) from Sec. 2:

$$\forall v, (v \geq 0) \implies (\exists n, \exists b, b \iff n \bmod 2 = 0 \wedge (b \wedge \perp) \vee (\neg b \wedge v = n))$$

Using **Subtyping**, it is straightforward to discharge well-formedness and subtyping obligations using the rules shown in Fig. 9. In the case of WFBASE, for example, observe

$$\begin{array}{c}
1072 \quad \frac{\not\models \text{Subtyping}(\Gamma, [v: b \mid \perp], [v: b \mid \phi])}{\text{err} \notin \llbracket [v: b \mid \phi] \rrbracket_{\Gamma}} \quad \frac{\models \text{Subtyping}(\Gamma, [v: b \mid \phi_1], [v: b \mid \phi_2])}{\Gamma \vdash [v: b \mid \phi_1] <: [v: b \mid \phi_2]} \\
1073 \\
1074 \\
1075 \quad \frac{\models \text{Subtyping}(\Gamma, [v: b \mid \phi_2], [v: b \mid \phi_1])}{\Gamma \vdash \{v: b \mid \phi_1\} <: \{v: b \mid \phi_2\}} \\
1076 \\
1077 \\
1078 \\
1079
\end{array}$$

Fig. 9. Auxiliary Algorithmic Typing Functions

1080 that the error term `err` is always an inhabitant of the type $[v: b \mid \perp]$ for arbitrary base type b .
1081 Thus, to check the last assumption of `WFBASE`, it suffices to iteratively check if any coverage
1082 types in the type context are a supertype of their associated bottom type.
1083

1084 Discharging subtyping obligations is slightly more involved, as we need to ensure that the
1085 formulas sent to the SMT solver are decidable. Observe that in order to produce effectively
1086 decidable formulas, the encoding strategy realized by `Subtyping` always generates a formula
1087 of the form $\forall \bar{x}. \exists \bar{y}. \phi$, i.e. it does not allow for arbitrary quantifier alternations. To ensure that
1088 this is sound strategy, we restrict all overapproximate refinement types in a type context to
1089 not have any free variables that have a coverage type. This constraint allows us to safely lift
1090 all universal quantifiers to the top level, thus avoiding arbitrary quantifier alternations.

1091 As an example of a scenario disallowed by this restriction, consider the following type
1092 checking judgment:
1093

$$1094 \quad x: [v: \text{nat} \mid v > 0] \vdash \lambda y : \text{nat}. x + y \Leftarrow y: \{v: \text{nat} \mid v > x + 1\} \rightarrow [v: \text{nat} \mid \phi]$$

1095 This judgment produces the following subtyping check:
1096

$$1097 \quad x: [v: \text{nat} \mid v > 0], y: \{v: \text{nat} \mid v > x + 1\} \vdash [v: \text{nat} \mid v = x + y] <: [v: \text{nat} \mid \phi]$$

1098 where the normal refinement type $\{v: \text{nat} \mid v > x + 1\}$ in the type context has free variable x
1099 that has coverage type. Evaluating this judgment entails solving the formula:
1100

$$1101 \quad \forall v, (\exists x, x > 0 \wedge (\forall y, y > x + 1 \implies \phi)) \implies (\exists x, x > 0 \wedge (\forall y, y > x + 1 \implies v = x + y))$$

1102 which is not decidable due to the quantifier alternation $\forall v \exists x \forall y$.
1103

1104 **Theorem 6.3.** [Soundness of Algorithmic Typing] For all type context Γ , term e and coverage
1105 type τ , $\Gamma \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau \implies \Gamma \vdash e : \tau$
1106

1107 **Theorem 6.4.** [Completeness of Algorithmic Typing] Assume an oracle for all formulas
1108 produced by the `Subtyping` subroutine. Then for any type context Γ , term e and coverage
1109 type τ , $\Gamma \vdash e : \tau \implies \Gamma \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau$.
1110

1111 7 Polymorphic Coverage Type

1112 Most mainstream PBT frameworks provide a set of combinators that enable users to
1113 compositionally build test generators. For example, the QCheck framework provides a `union`
1114 combinator shown in Fig. 10 that produces a new generator which covers the combined test
1115 cases of two test input generators. Unlike \oplus which takes two base values as arguments, the
1116 `union` combinator combines two input generators, defined as function values. As shown in
1117 Fig. 10, the `union` combinator is polymorphic and cannot be assigned a (principal) type in
1118 the monomorphic coverage type system we have discussed so far. As a consequence, we need
1119 to extend this type system in order to, e.g., type the simple generator on lines 7-9.
1120
1121
1122

```

1123 1   val union: (unit -> 'a) -> (unit -> 'a) -> (unit -> 'a)
1124 2   let union g1 g2 = fun () -> (g1 () ⊕ g2 ())
1125 3
1126 4   val pos_gen: unit -> int (* positive number generator *)
1127 5   val neg_gen: unit -> int (* negative number generator *)
1128 6
1129 7   let bool_gen = union (fun () -> true) (fun () -> false)
1130 8   let nat_gen = union pos_gen (fun () -> 0)
1131 9   let int_gen = union neg_gen nat_gen

```

Fig. 10. A union combinator example.

To support this flexibility, we extend this type system to align with how OCaml implements polymorphism. Thus, a polymorphic term is assigned a *principal* type (i.e., a most general type) that includes universally quantified type variables like 'a.

Example 7.1. In this extended type system, the non-deterministic choice operator \oplus is now assigned the following polymorphic function coverage type:

$$\tau_{\oplus} \doteq x:\{v: 'a \mid \top\} \rightarrow y:\{v: 'a \mid \top\} \rightarrow [v: 'a \mid v = x \vee v = y]$$

The type τ_{\oplus} imposes no constraint on its two parameters x and y , and guarantees the return value (v) must cover both (i.e., $v = x \vee v = y$).

While type polymorphism is sufficient to capture the basic behavior of generator combinators, it falls short in a type system, where we aim to specify and provide coverage guarantees. Consider lines 8-9 in Fig. 10: the `union` combinator combines a generator that produces only positive integers (`pos_gen`) with the constant generator that always returns 0 (`fun () -> 0`), to build a natural number generator (`nat_gen`). It is then used again to create an integer generator (`int_gen`) from a negative number generator (`neg_gen`) and the aforementioned natural number generator. Thus, `union` takes test generators with *arbitrary* coverage guarantees, and build generator whose coverage guarantees combines those guarantees.

Our goal is to assign the `union` combinator a principal coverage type τ_{union} that reflects that it builds a generator that returns a superset of the values produced by its arguments. This guarantee is similar to that of the non-deterministic choice operator \oplus shown in Example 7.1; but because the `union` combinator takes functions as parameters, the analog of the qualifier “ $v = x \vee v = y$ ” for the `union` combinator cannot be expressed in our current qualifier language. One potential solution is to add union and intersection types (e.g., $\tau \sqcap \tau$ and $\tau \sqcup \tau$) into our type system, but this strategy will not work for more complicated combinators like `bind`, `frequency`, and `fix` shown in Fig. 2.

To address this, we draw inspiration from other variants of refinement type systems (Kaki and Jagannathan [30] and Vazou et al. [61]) and introduce *qualifier polymorphism* to allow type to be parameterized over *predicate variables*. With this extension, the principal type of τ_{union} becomes:

$$\tau_{\text{union}} \doteq \forall P_1 P_2 : 'a \rightarrow \text{bool}. (\text{unit} \rightarrow [v: 'a \mid P_1(v)]) \rightarrow (\text{unit} \rightarrow [v: 'a \mid P_2(v)]) \rightarrow (\text{unit} \rightarrow [v: 'a \mid P_1(v) \vee P_2(v)])$$

Here, P_1 and P_2 are universally quantified predicate variable of type $'a \rightarrow \text{bool}$. This type states that “for all possible qualifiers $P_1(v)$ and $P_2(v)$, if the two input generators cover $P_1(v)$

1174	Type Variable	'a', 'b', 'c', ...
1175	Base Types	$b ::= 'a \mid \text{unit} \mid \text{bool} \mid \text{nat} \mid \text{int} \mid b \text{ list} \mid b \text{ tree} \mid \dots$
1176	Basic Types	$t ::= b \mid t \rightarrow t \mid 'a.t$
1177	Predicate Variable	P, \dots
1178	Predicates	$\text{pred} ::= P \mid \overline{\lambda x}. \phi$
1179	Qualifier	$\phi ::= l \mid \perp \mid \top \mid \text{op}(\overline{l}) \mid \text{up}(\overline{x}) \mid \neg \phi \mid \phi \wedge \phi \mid \phi \vee \phi \mid \phi \implies \phi$
1180		$\mid \forall u:b. \phi \mid \exists u:b. \phi \mid \text{pred}(\overline{l})$
1181	Refinement Types	$\tau ::= [\nu: b \mid \phi] \mid \{\nu: b \mid \phi\} \mid x:\tau \rightarrow \tau \mid 'a.\tau \mid \forall P: (\overline{b} \rightarrow \text{bool}). \tau$
1182	Type context	$\Gamma ::= \emptyset \mid \Gamma, x:\tau \mid \Gamma, P:t \mid \Gamma, 'a$
1183		
1184		
1185		
1186		
1187		
1188		
1189		

Fig. 11. Extended λ^U syntax.

and $P_2(\nu)$ respectively, then the generator that results from combining them with a union operation covers $P_1(\nu) \vee P_2(\nu)$ ".

Much like type variables, predicate variable must appear at the front of the type and be instantiated with concrete qualifiers during function application. For instance, when applying union combinator on line 8 in Fig. 10, we instantiate the predicate variables according to the following assignment:

$$P_1 \mapsto \lambda \nu. 0 < \nu \quad \text{and} \quad P_2 \mapsto \lambda \nu. \nu = 0$$

This allows us to assign union combinator the following coverage type:

$$\tau_{\text{union}_1} \doteq (\text{unit} \rightarrow [\nu: \text{int} \mid 0 < \nu]) \rightarrow (\text{unit} \rightarrow [\nu: \text{int} \mid \nu = 0]) \rightarrow (\text{unit} \rightarrow [\nu: \text{int} \mid 0 \leq \nu])$$

The rest of program can be checked using this type, which align the types of `neg_gen` and `fun ()` $\rightarrow \mathbb{0}$. Our extended bidirectional typing rules can automatically infer predicate variable assignments from the qualifier in the corresponding arguments using a simple form of syntactic unification, which we discuss below.

7.1 Extended Type Syntax

The syntax of our extended type system is presented in Fig. 11, with new additions highlighted in green.

Basic Types. Following the conventions of standard polymorphic type systems [50], the basic type system of λ^U supports both type variables ('a) and type quantification ('a.t). The type variable 'a in our type system can be used in refinement types $[\nu: 'a \mid \phi]$, and thus can only be instantiated with base type (b). As in OCaml, type and predicate quantifiers are omitted when the context is clear, e.g., $'a.\forall P: 'a \rightarrow \text{bool}.\text{unit} \rightarrow [\nu: 'a \mid P(\nu)]$ is written as $\text{unit} \rightarrow [\nu: 'a \mid P(\nu)]$.

Qualifiers and Refinement Types. In addition to supporting type quantification (e.g., 'a. τ), coverage refinement type also allow quantified *predicate variables* P . As is standard, *predicates* are functions (e.g., $\overline{\lambda x}.\phi$) whose parameters must be base types arguments and which return boolean values ($\overline{b} \rightarrow \text{bool}$). Fully applied predicate variables may appear in

Well-Formedness

$$\begin{array}{c}
\boxed{\Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} t \quad \Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} \tau \quad \vdash^{\text{WF}} \Gamma} \\
\frac{\text{FreeTypeVar}(t) \subseteq \Gamma}{\Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} t} \text{WF}_{\text{BASICTYPE}} \quad \frac{\vdash^{\text{WF}} \Gamma \quad [\Gamma], \nu: b \vdash_{\tau} \phi : \text{bool}}{\Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} b} \text{WF}_{\text{BASE}} \\
\frac{\Gamma, \bar{a} \vdash^{\text{WF}} \tau \quad \text{no type quantification in } \tau}{\Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} \bar{a}.\tau} \text{WF}_{\text{POLYTYPE}} \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} [\nu: b \mid \phi] \quad \Gamma, P:\bar{b} \rightarrow \text{bool} \vdash^{\text{WF}} \tau \quad \text{no predicate quantification in } \tau}{\Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} \forall P:\bar{b} \rightarrow \text{bool}.\tau} \text{WF}_{\text{POLYPRED}}
\end{array}$$

Subtyping

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} \tau[a \mapsto b]}{\Gamma \vdash a.\tau <: \tau[a \mapsto b]} \text{SUB}_{\text{POLYTYPE}} \quad \frac{\Gamma, \bar{x}:\bar{b} \vdash^{\text{WF}} \phi}{\Gamma \vdash \forall P:\bar{b} \rightarrow \text{bool}.\tau <: \tau[P \mapsto \bar{\lambda}x.\phi]} \text{SUB}_{\text{POLYPRED}} \quad \boxed{\Gamma \vdash \tau_1 <: \tau_2}$$

Typing

$$\frac{\Gamma, 'a \vdash e : \tau \quad \Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} \tau}{\Gamma \vdash e : 'a.\tau} \text{TP}_{\text{POLYTYPE}} \quad \frac{\Gamma, P:\bar{b} \rightarrow \text{bool} \vdash e : \tau \quad \Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} \tau}{\Gamma \vdash e : \forall P:\bar{b} \rightarrow \text{bool}.\tau} \text{TP}_{\text{POLYPRED}} \quad \boxed{\Gamma \vdash e : \tau}$$

Fig. 12. Extended typing relations

qualifiers, like $P(\bar{l})$, analogous to primitive operators (*op*). Predicate application $(\bar{\lambda}x.\phi)(\bar{l})$ is simplified as $\phi[x \mapsto \bar{l}]$. Notably, the extension of the qualifier language yields both universal (for type-checking polymorphic functions) and existential (for type-checking polymorphic function application) quantified type variables and predicate variables. Our subtyping rules instantiate these variables such that derived verification conditions only contain universal quantified variables. Type and predicate variables are encoded as *uninterpreted sorts* and *uninterpreted predicates* in the verification conditions generated by our type system, ensuring that type-checking remains within the decidable fragment of first order logic.

Type context and type erasure function. To support these extensions, the type context Γ is extended to include type variables ($\Gamma, 'a$) as well as predicate variables ($\Gamma, P:t$). The updated type erasure function $[\tau]$ preserves all quantified type variables and discards all quantified predicate variables.

7.2 Extended Typing Rules

The introduction of polymorphism induces the three new sets of typing rules shown in Fig. 12. The additional well-formedness $\text{WF}_{\text{POLYTYPE}}$ and $\text{WF}_{\text{POLYPRED}}$ rules ensure that refinement types are in prenex normal form, i.e., all quantifiers appear at the front of types. The subtyping extensions are also straightforward: the $\text{SUB}_{\text{POLYTYPE}}$ rule permits instantiating type variables with any valid base type, while the $\text{SUB}_{\text{POLYPRED}}$ rule allows a predicate variable P to be instantiated with any well-formed predicate $\bar{\lambda}x.\phi$. Finally, we have two new declarative typing rules ($\text{TP}_{\text{POLYTYPE}}$ and $\text{TP}_{\text{POLYPRED}}$) that move type and predicates quantifiers from the type into the type context.

1276 *Type Denotation and Soundness.* The extended denotational semantics for types is:

$$1277 \quad \llbracket 'a.\tau \rrbracket \doteq \bigcup_b \llbracket \tau \llbracket 'a \mapsto b \rrbracket \rrbracket \quad \text{where } b \text{ contains no type variables}$$

$$1280 \quad \llbracket \forall P: (\bar{b} \rightarrow \text{bool}).\tau \rrbracket \doteq \bigcup_{\phi} \llbracket \tau \llbracket P \mapsto \overline{\lambda x}.\phi \rrbracket \rrbracket \quad \text{where } \overline{x:\bar{b}} \vdash_{\tau} \phi : \text{bool}$$

1282 The fundamental theorem and overall type soundness remain unchanged.

1284 7.3 Extended Typing Algorithm

1286 Type Synthesis	1287 $\boxed{\Gamma \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau}$	1286 Type Check	1287 $\boxed{\Gamma \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau}$
1288 $\frac{\Gamma, 'a \Leftarrow e : \tau \quad \Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} \tau}{\Gamma \vdash e \Leftarrow 'a.\tau}$	1288 CHKPOLYTYPE	1288 $\frac{\Gamma, p:\bar{b} \rightarrow \text{bool} \Leftarrow e : \tau \quad \Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} \tau}{\Gamma \vdash e \Leftarrow \forall p:\bar{b} \rightarrow \text{bool}.\tau}$	1288 CHKPOLYPRED
1290			
1291 $\frac{\Gamma \vdash v_1 \Rightarrow \tau_1 \quad \Gamma \vdash v_2 \Rightarrow \tau_2 \quad [\tau_2] \notin b \quad \text{Inst}(\Gamma, \tau_1, \tau_2) = a:\tau'_2 \rightarrow \tau_x \quad \Gamma \vdash \tau_2 <: \tau'_2}{\Gamma' = x:\tau_x \quad \Gamma, \Gamma' \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau \quad \tau' = \text{Ex}(\Gamma', \tau) \quad \Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} \tau'}$			
1292 $\Gamma \vdash \text{let } x = v_1 v_2 \text{ in } e \Rightarrow \tau'$			
1292 SYNAPPFUN			
1294			
1295 $\frac{\Gamma \vdash v_1 \Rightarrow \tau_1 \quad \Gamma \vdash v_2 \Rightarrow [v: b \mid \phi_2] \quad \text{Inst}(\Gamma, \tau_1, [v: b \mid \phi_2]) = a:\{v: b \mid \phi\} \rightarrow \tau_x}{\Gamma' = a:\{v: b \mid v = v_2 \wedge \phi\}, x:\tau_x \quad \Gamma, \Gamma' \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau \quad \tau' = \text{Ex}(\Gamma', \tau) \quad \Gamma \vdash^{\text{WF}} \tau'}$			
1296 $\Gamma \vdash \text{let } x = v_1 v_2 \text{ in } e \Rightarrow \tau'$			
1296 SYNAPPBASE			

1299 Fig. 13. Extended bidirectional Typing Rules

1302 The extended bidirectional typing algorithm is shown in Fig. 13. We introduce two new
 1303 rules CHKPOLYTYPE and CHKPOLYPRED to type-check polymorphic terms, which are similar
 1304 to TPOLYTYPE and TPOLYPRED from Fig. 12. More challenging is, function application,
 1305 which in the declarative type system relies on the auxiliary SUBPOLYTYPE and SUBPOLYPRED
 1306 subtyping rules to instantiate both type variables and predicate variables in polymorphic
 1307 refinement types. We modify the previous typing algorithm for function application (i.e.,
 1308 SYNAPPFUN and SYNAPPBASE) as shown in Fig. 13, where modified parts are colored in gray.
 1309 These two rules first infer a function type (v_1) and type for the corresponding argument (v_2),
 1310 then invoke the instantiation subroutine **Inst**, which instantiates the polymorphic function
 1311 type with respect to the argument type (e.g., instantiates τ_1 on τ_2 in the rule SYNAPPFUN).
 1312 Since we perform type synthesis instead of type checking for the function v_1 in SYNAPPFUN ,
 1313 we additionally inline the rule CHKSUB to ensure the argument type τ_2 is a subtype of the
 1314 instantiated parameter type τ'_2 . The output of the **Inst** subroutine also ensures that the resulting
 1315 parameter type (e.g., $\{v: b \mid \phi\}$ in SYNAPPBASE) contains no free predicate variables. This
 1316 guarantees that the remaining typing rules can be directly copied from the original typing
 1317 algorithm.
 1318

1319 As shown in Algorithm 2, the **Inst** subroutine assumes that type qualifiers (e.g., $'a.\tau$)
 1320 have been eliminated, and divides the input function type τ_1 into three parts: quantified
 1321 predicates $\bar{P}:\bar{I}$, parameter type τ_{param} , and the return type τ_{ret} . Newly quantified predicates are
 1322 updated as shown on line 2 to guarantee that all predicate variables appearing in τ_{param} (i.e.,
 1323 $\text{FreePredVar}(\tau_{\text{param}})$) are instantiated. The algorithm then uses the unification subroutine to
 1324 obtain a predicate assignment σ that ensures predicate variables within the parameter type
 1325
 1326

Algorithm 2: Predicate Variable Instantiation

Inputs : A type context Γ , a function type $\forall \overline{P}. t.x:\tau_{\text{param}} \rightarrow \tau_{\text{ret}}$, and an argument type τ_2

Output : the instantiated function type

```

1 Procedure Inst( $\Gamma, \forall \overline{P}. t.x:\tau_{\text{param}} \rightarrow \tau_{\text{ret}}, \tau_2$ ) :=
2    $\overline{P}.t \leftarrow \overline{P}.t \setminus \text{FreePredVar}(\tau_{\text{param}})$ ;
3    $\sigma \leftarrow \text{UnifyType}(\Gamma, \emptyset, [(\tau_{\text{param}}, \tau_2)])$ ;
4    $x:\tau_{\text{param}} \rightarrow \tau_{\text{ret}} \leftarrow \sigma(x:\tau_{\text{param}} \rightarrow \tau_{\text{ret}})$ ;
5   return  $x:\tau_{\text{param}} \rightarrow (\forall \overline{P}. t.\tau_{\text{ret}})$ ;

```

τ_{param} are consistent with the argument type τ_2 (line 3). After substituting predicate variables with the corresponding assignments (line 4), **Inst** subroutine then returns an instantiated function type (line 5) whose return type is properly quantified.

The unification algorithm is shown in [Algorithm 3](#) and consists of two subroutines **UnifyType** and **UnifyQualifier** that collectively unify refinement type and qualifiers in similar manner to the standard type unification algorithm [50]. The **UnifyType** subroutine takes an initial predicate assignment solution (σ) and a list of type constraints (l). When encountering a base refinement type containing a free predicate variable that is not included in the type context (line 5), the algorithm invokes the qualifier unification subroutine (line 6) to get a predicate assignment σ_q . It then unions the predicate assignment and continues to process the remaining constraints after substitution (line 6 and 7). A function type is unified piecewise (line 12 – 13); otherwise, a mismatched case leads to a unification error (line 15). The **UnifyQualifier** subroutine works similarly but recursively processes over the syntactic structure of the qualifier instead.

Example 7.2. As shown on line 5 in [Fig. 10](#), type-checking the application `union neg_gen nat_gen` requires instantiating the quantified types predicates of τ_{union} based on its negative and natural number generators arguments.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{union} &: (\text{unit} \rightarrow [\nu: \text{int} \mid P_1(\nu)]) \rightarrow \\ & \quad (\text{unit} \rightarrow [\nu: \text{int} \mid P_2(\nu)]) \rightarrow (\text{unit} \rightarrow [\nu: \text{int} \mid P_1(\nu) \vee P_2(\nu)]), \\ \text{neg_gen} &: \text{unit} \rightarrow [\nu: \text{int} \mid \nu < 0], \text{nat_gen} : \text{unit} \rightarrow [\nu: \text{int} \mid 0 \leq \nu] \vdash \\ & \quad (\text{union neg_gen}) \text{nat_gen} \Rightarrow ? \end{aligned}$$

We type check the inner application `(union neg_gen)` first. The rule **SYNAPPFUN** uses the **Inst** subroutine to unify the type `unit` against `unit` \rightarrow $[\nu: \text{int} \mid \nu < 0]$. The predicate assignment after unification is $P_1 \mapsto \lambda \nu. \nu < 0$, and the synthesized type of the application `(union neg_gen)` is

$$(\text{unit} \rightarrow [\nu: \text{int} \mid P_2(\nu)]) \rightarrow (\text{unit} \rightarrow [\nu: \text{int} \mid \nu < 0 \vee P_2(\nu)])$$

Now we can type check the second application `(union neg_gen) nat_gen` in a similar way, where the **Inst** subroutine unifies the parameter type `unit` against `unit` \rightarrow $[\nu: \text{int} \mid 0 \leq \nu]$. The predicate assignment after unification is $P_2 \mapsto \lambda \nu. 0 \leq \nu$, and the coverage type of the final application is `unit` \rightarrow $[\nu: \text{int} \mid \nu < 0 \vee 0 \leq \nu]$, which covers all integers.

Note that our instantiation algorithm is not complete, as it relies on the assumption that the syntactic structures of two types under unification are aligned. For example, the

Algorithm 3: Predicate Unification

Inputs : A type context Γ , an initial predicate variable assignment σ , and a list of type alignment constraints l

Output : A predicate variable assignment that satisfies all input constraints.

```

1378 Procedure UnifyType( $\Gamma, \sigma, l$ ) :=
1379 1 match  $l$ :
1380 2   case [] do return  $\sigma$  ;
1381 3   case ( $\{v: b \mid \phi_1\}, \{v: b \mid \phi_2\}$ ) ::  $l$  or ( $[v: b \mid \phi_1], [v: b \mid \phi_2]$ ) ::  $l$  do
1382 4     if FreePredVar( $\phi_1$ ) \ Dom( $\Gamma$ )  $\neq \emptyset$  then
1383 5        $\sigma_q =$  UnifyQualifier( $\Gamma, \emptyset, [\phi_1, \phi_2]$ );
1384 6        $\sigma = \sigma_q(\sigma)$ ;
1385 7        $l = \sigma_q(l)$ ;
1386 8       return UnifyType( $\Gamma, \sigma \cup \sigma_q, l$ );
1387 9     else
1388 10      return UnifyType( $\Gamma, \sigma, l$ );
1389 11   case ( $x: \tau_{11} \rightarrow \tau_{12}, x: \tau_{21} \rightarrow \tau_{22}$ ) ::  $l$  do
1390 12     return UnifyType( $\sigma, (\tau_{11}, \tau_{21}) :: (\tau_{21}, \tau_{22}) :: l$ );
1391 13   case ( $\tau_1, \tau_2$ ) ::  $l$  do
1392 14     Raise Failure;
1393 15
1394
1395
1396
1397
1398
1399

```

Inputs : A type context Γ , an initial predicate variable assignment σ , and a list of qualifier alignment constraints l

Output : A predicate variable assignment that satisfies all input constraints.

```

1400 Procedure UnifyQualifier( $\Gamma, \sigma, l$ ) :=
1401 16 match  $l$ :
1402 17   case [] do return  $\sigma$  ;
1403 18   case ( $P(\bar{x}), \phi$ ) ::  $l$  do
1404 19      $\sigma_q = \{P \mapsto \bar{\lambda}x. \phi\}$ ;
1405 20      $\sigma = \sigma_q(\sigma)$ ;
1406 21      $l = \sigma_q(l)$ ;
1407 22     return UnifyQualifier( $\Gamma, \sigma \cup \sigma_q, l$ );
1408 23   case ( $\phi_1 \vee \phi_2, \phi'_1 \vee \phi'_2$ ) ::  $l$  do
1409 24     return UnifyQualifier( $\Gamma, \sigma, (\phi_1, \phi'_1) :: (\phi_2, \phi'_2) :: l$ );
1410 25   case ( $\phi_1 \wedge \phi_2, \phi'_1 \wedge \phi'_2$ ) ::  $l$  do
1411 26     return UnifyQualifier( $\Gamma, \sigma, (\phi_1, \phi'_1) :: (\phi_2, \phi'_2) :: l$ );
1412 27   case ( $\phi_1 \implies \phi_2, \phi'_1 \implies \phi'_2$ ) ::  $l$  do
1413 28     return UnifyQualifier( $\Gamma, \sigma, (\phi_1, \phi'_1) :: (\phi_2, \phi'_2) :: l$ );
1414 29   case ( $\neg \phi, \neg \phi'$ ) ::  $l$  do
1415 30     return UnifyQualifier( $\Gamma, \sigma, (\phi, \phi') :: l$ );
1416 31   case ( $\forall x. \phi, \forall x. \phi'$ ) ::  $l$  do
1417 32     return UnifyQualifier( $\Gamma, \sigma, (\phi, \phi') :: l$ );
1418 33   case ( $\exists x. \phi, \exists x. \phi'$ ) ::  $l$  do
1419 34     return UnifyQualifier( $\Gamma, \sigma, (\phi, \phi') :: l$ );
1420 35   case ( $\phi, \phi'$ ) ::  $l$  do
1421 36     Raise Failure;
1422 37
1423
1424
1425
1426
1427
1428

```

```

1429 1  module Gen = struct
1430 2    (* RS.t is the internal state of PRNG *)
1431 3    type 'a t = RS.t -> 'a
1432 4    let return (x: 'a) = fun (st: RS.t) -> x
1433 5    let bind (g: 'a t) (f: 'a -> 'b t) =
1434 6      fun (st: RS.t) -> let (x: 'a) = gen st in f x s
1435 7  end

```

Fig. 14. The definition of the test generator monad in QCheck.

Inst subroutine cannot unify $[v: \text{int} \mid P_1(v) \vee P_2(v)]$ with $[v: \text{int} \mid v \geq 0]$, although one possible solution is assigning P_1 to $\lambda v.v > 0$ and P_2 to $\lambda v.v = 0$.

Theorem 7.3. [Soundness of Extended Algorithmic Typing] For all type contexts Γ , term e and coverage type τ , $\Gamma \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau \implies \Gamma \vdash e : \tau$

Theorem 7.4. [Completeness of Extended Algorithmic Typing] Assuming an oracle for all formulas produced by the **Subtyping** subroutine, and assuming **Inst** subroutine always succeeds, then for any type context Γ , term e and coverage type τ , $\Gamma \vdash e : \tau \implies \Gamma \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau$.

8 The Coverage Monad and Monadic Generator Combinators

As discussed in [Sec. 1](#), real-world PBT frameworks like QCheck define the type of input generators as a monad and provide combinators for compositionally defining input generators. In order to align with this practice, this section defines a *coverage monad* that provides coverage guarantees about input generators defined in this style. This monad and the monadic generator combinators described in this section can all be desugared into the core language from the previous section.

8.1 Coverage Monad

In real-world programming languages, computational nondeterminism is typically introduced via a primitive pseudorandom number generator (PRNG) that produces unpredictable sequences of numbers based on a random seed. This facility is used by PBT frameworks like the generator library Gen of QCheck to parameterize the behavior of generators by a PRNG state, allowing test executions to be replayed by reusing the same initial seed. [Fig. 14](#) shows the definition of Gen in QCheck. The type of a generator 'a Gen.t is a function type $\text{RS.t} \rightarrow 'a$ (line 3), which takes a random seed and returns generated test value of type 'a. The `return` operator returns a constant value, regardless of the input state (line 4); while the `bind` operator passes the PRNG state through both the generator and the bind function (lines 5–6), respectively.

Example 8.1. In QCheck, a generator for positive integers can be compositionally defined by using the monadic `bind` combinator to get a random value from the natural number generator `nat_gen` and replacing it with 1 when it is a non-positive integer:

```

1475 1  val nat_gen: int Gen.t
1476 2  let pos_gen: int Gen.t =
1477 3    bind nat_gen (fun (n: int) ->
1478 4      if 0 < n then return n else return 1)
1479

```

```

1480  $\mathcal{M} [\nu: b \mid \phi] \doteq \{\nu: \text{RS.t} \mid \top\} \rightarrow [\nu: b \mid \phi]$ 
1481
1482  $\text{bind}^{\text{C}} \mathcal{M} [\nu: b_1 \mid \phi_1] (x: \{\nu: b_1 \mid \phi_2\} \rightarrow \mathcal{M} [\nu: b_2 \mid \phi_3]) \doteq$ 
1483  $\mathcal{M} [\nu: b_2 \mid \exists x: b_1. (\phi_1 \wedge \phi_2)[\nu \mapsto x] \wedge \phi_3]$ 
1484
1485
1486  $\text{return} : x: \{\nu: 'a \mid \top\} \rightarrow \mathcal{M} [\nu: 'a \mid \nu = x]$ 
1487
1488  $\text{bind} : \mathcal{M} [\nu: 'a \mid P_1(\nu)] \rightarrow (x: \{\nu: 'a \mid P_2(\nu)\} \rightarrow \mathcal{M} [\nu: 'b \mid P_3(x, \nu)]) \rightarrow$ 
1489  $\text{bind}^{\text{C}} \mathcal{M} [\nu: 'a \mid P_1(\nu)] (x: \{\nu: 'a \mid P_2(\nu)\} \rightarrow \mathcal{M} [\nu: 'b \mid P_3(x, \nu)])$ 
1490  $\equiv \mathcal{M} [\nu: 'b \mid \exists x. P_1(x) \wedge P_2(x) \wedge P_3(x, \nu)]$  (after unfolding  $\text{bind}^{\text{C}}$ )
1491

```

Fig. 15. The coverage monad and the signatures of its operators.

While `nat_gen` and `pos_gen` produce different sets of values, they both have the same basic type: `int Gen.t`. To better capture the coverage guarantees of these sorts of monadic generators, we define the coverage monad $\mathcal{M} [\nu: b \mid \phi]$, shown in Fig. 15. As expected, the shape of this monad augments the type parameter of `Gen.t` with a qualifier that captures its coverage properties. The definition of $\mathcal{M} [\nu: b \mid \phi]$ has two consequences: first, since only non-function values can be qualified, the coverage monad can only range over base types. Second, the coverage guarantees of a monadic generator cannot reference the random seed. This latter restriction makes intuitive sense, as a monadic test generator of type $\mathcal{M} [\nu: b \mid \phi]$ should be guaranteed to produce values satisfying predicate ϕ regardless of the random seed. We can use the coverage monad to capture the different coverages of `nat_gen` and `pos_gen`, as $\mathcal{M} [\nu: \text{int} \mid 0 < \nu]$ and $\mathcal{M} [\nu: \text{int} \mid 0 \leq \nu]$, respectively.

Fig. 15 also gives the signatures of the operators of the coverage monad; their definitions are the same as in Fig. 14. The signature of `return` reflects that lifts an arbitrary value into a generator that always produces that value (i.e., $\nu = x$). The signature of the `bind` operator uses a special notation, bind^{C} , for its codomain; this alias will be helpful in the upcoming discussion of generator combinators, which are built using `bind`. Intuitively, the qualifier in this type introduces an existentially quantified variable x that represents the intermediate value by the first argument of `bind`. This value is required to satisfy both the coverage guarantee of the test generator (ϕ_1) as well as the safety constraint associated with the bind function (ϕ_2).

To understand the definition of bind^{C} , consider how the definition of `bind` in Fig. 14 can be typed using the polymorphic type system of the previous section. After unfolding bind^{C} , the initial typing goal is:

```

1521  $g: \mathcal{M} [\nu: 'a \mid P_1(\nu)], f: (x: \{\nu: 'a \mid P_2(\nu)\} \rightarrow \mathcal{M} [\nu: 'b \mid P_3(x, \nu)]),$ 
1522  $\vdash \text{fun } (st: \text{RS.t}) \rightarrow \text{let } x = g \text{ st in } f \ x \text{ st} : [\nu: 'b \mid \exists x. P_1(x) \wedge P_2(x) \wedge P_3(x, \nu)]$ 
1523

```

After moving the PRNG state and the value produce by the first generator into the context, the typing goal is:

```

1527  $g: \mathcal{M} [\nu: 'a \mid P_1(\nu)], f: (x: \{\nu: 'a \mid P_2(\nu)\} \rightarrow \mathcal{M} [\nu: 'b \mid P_3(x, \nu)]), s: \text{RS.t}, x: [\nu: 'a \mid P_1(\nu)]$ 
1528  $\vdash f \ x \ s : [\nu: \exists x. 'b \mid P_1(x) \wedge P_2(x) \wedge P_3(x, \nu)]$ 
1529

```

```

1531 1   val power: m:{v: int | 0 ≤ v} → x:{v: int | 0 ≤ v} → [v: int | v = mx]
1532 2   let power_gen = bind (int_bound 10: [v: int | v ≤ 10])
1533 3     (fun (x: {v: int | 0 ≤ v}) -> return (power 2 x))

```

Fig. 16. A generator for powers of 2 less than 2^{10} .

Similarly to how `bst_gen` was typed in [Sec. 4](#), we can use `TEQ` to remove the existential quantifier in the target type, and then use `TSUB` to bring `x` into alignment with the argument type of `f` to yield the expected type.

Example 8.2. The coverage guarantees of generators built from monadic combinators are also derived compositionally. As an example, consider the definition of a generator for powers of 2 from 2^0 to 2^{10} shown in [Fig. 16](#). After randomly generating an integer using `int_bound 10`, `power_gen` raises 2 to this power and returns the result. Note that the coverage guarantees of `power` are only provided for arguments greater than 0, however, a fact that will be reflected in the final type of `power_gen`. Importantly, the instantiations of three predicate variables in the type of `bindc` come directly from the qualifiers of its arguments:

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 P_1 \mapsto \underbrace{\lambda v. v \leq 10}_{\text{int_bound } 10} & P_2 \mapsto \underbrace{\lambda v. 0 \leq v}_{\text{fun } x: \{v: \text{int} \mid 0 \leq v\} \rightarrow} & P_3 \mapsto \underbrace{\lambda x. \lambda v. v = 2^x}_{\text{power } 2 \ x}
 \end{array}$$

Allowing us to derive the desired coverage type for `power_gen`:

$$\text{power} : \dots \vdash \text{power_gen} : \mathcal{M} [v: \text{int} \mid \exists x. 0 \leq x \wedge x \leq 10 \wedge v = 2^x]$$

```

1556 1   let biased_nat_gen (st: RS.t) =
1557 2     union (int_range 0 10) (return Int.max_int)
1558 3
1559 4   ⊢ biased_nat_gen: M {v: int | 0 ≤ v ≤ Int.max_int}

```

Fig. 17. Example of safety monad.

Over- and under-approximate monads. Monadic combinators also lend themselves well to an over-approximate analysis via traditional refinement types. In the context of test input generators, such specifications are useful in contexts where developers want to prioritize certain *safe* values that always meet the preconditions of the system under test, e.g., when probing boundary cases. As an example of this situation, consider the following generator:

```

1569 1   let biased_nat_gen (st: RS.t) =
1570 2     union (int_range 0 10) (return Int.max_int)
1571 3
1572 4   ⊢ biased_nat_gen: M {v: int | 0 ≤ v ≤ Int.max_int}

```

`biased_nat_gen` does not enumerate all natural numbers; instead, it samples from a biased distribution that emphasizes small numbers (e.g., $[0, 10]$) and the maximum integer value (`Int.max_int`), the latter of which covers the critical edge case for overflow testing. To cover this scenario, we can similarly define a dual *safety* monad for generators $\mathcal{M} \{v: b \mid \phi\}$. Here, `biased_nat_gen` can be assigned the safety monad type $\mathcal{M} \{v: \text{int} \mid 0 \leq v \leq \text{Int.max_int}\}$, ensuring that all sampled values fall within this range. We further discuss real-world instances of such usage in [Sec. 9](#).

Using monad combinators to define generators enables the seamless use of both safety and coverage monads to provide richer specifications that capture their ability to produce every value that meets a precondition and only such values. Consider a generator g_1 for lists of integers which has the following type:

$$\vdash g_1 : \text{bind}^C \mathcal{M} \{v: \text{int} \mid 0 \leq v\} (n: \text{int} \rightarrow \mathcal{M} [v: \text{int list} \mid \text{len}(v, n) \wedge \text{sorted}(v)])$$

This type specifies that g_1 produces all possible sorted lists of integers with length n , where n is drawn from a generator assigned a safety monad type (e.g., `biased_nat_gen`) which is biased toward values believed to be important by developers. Conversely, consider a generator g_2 with the following type:

$$\vdash g_2 : \text{bind}^C \mathcal{M} [v: \text{int} \mid 0 \leq v] (n: \text{int} \rightarrow \mathcal{M} \{v: \text{int list} \mid \text{len}(v, n) \wedge \text{sorted}(v)\})$$

Here, g_2 produces all possible non-negative list lengths, while imposing no specific coverage obligations over the list contents of a generated sorted list of a given length. This form is useful when the target property under test is sensitive to shape of the datatype (i.e., list length) but not necessarily to the elements it contains. Developers are then allowed to specialize the generated list of length n as a fixed choice (e.g., `[1; 2; ... ; n]`), rather than generating all possible sorted lists, which would require more effort. In both of these examples, the combined use of safety and coverage monads provides developers more flexibility to specify generators that are neither totally over-approximated nor totally under-approximated.

8.2 Monadic Combinator Examples

This section provides examples of the coverage guarantees our system can provide for several monadic combinators typically found in PBT frameworks like QCheck. We show the (monadic) coverage type of each example combinator first using the coverage monad, and then a version in which \mathcal{M} and bind^C are unfolded.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{option} &: \mathcal{M} [v: 'a \mid P(v)] \rightarrow \\ &\quad \text{bind}^C \mathcal{M} [v: 'a \mid P(v)] (x: 'a \rightarrow \mathcal{M} [v: 'a \text{ option} \mid v = \text{None} \vee v = \text{Some}(x)]) \\ &\quad \equiv \mathcal{M} [v: 'a \text{ option} \mid v = \text{None} \vee \exists x. P(x) \wedge v = \text{Some}(x)] \quad (\text{after unfolding}) \\ \text{pair} &: \mathcal{M} [v: 'a \mid P_1(v)] \rightarrow \mathcal{M} [v: 'b \mid P_2(v)] \rightarrow \\ &\quad \text{bind}^C \mathcal{M} [v: 'a \mid P_1(v)] \\ &\quad (x: 'a \rightarrow \text{bind}^C \mathcal{M} [v: 'b \mid P_2(v)] (y: 'b \rightarrow \mathcal{M} [v: 'a \times 'b \mid v = (x, y)])) \\ &\quad \equiv \mathcal{M} [v: 'a \times 'b \mid P_1(\text{fst}(v)) \wedge P_2(\text{snd}(v))] \quad (\text{after unfolding}) \end{aligned}$$

The `option` combinator lifts a generator into a version for option types that covers both the `Some()` and `None` cases ($v = \text{None} \vee v = \text{Some}(x)$). Similarly, the `pair` combinator returns a pair containing the results of two input test generators ($v = (x, y)$).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{list_repeat} &: s: \{v: \text{int} \mid 0 \leq v\} \rightarrow g: (\mathcal{M} [v: 'a \mid P(v)] \rightarrow \\ &\quad \mathcal{M} [v: 'a \text{ list} \mid \text{len}(v, s) \wedge \forall x. \text{mem}(v, x) \implies P(x)]) \end{aligned}$$

The `list_repeat` combinator uses an input generator (g) to construct a list of s elements. Its coverage type guarantees that it produces all lists with of the stipulated length $len(v, s)$ that contain elements covered by the input generators (i.e., $\forall x. mem(v, x) \implies P_2(x)$). As a simple example, the following generator produces all lists with three positive numbers:

```
1 let pos_list_gen = list_repeat 3 pos_gen
```

$$\begin{aligned} \text{oneof} &: s:\{v: \text{int} \mid 0 < v\} \rightarrow (i:\{v: \text{int} \mid P_1(v)\} \rightarrow \mathcal{M} [v: 'a \mid P_2(i, v)]) \rightarrow \\ &\quad \text{bind}^c (\mathcal{M} [v: \text{int} \mid 0 \leq v < s]) (i:\{v: \text{int} \mid P_1(v)\} \rightarrow \mathcal{M} [v: 'a \mid P_2(i, v)]) \\ &\quad \equiv \mathcal{M} [v: 'a \mid \exists i. 0 \leq i < s \wedge P_1(i) \wedge P_2(i, v)] \quad (\text{after unfolding}) \\ \text{frequency} &: s:\{v: \text{int} \mid 0 < v\} \rightarrow (i:\{v: \text{int} \mid P_1(v)\} \rightarrow \mathcal{M} [v: \text{int} \times 'a \mid P_2(i, v)]) \rightarrow \\ &\quad \text{bind}^c (\text{bind}^c (\mathcal{M} [v: \text{nat} \mid 0 \leq v < s]) \\ &\quad\quad (i:\{v: \text{int} \mid P_1(v)\} \rightarrow \mathcal{M} [v: \text{int} \times 'a \mid P_2(i, v)])) \\ &\quad\quad (p:\text{nat} \times 'a \rightarrow \mathcal{M} [v: 'a \mid fst(p) > 0 \wedge snd(p) = v]) \\ &\quad \equiv \mathcal{M} [v: 'a \mid \exists i. 0 \leq i < s \wedge P_1(i) \wedge \exists w. w > 0 \wedge P_2(i, (w, v))] \quad (\text{after unfolding}) \end{aligned}$$

The `oneof` combinator is a more powerful version of the `union` combinator that combines an arbitrary number of test generators, instead of only two. This combinator takes two arguments: the total number of input generators (s) and an indexed function (f) where $f\ i$ represents the i^{th} input generator.¹⁰ As captured by its type signature, the number of input generators is constrained by predicate variable P_1 and the coverage guarantee of each input generator is constrained by P_2 . The coverage type of `union` guarantees that it builds a generator that covers everything that the input generators do (i.e., $\exists i. 0 \leq i < s$). As an example, the following (redundant) generator for integers uses `oneof` to combine 3 generators: a negative number generator (`neg_gen`), a constant generator that only produce 0 (`return 0`), and a positive number generator (`pos_gen`).

```
1 let int_gen = oneof 3 (function
2     | 0 -> neg_gen
3     | 1 -> return 0
4     | _ -> pos_gen)
```

The `frequency` combinator is similar to `oneof`, but it additionally allows the developer to provide a weight for each input generator that governs their sampling distribution. The type of this combinator requires that each of these weights are positive ($w > 0$).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{fix} &: (m:\text{nat} \rightarrow (n:\{v: \text{nat} \mid v < m\} \rightarrow \mathcal{M} [v: 'a \mid P(n, v)]) \rightarrow \mathcal{M} [v: 'a \mid P(m, v)]) \rightarrow \\ &\quad (m:\text{nat} \rightarrow \mathcal{M} [v: 'a \mid P(m, v)]) \end{aligned}$$

The `fix` combinator constructs a test generator that produces larger test inputs from a function that generators smaller test inputs; the first parameter of this function is a natural number that limits the number of recursive calls. Unsurprisingly, this combinator has the same premises as `TFix` in Fig. 7.

¹⁰The `oneof` and `frequency` combinators in QCheck use lists instead of a function to hold its input generators. Our formulation of both combinators allows them to straightforwardly combine generators with different coverage guarantees, without having to deal with heterogeneous lists.

```

1684 1  type 'a tree = Leaf of 'a | Node of 'a tree * 'a tree
1685 2  let tree_gen : int -> int tree Gen.t = fix
1686 3    (fun n self -> match n with
1687 4      | 0 -> return err
1688 5      | 1 -> bind nat_gen (fun x -> return (Leaf x))
1689 6      | n ->
1690 7        frequency 2
1691 8        (function
1692 9          | 0 -> (1, bind nat_gen (fun x -> return (Leaf x)))
1693 10         | _ -> (2, bind (self n/2) (fun tr1 ->
1694 11           bind (self n/2) (fun tr2 ->
1695 12             return (Node (tr1, tr2))))))
1696 13    )

```

Fig. 18. Defining a tree generator using `frequency` and `fix`.

Fig. 19. A 5-node tree that cannot be produced by `tree_gen 5`.

Example 8.3. We demonstrate how these combinators work by reimplementing the tree generator example from Sec. 1 using the `fix` and `frequency` combinators. The new implementation is given in Fig. 18. Since every tree contains at least one element, the base case returns an error. Otherwise, if the target number of elements is 1 (line 5), we generate a leaf node by binding the natural number generator with the `Leaf` constructor. In the other cases, we use the `frequency` combinator to combine two test generators with weight 1 and 2 respectively (line 9 - 12). The first generator is a singleton tree generator, while the second generator calls `self` recursively to generate left and right subtrees containing half the nodes. Note that each subtree has at most half the target number of nodes, to ensure that the final tree contains the expected number of elements.

Although this tree generator accepts a bound n as input, it cannot be assigned the coverage type $n:\text{nat} \rightarrow \mathcal{M} [v:\text{nat tree} \mid \text{numElem}(v) \leq n]$, which would require it to generate all trees containing at most n elements. This is because the implementation divides the input bound evenly during recursive calls (lines 10 and 11), making it unable to construct trees that are highly unbalanced. For instance, with input 5, the generator cannot produce the tree illustrated in Fig. 19, where the left subtree (highlighted in blue) contains 3 elements which is exceeding the divided bound $5/2$. Instead, we can assign it the coverage type $n:\text{nat} \rightarrow \mathcal{M} [v:\text{nat tree} \mid 2^{\text{depth}(v)} \leq n]$, which captures the idea that all trees of depth m can be covered when the input bound is at least 2^m . According to this type, any tree can be generated by this tree generator given a sufficiently large input bound. This alternative interpretation of the input bound as “depth” is coverage-complete but less intuitive than the “number of nodes” interpretation, highlighting the intricate nature involved in underapproximate-style reasoning.

Table 3. Experimental results on hand-written generators. Existing benchmarks are annotated with their source: QuickChick [36] (*), QuickCheck [5] (°), and bespoke test input generators from [34] (*) and [68] (°).

	#Branch	Rec	#LVar	#UP	#Query	(max. # \forall , # \exists)	total(avg. time) (ms)
SizedList*	3	✓	9	3	8	(2, 5)	10.45(1.31)
SortedList*	3	✓	13	4	11	(4, 7)	31.21(2.84)
UniqueList°	3	✓	10	5	9	(2, 5)	12.28(1.36)
SizedTree*	3	✓	12	4	11	(2, 7)	15.00(1.36)
CompleteTree*	2	✓	9	5	8	(2, 5)	12.01(1.50)
RedBlackTree*	6	✓	44	7	41	(5, 20)	83.28(2.03)
SizedBST*	4	✓	28	6	25	(6, 12)	42.69(1.71)
BatchedQueue°	1		5	1	5	(2, 4)	6.58(1.65)
BankersQueue°	1		5	1	5	(2, 4)	7.53(1.51)
Stream°	3	✓	10	4	9	(2, 6)	11.84(1.32)
SizedHeap°	4	✓	17	5	15	(5, 9)	23.10(1.54)
LeftistHeap°	2	✓	13	5	12	(2, 7)	47.06(3.92)
SizedSet°	3	✓	26	6	23	(5, 11)	45.17(1.96)
UnbalanceSet°	4	✓	35	6	31	(6, 14)	67.22(2.17)

9 Implementation and Evaluation

Implementation. We have implemented a coverage type checker, called Poirot, based on the above approach. Poirot targets functional, non-concurrent OCaml programs that rely on libraries to manipulate algebraic data types; it consists of approximately 11K lines of OCaml and uses Z3 [8] as its backend solver.

Poirot takes as input an Ocaml program representing a test input generator and a user-supplied coverage type for that generator. After basic type-checking and translation into MNF, Poirot applies bidirectional type inference and checking to validate that the program satisfies the requirements specified by the type. Our implementation provides built-in coverage types for a number of OCaml primitives, including constants, various arithmetic operators, and data constructors for a range of datatypes. Refinements defined in coverage types can also use predefined (polymorphic) uninterpreted predicates that capture non-trivial datatype shape properties. For example, the uninterpreted predicate $mem(l, u)$ indicates the element u : a is contained in the data type instance l : a list; the uninterpreted predicate $len(l, 3)$ indicates the list l has length 3, or the tree l has depth 3. The semantics of these uninterpreted predicates are defined as a set of FOL-encoded lemmas and axioms to facilitate automated verification; e.g., the lemma $len(l, 0) \implies \forall u, \neg mem(l, u)$ indicates that the empty datatype instance contains no element.

In order to improve efficiency, verification conditions generated by Poirot are simplified before being solved by the underlying SMT solver. For example, the `Ex` function generates queries of the form $\exists x. x = v \wedge \phi$, which can be simplified to $\phi[x \mapsto v]$. This transformation can significantly reduce both the number of quantifiers and the overall size of queries.

9.1 Completeness of Hand-Written Generators

We have evaluated Poirot on a corpus of hand-written, non-trivial test input generators drawn from a variety of sources (see Table 3). These benchmarks provide test input generators over a diverse range of datatypes, including various kinds of lists, trees, queues, streams, heaps, and sets. For each datatype implementation, Poirot type checks the provided implementation

1786 against its supplied coverage type to verify that the generator is able to generate all possible
 1787 datatype instances consistent with this type. Our uninterpreted predicates allow us capture
 1788 non-trivial structural properties. For example, to verify a red-black tree generator, we use the
 1789 predicate *black_height*(v, n) to indicate that all branches of the tree v have exactly n black
 1790 nodes, the predicate *no_red_red*(v) to indicate v contains no red node with red children, and
 1791 the predicate *root_color*(v, b) to indicate the root of the tree v has the red (black) color when
 1792 the boolean value b is true (false).¹¹
 1793

1794 Given this rich set of predicates, it is straightforward to express interesting coverage types.
 1795 For example, given size s and lower bound lo , we can express the property that a sorted list
 1796 generator *sorted_list_gen* *must* generate all possible sorted lists with the length s and in
 1797 which all elements are greater than or equal to lo , as the following type:

$$1798 \quad s:\{v:\text{int} \mid v \leq 0\} \rightarrow lo:\{v:\text{int} \mid \top\} \rightarrow$$

$$1799 \quad [v:\text{int list} \mid len(v, s) \wedge sorted(v) \wedge \forall u, mem(v, u) \implies lo \leq u]$$

1800 Notice that this type is remarkably similar to a normal refinement type:
 1801

$$1802 \quad s:\{v:\text{int} \mid v \leq 0\} \rightarrow lo:\{v:\text{int} \mid \top\} \rightarrow$$

$$1803 \quad \{v:\text{int list} \mid len(v, s) \wedge sorted(v) \wedge \forall u, mem(v, u) \implies lo \leq u\}$$

1804 albeit with the return type marked as a coverage type to capture our desired must-property.
 1805

1806 The first group of columns in Table 3 describes the salient features of our benchmarks.
 1807 Each benchmark exhibits non-trivial control-flow, containing anywhere from 1 to 6 nested
 1808 branches; the majority of our benchmarks are also recursive (column Rec). The number of
 1809 local (i.e., let-bound) variables (column #LVars) is a proxy for path lengths that must be
 1810 encoded within the types inferred by our type-checker; column #UP indicates the number of
 1811 uninterpreted predicates found in the benchmark’s type specification.
 1812

1813 The second group of columns presents type checking results. The column #Query indicates
 1814 the number of SMT queries that are triggered during type checking. The column #(\forall, \exists)
 1815 indicates the maximum number of universal and existential quantifiers in these queries,
 1816 respectively. The \exists column is a direct reflection of control-flow (path) complexity — complex
 1817 generators with deeply nested match-expressions like RedBlackTree result in queries with
 1818 over 20 existential quantifiers. These numbers broadly track with the values in columns
 1819 #Branch and #LVar. Despite the complexity of some of these queries, as evidenced by the
 1820 number of their quantifiers, overall verification time (average verification time per query,
 1821 resp.), reported in the last column, is quite reasonable, with times ranging from 6.58 to 83.28
 1822 milliseconds, i.e., all benchmarks finishing in less than 0.1 second.
 1823

1824 9.2 Case Study: Well-Typed STLC Terms

1825 We have also applied Poirot to a more substantial example: a generator for well-typed simply
 1826 typed lambda calculus (STLC) terms adapted from Lampropoulos et al. [33], Pařka et al. [47].
 1827 Such a generator can be used to test that the typing relation guarantees the expected runtime
 1828 behaviors of programs, e.g. progress and preservation. In addition to the complexity of the
 1829 coverage property itself (well-typedness), this case study features multiple inductive datatypes
 1830 (for types, terms, and typing contexts, as shown in Fig. 20), and 13 auxiliary functions. The
 1831 coverage type of *gen_term_size*, the top-level generator, stipulates that it can generate all
 1832
 1833

1834
 1835 ¹¹These uninterpreted predicates can be found in the implementation of the red-black tree generator given in [36].
 1836

```

1837 type ty = Ty_nat | Ty_arr of ty * ty
1838
1839 type term =
1840   | Const of int
1841   | Var of int
1842   | Abs of ty * term
1843   | App of term * term
1844
1845 type tyctx = ty list

```

Fig. 20. Datatypes from the STLC case study.

Table 4. Experimental results from the STLC case study. Each function is implemented as a wrapper around a subsidiary function that takes an additional strictly decreasing argument to ensure termination (the original QuickChick implementations uses Coq/Rocq’s Program command for this purpose). These subsidiary functions are responsible for the bulk of the computation, so we report the results for those functions here.

	#Branch	Rec	#LVar	#UP	#Query	(max. #V,#E)	total (avg. time) (ms)
type_eq	5	✓	6	4	4	(3, 12)	57.15(14.29)
gen_type	2	✓	9	3	8	(2, 5)	9.47(1.18)
vars_with_type	4	✓	7	5	5	(3, 6)	8.38(1.68)
gen_term_no_app	3	✓	8	12	6	(3, 7)	13.88(2.31)
gen_term_size	4	✓	36	11	32	(5, 16)	4735.37(147.98)

terms of a desired type, up to a user-provided size bound:

$$\text{gen_term_size} : n : \{v : \text{int} \mid 0 \leq v\} \rightarrow \underbrace{\mathbf{t} : \{\nu : \text{ty} \mid \top\}}_{\text{type of term}} \rightarrow \underbrace{\Gamma : \{\nu : \text{tyctx} \mid \top\}}_{\text{typing context}} \rightarrow \underbrace{[v : \text{term} \mid \text{has_ty}(\Gamma, \nu, \mathbf{t}) \wedge \text{max_app_num}(\nu, n)]}_{\text{result is well-typed and has at most } n \text{ applications}}$$

The results of using Poirot to verify that `gen_term_size` meets the above specification are shown in Table 4. The table also reports the results for the most interesting auxiliary functions used by the function. The last column shows that Poirot is able to verify these functions within a reasonable time, ranging from 0.01 to 4.74 seconds. Although more complex functions (as indicated by the column labeled #Branch) require more time to verify, total verification time is nonetheless reasonable: less than 5 seconds in total. Taken together, these results highlight the compositionality of Poirot’s type-based approach: each of the 13 auxiliary functions used by `gen_term_size` is individually type-checked against its signature; these signatures are then used to verify any procedures that call the function.

Interestingly, the function `type_eq` has a longer average query time than most of other functions, despite having fewer local variables and uninterpreted predicates. This function implements a deterministic equality test, returning `true` when two types are the same and `false` otherwise. Thus, the coverage type of this function degenerates into a singleton type for each of the branches, resulting in stricter queries to the SMT solver that take longer to find a valid witness.

Discussion. To handle the complexity of this benchmark, Poirot requires 16 uninterpreted predicates and 24 axioms, the large majority of which correspond to helper definitions and

lemmas from the original development. The predicates that encode typing and the bounds on the number of applications in a term (*has_ty* and *max_num_app*, resp.) come directly from the QuickCheck version, for example. The following axiom encodes the semantic relationship of these predicates

$$\forall \Gamma: \text{tyctx}. \forall t: \text{ty}. \forall e: \text{term}.$$

$$\text{has_ty}(\Gamma, e, t) \iff \exists n: \text{nat}. \text{max_num_app}(e, n) \wedge \text{has_ty}(\Gamma, e, t)$$

and is analogous to the helper lemma *has_ty_max_tau_correct* in the original Coq/Rocq development. In addition, some predicates and axioms are independent of this particular case study: the typing context is implemented as a list of STLC types, and thus we were able to reuse generic predicates and axioms about polymorphic lists.

9.3 Completeness of Synthesized Generators

Table 5. Quantifying the space of safe and complete test input generators constructed by an automated program synthesis tool.

Benchmark	#Total	#Complete
UniqueList	284	10
SizedList	126	28
SortedList	30	8
SizedTree	103	2
SizedBST	229	54
RedBlackTree	234	2

An underlying hypothesis motivating our work is that writing sound and *complete* test input generators can be subtle and tricky, as demonstrated by our motivating example (Figure 1). To justify this hypothesis, we repurposed an existing deductive component-based program synthesizer [40] to automatically synthesize correct (albeit possibly incomplete) generators that satisfy a specification given as an overapproximate refinement type; these generators are then fed to Poirot to validate their completeness. We provided the synthesizer with a datatype definition and a set of specifications describing constraints on that datatype the synthesized generator should use, along with a library of functions, including primitive generators such as *nat_gen*, available to the synthesizer for construction. A refinement type-guided enumeration is performed to find all correct programs consistent with the specification. Since the space of these programs is potentially quite large (possibly infinite), we constrain the synthesizer to only generate programs with bounded function call depths; in our experiments, this bound was set to three. The generator outputs all programs that are safe with respect to the specification. Table 5 shows results of this experiment for five of the benchmarks given in Table 3; results for the other benchmarks are similar. We report the total number of synthesized generators (#Total) constructed and the number of those that are *correct and complete* as verified by Poirot (#Complete). The table confirms our hypothesis that the space of complete generators with respect to the supplied coverage type is significantly smaller than the space of safe generators, as defined by an overapproximate refinement type specification.

More concretely, Figure 21 shows three synthesized generators that satisfy the following specification of a list generator that is meant to construct *all* lists no longer than some provided

```

1939 1  let rec sized_list_gen
1940 2      (size : int) : (int list) =
1941 3      if (size == 0) then []
1942 4      else
1943 5          if bool_gen () then sized_list_gen (size - 1)
1944 6          else (int_gen ()) :: (sized_list_gen (size - 1))
1945
1946                                     (a) A sound and complete generator.
1947
1948 let rec sized_list_gen
1949 (size : int) : (int list) =
1950 if (size == 0) then []
1951 else (int_gen ()) :: (sized_list_gen (size - 1))
1952
1953                                     (b) A sound but incomplete generator.
1954
1955 let rec sized_list_gen
1956 (size : int) : (int list) =
1957 if (size == 0) then []
1958 else
1959     if bool_gen () then sized_list_gen (size - 1)
1960     else size :: (sized_list_gen (size - 1))
1961
1962                                     (c) Another sound but incomplete generator.

```

Fig. 21. Three example generators that generate size-bounded lists.

bound:

$$\text{size:}\{v: \text{int} \mid v \leq 0\} \rightarrow [v: \text{int list} \mid \forall u, \text{len}(v, u) \implies (0 \leq u \wedge u \leq \text{size})]$$

Fig. 21b is incomplete because it never generates an empty list when the size parameter size is greater than 0. On the other hand, while Fig. 21c does generate empty lists, the else branch of its second conditional has a fixed first element and will therefore never generate lists with distinct elements. The complete generator shown in Fig. 21a incorporates a control-flow path (line 5) that can non-deterministically choose to make a recursive call to sized_list_gen with a smaller size, thereby allowing it to generate lists of variable size up to the size bound, including the empty list; another conditional branch uses int_gen() to generate a new randomly selected list element, thereby allowing the implementation to generate lists containing distinct elements. We again emphasize that Poirot was able to verify the correct generator and discard the two incorrect generators *automatically*, without any user involvement.

9.4 Case Study: Checking Coverage in Practice

In this section, we focus on test input generators from real-world applications as well as the underlying combinators provided by mainstream PBT frameworks.

The experimental result of verifying the monadic combinators for Sec. 8 is shown in Table 6. These combinators are relatively simple and Poirot is able to verify them within 0.03 seconds with small variance.

We also apply Poirot to identify coverage completeness violations across five open-source repositories that use the QCheck framework to test their implementation. Each project deals with a different real-world application domain: blockchain [59], virtualization [63], compiler verification [67], weak memory model testing [39], and automated theorem proving [6]. The details of these projects are as follows:

Table 6. Experimental results that use monadic combinators from the Gen library of the QCheck framework. The columns are the same as in Table 3; we additionally count the number of type variables (#a) and predicate variables (#P) for these polymorphic combinators. A number of combinator types do not require uninterpreted predicates since they do not make use of datatypes; list_repeat (list), option (option), pair (pair), and frequency (pair), do however, employ such predicates.

	#Branch	Rec	#LVar	#a	#P	#UP	#Query	(max. #V,#E)	total (avg. time) (ms)
return	1		2	1	0	0	1	(0, 0)	0.14(0.14)
bind	1		5	2	2	0	3	(2, 1)	28.74(9.58)
fmap	1		4	2	2	0	2	(2, 1)	2.23(1.11)
pair	1		5	2	2	2	3	(1, 2)	2.61(0.87)
option	2		7	1	1	3	14	(2, 3)	5.91(0.42)
union	2		4	1	2	0	12	(1, 1)	2.48(0.21)
oneof	1		4	1	1	0	3	(2, 1)	4.35(1.45)
frequency	1		5	1	1	2	3	(3, 2)	3.04(1.01)
list_repeat	2	✓	12	1	1	4	12	(3, 5)	11.48(0.96)
fix	1		5	1	1	0	15	(2, 0)	11.23(0.75)

Table 7. Experimental results for test generators of open-source repositories. The columns follow the same format as in Table 3, with an additional column showing the number of combinators (#C) used by these generators. The verification time in the last column is given in seconds.

	#Branch	Rec	#LVar	#UP	#C	#Query	(max. #V,#E)	total (avg. time) (s)
Tezos	7	✓	40	15	3	73	(3, 35)	10.75(0.15)
Xen API	1		21	5	3	24	(1, 16)	6.51(0.27)
Vellvm	10	✓	41	19	4	84	(4, 19)	2.05(0.02)
Herdtools7	1		32	10	3	90	(2, 8)	2.08(0.02)
Zipperposition	7	✓	71	16	4	134	(2, 49)	15.81(0.12)

- (1) **Tezos.** Tezos [59] is a blockchain platform implemented in OCaml that supports decentralized assets and applications. Tezos writes its own generators to construct block trees, i.e., trees of block nodes representing the shape of a blockchain, where blocks are expected to have unique hash codes.
- (2) **Xen API.** Xen API [63] is a management API for controlling the virtualization environments of then Xen Project Hypervisor [64]. We selected the file descriptor generator of the API, which produces random file descriptors with different attributes, e.g., file size, kind, read and write delay time. The generated test inputs are expected to be a subset of valid Unix file descriptors (e.g., not a symbolic link).
- (3) **Vellvm.** Vellvm [67] is a formal verification framework for the LLVM IR, implemented in both OCaml and Coq/Rocq. We selected the generator for LLVM values used to provide as arguments of various LLVM functions under test. Given a specific LLVM type, this generator is expected to generate all well-typed LLVM values.
- (4) **Herdtools7.** Herdtools7 [39] is a collection of tools for modeling and analyzing concurrent programs with weak memory models. The generator Carpenter in Herdtools7 produces random ASTs of the Arm Architecture Specification Language [54], where the generator is expected to generate every AST of a specified size.
- (5) **Zipperposition.** Zipperposition [6] is an automated theorem prover that supports polymorphic types and higher-order unification. Test generators are used to produce valid first-order logic (e.g., $\forall x:\alpha.\exists y:\alpha.x \neq y$) and lambda-free higher-order logic formulae.

We used our polymorphic version of Poirot to check that these test generators can cover all test inputs that satisfy the precondition of the program under test. Thus, we type check generators against coverage types that encode specifications extracted from README files, documentation, and comments in the source code. As shown in Table 7, these test generators are complex, including 1-10 control flow branches, 21-71 local variables, and 5-19 uninterpreted predicates. Most uninterpreted predicates are directly converted from datatype constructors (e.g., `cons` for list datatype). Notably, Poirot reports that *none* of these generators are coverage complete with respect to the preconditions we expected, with verification times ranging from 2.08 to 15.81 seconds. Due to the sophisticated nature of realistic test generators, verification takes longer compared to previous benchmarks, though it remains within acceptable limits. One observation is that the result of type checking does not significantly affect the verification time, which differs from standard refinement type checkers that can return early when detecting safety violations in one control flow. This is because Poirot cannot determine the coverage completeness of a program without analyzing *all* corresponding control flows, as discussed in Sec. 4.

In the rest of section, we highlight three representative categories of coverage incompleteness detected by Poirot for these benchmarks, examine the underlying causes, and suggest candidate fixes to address these coverage missing.

Limited sampling range. Manually written test input generators often rely on restricted sampling ranges, resulting in coverage completeness violations. For example, Vellvm [67] generates LLVM `int32` and LLVM `int64` values only within the range 0–10000, and the generators in the herdttools7 framework [39] also restrict integer literals appearing in theorems to this interval. These generators typically use QCheck’s built-in `Gen.nat` combinator, which only produces natural numbers below 10000. While developers adopt this restriction under the assumption that smaller values are more likely to detect bugs, such approaches (theoretically) compromise completeness. One solution is to run two sets of tests, one with smaller values and one with the full range of values. Alternatively, it is straightforward to build a repaired version of this generator by using QCheck’s `frequency` combinator to combine the original with the default, unconstrained generator, adjusting the weights so that it is biased towards the original input space while retaining the possibility of producing other values:

```
let nat = frequency 2 (function
  | 0 -> (10, Gen.nat)
  | _ -> (1, full_nat_gen))
```

Fixed values. Zipperposition [6] uses the `oneof` combinator to restrict variable names to one of three fixed options: X, Y, or Z. Similarly, the Xen hypervisor [63] constrains file sizes to 9 predetermined lengths and only uses one of 4 fixed float number (e.g., 0.001, 0.01, 0.1, and 0.4) as file read and write delay times. While such choices may reflect the developer’s intuition about likely corner cases, they also prevent the exploration of errors outside these considerations. The repair strategies proposed earlier apply here as well.

Datatype transformations. Poirot identified an interesting coverage completeness violation in the Tezos blockchain project [59], where test input generators construct block trees, i.e., trees of block nodes representing the shape of the block chain. Instead of generating such trees directly, Tezos implements a helper function `tree_gen` (shown in Fig. 22) that builds trees from lists of blocks. Specifically, `tree_gen` accepts a non-empty, duplicate-free list of blocks

```

2092 1     type 'a tree =
2093 2     | Leaf of 'a
2094 3     | Node1 of ('a * 'a tree)
2095 4     | Node2 of ('a * 'a tree * 'a tree)
2096 5
2096 6     let rec tree_gen (blocks: block list): block tree gen =
2097 7         match block with
2098 8         | [x] -> return (Leaf x)
2099 9         | x :: xs -> (
2100 10             ... (* the case producing Leaf *)
2101 11             ... (* the case producing Node1 *)
2102 12             int_bound (List.length xs - 1) >>= fun n ->
2103 13             let left, right = List.split_n n xs in
2104 14             tree_gen left >>= fun left ->
2105 15             tree_gen right >>= fun right ->
2106 16             return (Node2 (x, left, right))
2107 17
2107 18     tree_gen (Block.set_to_list unique_nonempty_block_gen)
2108
2109
2110
2111

```

Fig. 22. A tree-like block chain generator.

and returns a generator that produces a tree with non-duplicate blocks. The code comments state that this approach allows better control over sampling distributions and uniqueness. Thus, the expected coverage refinement type of `tree_gen` should be:

$$\text{tree_gen} : \mathbb{1} : \{v: \text{block list} \mid \text{uniqList}(v)\} \rightarrow$$

$$\mathcal{M} [v: \text{block tree} \mid \text{uniqTree}(v) \wedge \forall u. \text{memTree}(v, u) \iff \text{mem}(1, u)]$$

However, the actual implementation in Tezos fails to satisfy this specification and is rejected by Poirot. The root of every generated tree (line 16) is deterministically selected as the head of the input list. Moreover, the use of `List.split_n` partitions the input list into sublists that preserve element ordering, leading to the left subtree always containing earlier elements in the list. Since Tezos applies `tree_gen` to sorted lists (line 18), the resulting block trees consistently place the smallest element at the root, with left subtree elements always being smaller than those in the right subtree. The root cause of this error lies in the complexity of maintaining coverage completeness through transformations between inductive datatypes (e.g., from lists to trees).

One possible solution is to randomly permute the input list of blocks. Another patch is to replace the list input with a set:

$$\text{tree_gen} : \mathbb{s} : \{v: \text{block set} \mid \top\} \rightarrow$$

$$\mathcal{M} [v: \text{block tree} \mid \text{uniqTree}(v) \wedge \forall u. \text{memTree}(v, u) \iff \text{memSet}(s, u)]$$

A coverage complete implementation would then randomly select the root node from this set and partition the set into two disjoint subsets using a randomized split instead of relying on list indexing. We have submitted this patch to the Tezos codebase.

Discussion. As with any verification methodology, the question of whether the completeness violations discovered by Poirot in our case studies are true bugs or represent deliberate trade-offs is one that must ultimately be answered by the authors of these generators. We emphasize, however, that coverage types do enable developers to rigorously specify the

intended behaviors of an input generator and to validate that an implementation exhibits those behaviors. The ability to do so has concrete benefits for both the developers of input generators and the test engineers that rely on them.

First, potential incompleteness bugs can help to surface semantic mismatches between the test engineer’s and system developer’s understandings of the precondition of the system under test. In the case of the Tezos case study, for example, the test engineer may have believed that a tree of distinct blocks is isomorphic to a flattened, sorted list of blocks. By identifying this mismatch, Poirot can provide actionable feedback to both parties, enabling them to align their mental models of the system under test.

On the other hand, the coverage type of a generator also provides useful documentation to its clients. As our case studies shows, developers may deliberately prioritize efficient sampling over coverage completeness in practice, embedding *ad hoc* restrictions and choices in their implementations. When these trade-offs are not explicitly documented, as is often the case, the users of such generators may inadvertently fail to probe system behaviors on relevant portions of the input space. A generator for a parser or string manipulating program that restricts variable names to a, b, and c will fail to discover errors that can only be triggered by programs with more than three distinct variables. Similarly, only considering small integers may fail to probe arithmetic overflow cases like $-2^{31}/-1$ (the range of `int32` is $-2^{31} \sim 2^{31}-1$). By codifying these sorts of trade-offs as explicit type-level specifications, Poirot helps clients understand and justify the use of a particular generator when testing a system.

Finally, as [Sec. 9.3](#) demonstrated, coverage types can provide useful information when constructing new generators, particularly when doing so automatically [31]. These types can also be helpful when manually defining generators *compositionally* via monadic combinators, e.g., when a test engineer wants to combine generators that sample from different distributions. For example, the Xen API [63] includes the file descriptor generator shown in [Fig. 23](#), which applies the `oneof` combinator to generators for singleton lists and general file descriptor lists. Currently, these generators are informally described in the accompanying code comment; coverage types provide a rigorous mechanism for capturing these sorts of behaviors along with a principled characterization of how they fit together.

```

1  (* generates 2 kinds of lists:
2     - lists that contain only a single file kind
3     - lists that contain multiple file kinds
4
5     This is important for testing [select], because a single
6     [Unix.S_REG] would cause it to return immediately,
7     making it unlikely that we're actually testing
8     the behaviour for other file descriptors.
9  *)
10 oneof [g1; g2]
```

Fig. 23. A file descriptor generator that uses `oneof` to combine two generators with different coverage guarantees.

10 Related Work

Property-based testing (PBT) is an automated testing approach that uses random tests to determine if a user-defined property is satisfied by the component under test. In a PBT setting,

test inputs are expected to satisfy the preconditions of the functions under test and are equipped with a “shrink” procedure that automatically reduces failing inputs to minimal examples for reporting to users. First introduced for Haskell [5] to test the behavioral correctness of simple programs over algebraic datatypes (ADTs), PBT has since been successfully applied to a number of application domains, including operating systems [63], compilers [18], networks [38], memory models [39], web applications [44], and quantum computation [26]. Meanwhile, the properties in PBT have also been extended to richer logics. For instance, O’Connor and Wickström [44] allows users to provide specifications in linear temporal logic (LTL) to guide the testing of interactive applications. Property-based testing can also validate performance specifications, in addition to safety properties. For example, Löscher et al. [38] uses PropEr [52], a PBT framework in Erlang, to verify that the energy consumption of sensor networks remains within a specific bound.

Although PBT test generators can be derived automatically for arbitrary datatypes, handwritten test generators remain widely used. Etna [58] evaluates the test generators of mainstream PBT frameworks in Coq/Rocq and Haskell, concluding that “bespoke generators” (user-defined test generators) perform well in most cases. However, a recent empirical study [21] analyzed the use of property-based testing (PBT) in industrial practice. One key finding is that writing test generators for complex precondition properties (e.g., valid red-black trees) remains a significant challenge, even when PBT frameworks provide extensive combinators and monadic APIs. Developers described the process as “tedious” and “high-effort”, particularly when balancing coverage and input quality (e.g., generating inputs closer to realistic distributions). Poirot’s integration of PBT abstractions within an expressive refinement-type system tailored for coverage provides an automated validation mechanism to ensure generators satisfy rich safety and completeness constraints.

There has also been recent work that reduce user effort in writing high-quality test generators. Tyche [23] enables better visualization of test generator quality, including valid and invalid test cases, duplicate test cases, and corresponding distribution. Elazar Mittelman et al. [14] demonstrates that test generators for complex ADTs can be improved through combinatorial testing [43], where the domain of input ADT instances can be partitioned by combinations of datatype constructors. Several works have considered how to automatically synthesize sound and complete generators for a target precondition: the QuickChick PBT framework for Coq/Rocq, for example, is capable of deriving generators from preconditions expressed as inductive relations [35, 48]. LaFontaine et al. [31] present a technique for automatically repairing incomplete generators used coverage-type-guided program synthesis; when applied to a control-flow sketch, this technique is capable of synthesizing a coverage-complete generator for a given precondition. The recently proposed Palmedes [22] tool uses deductive synthesis to generate sound and complete generators from precondition that are expressed in Lean using an extensible set of recursion schemes. Another set of works consider the more specific problem of how to automatically adjust the distribution of an input generator. The Dragen tool [41, 42], for example, refines the default input generators derived by the QuickCheck framework by tuning input weights of frequency combinators using additional structural information provided by users. Loaded Dice [60] relaxes this restriction, allowing users to automatically tune the distribution of an arbitrary generator by first lowering it into a probabilistic DSL embedded in Julia and then optimizing those weights based on a user-provided objective function.

2245 A general limitation of PBT is that its effectiveness suffers when the property of interest
2246 has a strict precondition [32], because most of the inputs produced by a purely random
2247 test generation strategy will be simply discarded. As a result, there has been much recent
2248 interest on improving the coverage of test generators with respect to a particular precondition.
2249 Proposed solutions range from adopting ideas from fuzzing [10, 66] to intelligently mutate
2250 the outputs produced by the generator [34, 46], to focusing on generators for particular classes
2251 of inputs (e.g., well-typed programs) [16, 47, 65], to automatically building complete-by-
2252 construction generators [4, 33, 35]. While sharing broadly similar goals with these proposals,
2253 our approach differs significantly in its framing of coverage in purely type-theoretic terms.
2254 This fundamental change in perspective allows us to statically and compositionally verify
2255 coverage properties of a generator without the need for any form of instrumentation on, or
2256 runtime monitoring of, the program under test (as in [10, 34]). Unlike other approaches
2257 that have also considered the verification of a generator’s coverage properties [12, 13, 49]
2258 using a mechanized proof assistant, our proposed type-based framing is highly-automated
2259 and inherently compositional. Expressing coverage as part of a type system also allows us
2260 to be agnostic to (a) how generators are constructed, (b) the particulars of the application
2261 domain [16, 18, 47, 65], and (c) the specific structure of the properties being tested [33, 35].
2262 Poirot’s ability to specify and type-check a complex coverage property depends only on
2263 whether we can express a desired specification using available uninterpreted predicates.
2264

2265 A number of logics have been proposed for reasoning about underapproximations of
2266 program behavior, including the recently developed incorrectness logic (IL) [45, 53], reverse
2267 Hoare logic (RHL) [9], and dynamic logic (DL) [51]. Both IL and RHL are formalisms
2268 similar to Hoare logic, but support composable specifications that assert underapproximate
2269 postconditions, with IL adding special post-assertions for error states. IL was originally
2270 proposed as a way of formalizing the conditions under which a particular program point (say
2271 an error state) is guaranteed to be reachable, and has recently been used in program analyses
2272 that discover memory errors [37]. DL, in contrast, reinterprets Hoare logic as a multi-modal
2273 logic equipped with operators for reasoning about the existence of executions that end in a
2274 state satisfying some desired postcondition. This paper instead provides the first development
2275 that interprets these notions in the context of a type system for a rich functional language.
2276 While our ideas are formulated in the context of verifying coverage properties for test input
2277 generators, we believe our framework can be equally adept in expressing type-based program
2278 analyses for bug finding or compiler optimizations.
2279

2280 Our focus on reasoning about coverage properties of test input generators distinguishes
2281 our approach, in obvious ways from other refinement type-based testing solutions such as
2282 TARGET [57]. Nonetheless, our setup follows the same general verification playbook as Liquid
2283 Types [29, 62] — our underapproximate specifications are identical to their overapproximate
2284 counterpart, except that we syntactically distinguish the return types for functions to reflect
2285 their expected underapproximate (rather than overapproximate) behavior. An important
2286 consequence of this design is that the burden of specifying and checking the coverage
2287 behavior of a program is no greater than specifying its safety properties.
2288

2289 Another related line of work has explored how to reason about the distribution of
2290 data produced by a function [1, 2], with a focus on ensuring that these distributions are
2291 free of unwanted biases. These works have considered decision-making and machine-
2292 learning applications, in which these sorts of fairness properties can be naturally encoded as
2293
2294
2295

(probabilistic) formulas in real arithmetic. In contrast, coverage types can only verify that a generator has a nonzero probability of producing a particular output. Extending our type system and its guarantees to provide stronger fairness guarantees about the distribution of the sorts of discrete data produced by test input generators is an exciting direction for future work.

11 Conclusion

This paper adapts principles of underapproximate reasoning found in recent work on Incorrectness Logic to the specification and automated verification of test input generators used in modern property-based testing systems. Specifications are expressed in the language of refinement types, augmented with coverage types, types that reflect underapproximate constraints on program behavior. A novel bidirectional type-checking algorithm enables an expressive form of inference over these types. Our experimental results demonstrate that our approach is capable of verifying both sophisticated hand-written generators, as well as being able to successfully identify type-correct (in an overapproximate sense) but coverage-incomplete generators produced from a deductive refinement type-aware synthesizer. We also demonstrate how polymorphic extensions to our type system can be used to successfully detect coverage violations of complex test generators implemented using monadic combinators in real-world developments.

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Data Availability

An artifact containing this implementation, our benchmark suite, results and corresponding Rocq proofs (i.e., our soundness theorems Theorem 5.3) is publicly available on Zenodo [69]. The benchmark suite of our new case study is available on GitHub: <https://github.com/zhezhouzz/CoverageType/tree/jfp> (Commit c6fa15d)

Conflicts of Interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to report.

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A Operational Semantics

Operational Semantics

$$e \hookrightarrow e$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \frac{op \bar{v} \equiv v_y}{\mathbf{let} \ y = op \ \bar{v} \ \mathbf{in} \ e \hookrightarrow e[y \mapsto v_y]} \text{STAPP}OP \\
 \\
 \frac{e_1 \hookrightarrow e'_1}{\mathbf{let} \ y = e_1 \ \mathbf{in} \ e_2 \hookrightarrow \mathbf{let} \ y = e'_1 \ \mathbf{in} \ e_2} \text{STLET}E1 \quad \frac{}{\mathbf{let} \ y = v \ \mathbf{in} \ e \hookrightarrow e[y \mapsto v]} \text{STLET}E2 \\
 \\
 \frac{}{\mathbf{let} \ y = \mathbf{fun} \ (x:t) \rightarrow e_1 \ v_x \ \mathbf{in} \ e_2 \hookrightarrow \mathbf{let} \ y = e_1[x \mapsto v_x] \ \mathbf{in} \ e_2} \text{STLET}APP\text{LAM} \\
 \\
 \frac{}{\mathbf{let} \ y = \mathbf{fix} \ (f:t) \ \mathbf{fun} \ (x:t_x) \rightarrow e_1 \ v_x \ \mathbf{in} \ e_2 \hookrightarrow \mathbf{let} \ y = (\mathbf{fun} \ (f:t) \rightarrow e_1[x \mapsto v_x]) \ (\mathbf{fix} \ (f:t) \ \mathbf{fun} \ (x:t_x) \rightarrow e_1) \ \mathbf{in} \ e_2} \text{STLET}APP\text{FIX} \\
 \\
 \frac{}{\mathbf{match} \ d_i \ \bar{v}_j \ \mathbf{with} \ \overline{d_i \ \bar{y}_j \rightarrow e_i} \hookrightarrow e_i[y_j \mapsto v_j]} \text{STMATCH}
 \end{array}$$

Fig. 24. Small Step Operational Semantics

The operational semantics of our core language is shown in Fig. 24, which is a standard small step semantics.

B Basic Typing rules

Basic Typing

$$\Gamma \vdash_t e : t$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \frac{}{\Gamma \vdash_t \mathbf{err} : t} \text{BTERR} \quad \frac{}{\Gamma \vdash_t c : \mathbf{Ty}(c)} \text{BTCONST} \quad \frac{}{\Gamma \vdash_t op : \mathbf{Ty}(op)} \text{BTOP} \quad \frac{\Gamma(x) = t}{\Gamma \vdash_t x : t} \text{BTVAR} \\
 \\
 \frac{\Gamma, x:t_1 \vdash_t e : t_2}{\Gamma \vdash_t \mathbf{fun} \ (x:t_1) \rightarrow e : t_1 \rightarrow t_2} \text{BTFUN} \quad \frac{\Gamma, f:t_1 \rightarrow t_2 \vdash_t \mathbf{fun} \ (x:t_1) \rightarrow e : t_1 \rightarrow t_2}{\Gamma \vdash_t \mathbf{fix} \ (f:t_1 \rightarrow t_2) \ \mathbf{fun} \ (x:t_1) \rightarrow e : t_1 \rightarrow t_2} \text{BTFIX} \\
 \\
 \frac{\emptyset \vdash_t e_1 : t_x \quad \Gamma, x:t_x \vdash_t e_2 : t}{\Gamma \vdash_t \mathbf{let} \ x = e_1 \ \mathbf{in} \ e_2 : t} \text{BTLET}E \quad \frac{\mathbf{Ty}(op) = \bar{t}_i \rightarrow t_x \quad \Gamma \vdash_t v_i : t_i \quad \Gamma, x:t_x \vdash_t e : t}{\Gamma \vdash_t \mathbf{let} \ x = op \ \bar{v}_i \ \mathbf{in} \ e : t} \text{BTAPP}OP \\
 \\
 \frac{\Gamma \vdash_t v_1 : t_2 \rightarrow t_x \quad \Gamma \vdash_t v_2 : t_2 \quad \Gamma, x:t_x \vdash_t e : t}{\Gamma \vdash_t \mathbf{let} \ x = v_1 \ v_2 \ \mathbf{in} \ e : t} \text{BTAPP} \\
 \\
 \frac{\Gamma \vdash_t v : t_v \quad \forall i, \mathbf{Ty}(d_i) = \bar{t}_j \rightarrow t_v \quad \Gamma, \overline{y_j:t_j} \vdash_t e_i : t}{\Gamma \vdash_t \mathbf{match} \ v \ \mathbf{with} \ \overline{d_i \ \bar{y}_j \rightarrow e_i} : t} \text{BTMATCH}
 \end{array}$$

Fig. 25. Basic Typing Rules

The basic typing rules of our core language and qualifiers are shown in Fig. 25 and Fig. 26. We use an auxiliary function \mathbf{Ty} to provide a basic type for the primitives of our language, e.g., constants, built-in operators, and data constructors.

Basic Qualifier Typing

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \boxed{\Gamma \vdash_t l : t \quad \Gamma \vdash_t \phi : t} \\
 \frac{\mathbf{Ty}(c) = t}{\Gamma \vdash_t c : t} \text{BTLITCONST} \quad \frac{\Gamma(x) = t}{\Gamma \vdash_t x : t} \text{BTLITVAR} \quad \frac{}{\Gamma \vdash_t \top : \text{bool}} \text{BTOP} \quad \frac{}{\Gamma \vdash_t \perp : \text{bool}} \text{BTBOT} \\
 \frac{\mathbf{Ty}(op) = \bar{t}_i \rightarrow t \quad \forall i. \Gamma \vdash_t l_i : t_i}{\Gamma \vdash_t op \bar{l}_i : t} \text{BTLITOP} \quad \frac{\mathbf{Ty}(up) = \bar{t}_i \rightarrow \text{bool} \quad \forall i. \Gamma \vdash_t l_i : t_i}{\Gamma \vdash_t up \bar{l}_i : t} \text{BTLITMP} \\
 \frac{\Gamma \vdash_t \phi_1 : \text{bool} \quad \Gamma \vdash_t \phi_2 : \text{bool}}{\Gamma \vdash_t \phi_1 \wedge \phi_2 : \text{bool}} \text{BTAND} \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash_t \phi_1 : \text{bool} \quad \Gamma \vdash_t \phi_2 : \text{bool}}{\Gamma \vdash_t \phi_1 \vee \phi_2 : \text{bool}} \text{BTOR} \\
 \frac{\Gamma, x:b \vdash_t \phi : \text{bool}}{\Gamma \vdash_t \forall x:b. \phi : \text{bool}} \text{BTFORALL} \quad \frac{\Gamma, x:b \vdash_t \phi : \text{bool}}{\Gamma \vdash_t \exists x:b. \phi : \text{bool}} \text{BT EXISTS} \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash_t \phi : \text{bool}}{\Gamma \vdash_t \neg \phi : \text{bool}} \text{BTNEG}
 \end{array}$$

Fig. 26. Basic Qualifier Typing Rules

C Type System Details

The subset relation between the denotation of two refinement types τ_1 and τ_2 under a type context Γ (written $\llbracket \tau_1 \rrbracket_\Gamma \subseteq \llbracket \tau_2 \rrbracket_\Gamma$) is:

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \llbracket \tau_1 \rrbracket_\emptyset \subseteq \llbracket \tau_2 \rrbracket_\emptyset \doteq \llbracket \tau_1 \rrbracket \subseteq \llbracket \tau_2 \rrbracket \\
 \llbracket \tau_1 \rrbracket_{x:\tau_x, \Gamma} \subseteq \llbracket \tau_1 \rrbracket_{x:\tau_x, \Gamma} \doteq \forall v_x \in \llbracket \tau_x \rrbracket, \\
 \quad \llbracket \tau_1[x \mapsto v_x] \rrbracket_{\Gamma[x \mapsto v_x]} \subseteq \llbracket \tau_2[x \mapsto v_x] \rrbracket_{\Gamma[x \mapsto v_x]} \quad \text{if } \tau \equiv \{v: b \mid \phi\} \\
 \llbracket \tau_1 \rrbracket_{x:\tau_x, \Gamma} \subseteq \llbracket \tau_2 \rrbracket_{x:\tau_x, \Gamma} \doteq \exists \hat{e}_x \in \llbracket \tau_x \rrbracket, \forall v_x, \hat{e}_x \hookrightarrow^* v_x \implies \\
 \quad \llbracket \tau_1[x \mapsto v_x] \rrbracket_{\Gamma[x \mapsto v_x]} \subseteq \llbracket \tau_2[x \mapsto v_x] \rrbracket_{\Gamma[x \mapsto v_x]} \quad \text{otherwise}
 \end{array}$$

The way we interpret the type context Γ here is the same as the definition of the type denotation under the type context, but we keep the denotation of τ_1 and τ_2 as the subset relation under the same interpretation of Γ , that is under the *same* substitution $[x \mapsto v_x]$. This constraint is also required by other refinement type systems, which define the denotation of the type context Γ as a set of substitutions, with the subset relation of the denotation of two types holding under the *same* substitution. However, our type context is more complicated, since it has both under- and overapproximate types that are interpreted via existential and universal quantifiers, and cannot simply be denoted as a set of substitution. Thus, we define a subset relation over denotations under a type context to ensure the same substitution is applied to both types.

D Typing Algorithm Details

We implement the auxiliary **Disj** operation using the mutually recursive functions shown in Fig. 27. The disjunction of two underapproximate base types $[v: b \mid v = 1]$ and $[v: b \mid v = 2]$ is simply the disjunction of their qualifiers: $[v: b \mid v = 1 \vee v = 2]$ (lines 3-4), as is the disjunction of two overapproximate base types (lines 5-6). We build the disjunction of two function types by taking the conjunction of their argument types and the disjunction of their return type (lines 7-9). We build the disjunction of a sequence of types by folding **Disj** over

	Algorithm 4: Disjunction		Algorithm 5: Conjunction
2653	1 Procedure Disj (τ_1, τ_2) :=	2654	1 Procedure Conj (τ_1, τ_2) :=
2654	2 match τ_1, τ_2 :	2655	2 match τ_1, τ_2 :
2656	3 case $[v: b \mid \phi_1], [v: b \mid \phi_2]$ do	2656	3 case $[v: b \mid \phi_1], [v: b \mid \phi_2]$ do
2657	4 return $[v: b \mid \phi_1 \vee \phi_2]$;	2657	4 return $[v: b \mid \phi_1 \wedge \phi_2]$;
2658	5 case $\{v: b \mid \phi_1\}, \{v: b \mid \phi_2\}$ do	2658	5 case $\{v: b \mid \phi_1\}, \{v: b \mid \phi_2\}$ do
2659	6 return $\{v: b \mid \phi_1 \vee \phi_2\}$;	2659	6 return $\{v: b \mid \phi_1 \wedge \phi_2\}$;
2660	7 case $a: \tau_{a_1} \rightarrow \tau_1, a: \tau_{a_2} \rightarrow \tau_2$ do	2660	7 case $a: \tau_{a_1} \rightarrow \tau_1, a: \tau_{a_2} \rightarrow \tau_2$ do
2661	8 $\tau_a \leftarrow$ Conj (τ_{a_1}, τ_{a_2});	2661	8 $\tau_a \leftarrow$ Disj (τ_{a_1}, τ_{a_2});
2662	9 return $a: \tau_a \rightarrow$ Disj (τ_1, τ_2);	2662	9 return $a: \tau_a \rightarrow$ Conj (τ_1, τ_2);
2663		2663	
2664		2664	

Fig. 27. Type Disjunction and Conjunction

2668 them:

$$2669 \quad \mathbf{Disj}(\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_{n-1}, \tau_n) \doteq \mathbf{Disj}(\tau_1, \mathbf{Disj}(\tau_2, \dots, \mathbf{Disj}(\tau_{n-1}, \tau_n)))$$

	Algorithm 6: Exists		Algorithm 7: Forall
2672	1 Procedure Ex ($x, [v: b \mid \phi_x], \tau$) :=	2672	1 Procedure Fa ($x, [v: b \mid \phi_x], \tau$) :=
2673	2 match τ :	2673	2 match τ :
2674	3 case $[v: b \mid \phi]$ do	2674	3 case $[v: b \mid \phi]$ do
2675	4 $\phi' \leftarrow \exists x. \phi_x [v \mapsto x] \wedge \phi$;	2675	4 $\phi' \leftarrow \forall x. \phi_x [v \mapsto x] \implies \phi$;
2676	5 return $[v: b \mid \phi']$;	2676	5 return $[v: b \mid \phi']$;
2677	6 case $\{v: b \mid \phi\}$ do	2677	6 case $\{v: b \mid \phi\}$ do
2678	7 $\phi' \leftarrow \exists x. \phi_x [v \mapsto x] \wedge \phi$;	2678	7 $\phi' \leftarrow \forall x. \phi_x [v \mapsto x] \implies \phi$;
2679	8 return $\{v: b \mid \phi'\}$;	2679	8 return $\{v: b \mid \phi'\}$;
2680	9 case $a: \tau_a \rightarrow \tau$ do	2680	9 case $a: \tau_a \rightarrow \tau$ do
2681	10 $\tau'_a \leftarrow$ Fa ($x, [v: b \mid \phi_x], \tau_a$);	2681	10 $\tau'_a \leftarrow$ Ex ($x, [v: b \mid \phi_x], \tau_a$);
2682	11 $\tau' \leftarrow$ Ex ($x, [v: b \mid \phi_x], \tau$);	2682	11 $\tau' \leftarrow$ Fa ($x, [v: b \mid \phi_x], \tau$);
2683	12 return $a: \tau'_a \rightarrow \tau'$;	2683	12 return $a: \tau'_a \rightarrow \tau'$;
2684		2684	
2685		2685	
2686		2686	

Fig. 28. Embedding bindings into type qualifiers

2690 The operation $\mathbf{Ex}(x, [v: b \mid \phi_x], \tau)$ generalizes \mathbf{Disj} by aggregating not just two types, but all instances of $\tau[x \mapsto v]$ for every v such that ϕ_x holds. Thus, our algorithm also implements \mathbf{Ex} using the pair of mutually recursive functions shown in Fig. 28. To embed an underapproximate type binding into an under- or over-approximate base type, we simply add the appropriate quantifier into its type qualifier: thus, embedding the binding $x: [v: \text{nat} \mid v > 0]$ into the type $[v: \text{nat} \mid v = x + 1]$ produces the type $[v: \text{nat} \mid \exists x. x > 0 \wedge v = x + 1]$. Bindings are embedded into a function type by contravariantly moving the binding into its argument type and covariantly into its result type. To illustrate the necessity of embedding bindings contravariantly into function types, consider the following function, which returns normally only if the input parameter y exceeds a random value x :

```
2701 let x = 1  $\oplus$  2 in
2702 fun (y: int) -> if y > x then x else err
```

2703

2704 Within the type context $x:[v: \text{int} \mid v = 1 \vee v = 2]$, we can assign the function the type
 2705 $y:\{v: \text{int} \mid v > x\} \rightarrow [v: \text{int} \mid v = x]$. After applying the **Ex** operation to embed the binding
 2706 for x , we obtain:

$$2707 \quad y:\{v: \text{int} \mid \forall x. (x = 1 \vee x = 2) \implies v > x\} \rightarrow [v: \text{int} \mid \exists x. (x = 1 \vee x = 2) \wedge v = x]$$

$$2708 \quad \equiv y:\{v: \text{int} \mid v > 2\} \rightarrow [v: \text{int} \mid v = 1 \vee v = 2]$$

2709 In contrast, incorrectly treating the parameter position covariantly leads to unsoundness:

$$2710 \quad y:\{v: \text{int} \mid \exists x. (x = 1 \vee x = 2) \wedge v > x\} \rightarrow [v: \text{int} \mid \exists x. (x = 1 \vee x = 2) \wedge v = x]$$

$$2711 \quad \equiv y:\{v: \text{int} \mid v > 1\} \rightarrow [v: \text{int} \mid v = 1 \vee v = 2]$$

2712 Here, if $y = 2$, the function could only return 1, violating the intended behavior.

2713 *SMT Query Encoding for data types.* In order to reason over data types, we allow the
 2714 user to specify refinement types with uninterpreted predicates (e.g., *mem*) and quantifiers
 2715 (e.g., $\forall u. \neg \text{mem}(v, u)$). These uninterpreted predicates are encoded as uninterpreted functions
 2716 with stratified sorts. In order to ensure the query is an EPR sentence, we require that
 2717 a normal refinement type (overapproximate types) can only use universal quantifiers. In
 2718 addition, as shown in Fig. 5, we disallow nested uninterpreted predicate application (e.g.,
 2719 $\text{mem}(v, \text{mem}(v, u))$) and can only apply a uninterpreted predicate over constants $\text{mem}(v, 3)$
 2720 (it can be encoded as $\forall u. u = 3 \implies \text{mem}(v, u)$).

2721 E Proofs

2722 *Type Soundness.* The Rocq formalization of our core language, typing rules and the proof of
 2723 [Theorem 5.3](#) is publicly available on Zenodo[69].

2724 *Soundness of Algorithmic Typing.* We present the proof for [Theorem 6.3](#) from [Sec. 6](#). The
 2725 proof requires the following lemmas about the **Subtyping** subroutine, **Ex** and **Disj** functions.

2726 **Lemma E.1.** [Soundness of **Subtyping** subroutine] For all type context Γ and coverage type
 2727 $[v: b \mid \phi_1]$ and $[v: b \mid \phi_2]$, **Subtyping**($\Gamma, [v: b \mid \phi_1], [v: b \mid \phi_2]$) implies $\Gamma \vdash [v: b \mid \phi_1] <:$
 2728 $[v: b \mid \phi_2]$.

2729 **Lemma E.2** (The **Disj** Function implies disjunction judgement). For all type context Γ , type
 2730 τ_1 and τ_2 , $\Gamma \vdash \tau_1 \vee \tau_2 = \text{Disj}(\tau_1, \tau_2)$.

2731 **Lemma E.3** (The **Ex** Function implies type judgement transformation). For all type context
 2732 Γ, Γ' , term e , and type τ ,

$$2733 \quad \Gamma, \Gamma' \vdash e : \tau \implies \Gamma, \Gamma' \vdash e : \text{Ex}(\Gamma', \tau) \wedge \Gamma \vdash \text{Ex}(\Gamma', \tau)$$

2734 We also lift the subtyping relation to type contexts.

2735 **Definition E.4** (Subtyping relation over Type Contexts). As in the subtyping relation between
 2736 types, the subtyping relation between two type context $\Gamma_1 \sqsubseteq \Gamma_2$ means that if a term have
 2737 type τ under one context, it should also have the same type in the second context.

$$2738 \quad \Gamma_1 \sqsubseteq \Gamma_2 \doteq \forall \tau, \forall e, e \in \llbracket \tau \rrbracket_{\Gamma_1} \implies e \in \llbracket \tau \rrbracket_{\Gamma_2}$$

2739 **Lemma E.5.** [Sub Type Context Implies Type Judgement Transformation] For two type
 2740 context $\Gamma_1 \sqsubseteq \Gamma_2$, term e and coverage type τ ,

$$2741 \quad \Gamma_1 \vdash e : \tau \implies \Gamma_2 \vdash e : \tau$$

2742

Intuitively, modifying a type binding in a type context is equivalent to applying the subsumption rule before we introduce this binding into the type context. This subtype context relation allows us to prove the correctness of the typing algorithm, which lazily strengthens the types in the type context by need.

Now we can prove the soundness theorem of our typing algorithm with respect to our declarative type system. As the type synthesis rules are defined mutually recursively, we simultaneously prove both are correct:

Theorem E.6. [Soundness of the type synthesis and type check algorithm] For all type context Γ , term e and coverage type τ ,

$$\begin{aligned}\Gamma \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau &\implies \Gamma \vdash e : \tau \\ \Gamma \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau &\implies \Gamma \vdash e : \tau\end{aligned}$$

PROOF. We proceed by induction of the mutual recursive structure of $\Gamma \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau$ and $\Gamma \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau$. In the cases of rule `SYNCONST`, `SYNOP`, `SYNERR`, `SYNVARBASE`, `SYNVARFUN`, `CHKSUB`, `CHKFUN`, and `CHKFIX`, the coverage typing rules in Fig. 7 aligns exactly with these rules, thus the soundness is immediate in these cases.

In addition, the rule `SYNAPPOP` is similar to `SYNAPPBASE`, but has multiple arguments; the rule `SYNLETE` is the same as `SYNAPPFUN` but has no application; the rule `SYNMATCH` is similar with `CHKMATCH`, thus we discuss one rule in each of these pairs while the second follows in a similar fashion. Consequently, there are three interesting cases, corresponding to the rules shown in Fig. 8.

Case `SYNAPPFUN`: This rule can be treated as a combination of `TAPPFUN` and `TEQ`. From the induction hypothesis and the precondition of `SYNAPPFUN`, we know

$$\begin{aligned}\Gamma \vdash v_1 : (a:\tau_a \rightarrow \tau_b) \rightarrow \tau_x &\quad \text{since } \Gamma \vdash v_1 \Rightarrow (a:\tau_a \rightarrow \tau_b) \rightarrow \tau_x \\ \Gamma \vdash v_2 : a:\tau_a \rightarrow \tau_b &\quad \text{since } \Gamma \vdash v_2 \Leftarrow a:\tau_a \rightarrow \tau_b \\ \Gamma, x:\tau_x \vdash e : \tau &\quad \text{since } \Gamma, x:\tau_x \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau\end{aligned}$$

For the $\tau' = \mathbf{Ex}(x:\tau_x, \tau)$, according to Lemma E.3, we know

$$\Gamma, x:\tau_x \vdash e : \tau' \wedge \Gamma \vdash \tau'$$

Using the above conclusions, Since all the preconditions of `TAPPFUN` hold, applying the rule `TAPPFUN`, we have $\Gamma \vdash \mathbf{let } x = v_1 \ v_2 \ \mathbf{in } e : \tau'$.

Case `SYNAPPBASE`: Notice that the value v_2 has the base type t , and can only be a constant or a variable, doing a case split on this:

- (a) If v_2 is a constant c_2 , notice that $\phi[v \mapsto c_2]$ has to be true, otherwise the binding $a:[v: b \mid v = c_2 \wedge \phi]$ has the bottom type, and the type context that contains it is not well formed. Thus, using the well-formedness of the context, it follows that

$$v = c_2 \wedge \phi \equiv v = c_2$$

Thus, again using the Induction Hypothesis on the antecedents of the rule we have:

$$\begin{aligned} & \Gamma \vdash v_1 : a : \{v : b \mid v = c_2 \wedge \phi\} \rightarrow \tau_x [a \mapsto c_2] \\ & \quad \text{since } \Gamma \vdash v_1 \Rightarrow a : \{v : b \mid v = c_2 \wedge \phi\} \rightarrow \tau_x \text{ and T}_{\text{SUB}} \\ & \Gamma \vdash c_2 : [v : b \mid v = c_2 \wedge \phi] \\ & \quad \text{since T}_{\text{CONST}} \text{ and } v = c_2 \equiv v = c_2 \wedge \phi \\ & \Gamma, a : [v : b \mid v = c_2 \wedge \phi], x : \tau_x [a \mapsto c_2] \vdash e : \tau [a \mapsto c_2] \\ & \quad \text{since } \Gamma, a : [v : b \mid v = c_2 \wedge \phi], x : \tau_x \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau \end{aligned}$$

Since the variable a is not free in the type judgment, we can remove it from the type context

$$\Gamma, x : \tau_x [a \mapsto c_2] \vdash e : \tau [a \mapsto c_2]$$

According to the Lemma E.3, we know that

$$\Gamma, x : \tau_x [a \mapsto c_2] \vdash e : \mathbf{Ex}(x : \tau_x [a \mapsto c_2], \tau [a \mapsto c_2])$$

The type $\mathbf{Ex}(x : \tau_x [a \mapsto c_2], \tau)$ is well formed under the type context Γ , and all preconditions of the rule TAPP are satisfied, so we can conclude

$$\Gamma \vdash e : \mathbf{let } x = v_1 \ c_2 \ \mathbf{in } e : \mathbf{Ex}(x : \tau_x [a \mapsto c_2], \tau [a \mapsto c_2])$$

Notice that, $\phi[v \mapsto c_2]$ is true, thus we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbf{Ex}(x : \tau_x [a \mapsto c_2], \tau [a \mapsto c_2]) \\ & \equiv \mathbf{Ex}(a : [v : b \mid v = c_2], x : \tau_x [a \mapsto a], \tau [a \mapsto a]) \\ & \equiv \mathbf{Ex}(a : [v : b \mid v = c_2 \wedge \phi], x : \tau_x, \tau) \\ & \equiv \tau' \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we can conclude $\Gamma \vdash e : \mathbf{let } x = v_1 \ c_2 \ \mathbf{in } e : \tau'$.

- (b) If v_2 is a variable x_2 , we first construct a subcontext of Γ where we modify the type of x_2 in the type context Γ . Since the variable x_2 has a type in the context Γ , then¹²

$$\Gamma \equiv \Gamma_1, x_2 : [v : t_2 \mid \phi_2], \Gamma_2$$

we build a type context Γ^*

$$\Gamma \equiv \Gamma_1, x_2 : [v : t_2 \mid \phi_2 \wedge \phi], \Gamma_2$$

Intuitively, this new context gives us an assumption similar to the constant case above:

$$v = x_2 \wedge \phi \iff v = x_2$$

In fact, the new context Γ^* implies two subtyping relations over the context:

$$\begin{aligned} & \Gamma^* \sqsubseteq \Gamma \\ & \Gamma, a : [v : b \mid v = x_2 \wedge \phi] \sqsubseteq \Gamma^*, a : [v : b \mid v = x_2 \wedge \phi] \end{aligned}$$

¹²We use the same way when the variable x_2 having a normal refinement type $\{v : t_2 \mid \phi_2\}$, thus we omitted this situation.

2857 The first is obvious, since we only add a conjunction into the type of x_2 . On
 2858 the other hand, $\Gamma, a:[\nu: b \mid \nu = x_2 \wedge \phi]$ is a subtype of $\Gamma^*, a:[\nu: b \mid \nu = x_2 \wedge \phi]$
 2859 in reverse, since we strengthen the coverage type of x_2 in the last binding
 2860 $a:[\nu: b \mid \nu = x_2 \wedge \phi]$. Then, according to the second subtype context relation,
 2861 we have

$$2862 \Gamma^* \vdash \nu_1 : a:\{\nu: b \mid \nu = x_2 \wedge \phi\} \rightarrow \tau_x \quad \text{since } \Gamma \vdash \nu_1 \Rightarrow a:\{\nu: b \mid \phi\} \rightarrow \tau_x \text{ and TSUB}$$

2863 Based on the fact $\nu = x_2 \wedge \phi \iff \nu = x_2$, we have

$$2864 \Gamma^* \vdash \nu_2 : [\nu: b \mid \nu = x_2 \wedge \phi] \quad \text{According to the rule TVAR}$$

2865 According to the second subtype context relation, we have

$$2866 \Gamma^*, a:[\nu: b \mid \nu = x_2 \wedge \phi], x:\tau_x[a \mapsto x_2] \vdash e : \tau[a \mapsto x_2]$$

$$2867 \text{since } \Gamma, a:[\nu: b \mid \nu = x_2 \wedge \phi], x:\tau_x \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau$$

2868 Again, since the variable a is not free, we can also remove it. Moreover, according
 2869 to the typing rule TAPP and the Lemma E.3, we know

$$2870 \Gamma^* \vdash \mathbf{let} \ x = \nu_1 \ x_2 \ \mathbf{in} \ e : \mathbf{Ex}(x:\tau_x[a \mapsto x_2], \tau[a \mapsto x_2])$$

2871 Again, we have

$$2872 \mathbf{Ex}(x:\tau_x[a \mapsto x_2], \tau[a \mapsto x_2])$$

$$2873 \equiv \mathbf{Ex}(a:[\nu: b \mid \nu = x_2], x:\tau_x[a \mapsto a], \tau[a \mapsto a])$$

$$2874 \equiv \mathbf{Ex}(a:[\nu: b \mid \nu = x_2 \wedge \phi], x:\tau_x, \tau)$$

$$2875 \equiv \tau'$$

2876 Then we have

$$2877 \Gamma^* \vdash \mathbf{let} \ x = \nu_1 \ x_2 \ \mathbf{in} \ e : \tau'$$

2878 Finally, by combining Lemma E.5 and $\Gamma^* \sqsubseteq \Gamma$, we have

$$2879 \Gamma \vdash \mathbf{let} \ x = \nu_1 \ x_2 \ \mathbf{in} \ e : \tau'$$

2880 Case CHKMATCH: The rule is a combination of TMATCH and TMERGE. For the i^{th} branch
 2881 of the pattern matching branch, we have the following judgment after unfolding Γ'_i

$$2882 \Gamma, y:[\nu: b_y \mid \theta_y], a:[\nu: b \mid \nu = \nu_a \wedge \psi_i] \vdash e_i : \tau_i \quad \text{since } \Gamma, \Gamma'_i \vdash e_i \Rightarrow \tau_i$$

2883 Similarly to the approach we used for the SYNAPPBASE case, since ν_a is a value of
 2884 base type, it can only be a constant or a variable. Then we can derive the following
 2885 judgement without the variable a :

$$2886 \Gamma, y:[\nu: b_y \mid \theta_y] \vdash e_i : \mathbf{Ex}(\overline{y:[\nu: b_y \mid \theta_y]}, \tau_i[a \mapsto \nu_a]) \equiv \tau'_i$$

2887 According to the rule TMATCH, we have the following judgement for all branches

$$2888 \Gamma \vdash \mathbf{match} \ \nu_a \ \mathbf{with} \ \overline{d_i \ \bar{y} \rightarrow e_i} : \tau'_i$$

2889 Then according to the Lemma E.2, we have

$$2890 \Gamma \vdash \mathbf{match} \ \nu_a \ \mathbf{with} \ \overline{d_i \ \bar{y} \rightarrow e_i} : \mathbf{Disj}(\overline{\tau'_i})$$

2901
2902
2903
2904
2905
2906
2907

Finally, according to TSUB , for a type τ' that $\Gamma \vdash \text{Disj}(\overline{\tau'_i}) <: \tau'$, we have

$$\Gamma \vdash \text{match } v_a \text{ with } \overline{d_i \bar{y}} \rightarrow e_i : \tau'$$

which is exactly what we needed to prove for this case.

□

Completeness of Algorithmic Typing. We present the proof for [Theorem 6.4](#) from [Sec. 6](#). The theorem assumes “an oracle for all formulas produced by the Query subroutine”, which can be stated as the following lemma.

Lemma E.7. [An oracle of [Subtyping](#) subroutine exists] For all type context Γ and coverage type $[v: b \mid \phi_1]$ and $[v: b \mid \phi_2]$, $\Gamma \vdash [v: b \mid \phi_1] <: [v: b \mid \phi_2]$ iff [Subtyping](#)($\Gamma, [v: b \mid \phi_1], [v: b \mid \phi_2]$).

With the assumption above, we introduce the following lemmas about the [Subtyping](#) subroutine, [Disj](#) and [Ex](#) functions as we did in the soundness proof.

Lemma E.8 ([Subtyping](#) subroutine implies propositional equality). For all type context Γ , type $[v: b \mid \phi_1]$, $[v: b \mid \phi_2]$

$$\text{Subtyping}(\Gamma, [v: b \mid \phi_1], [v: b \mid \phi_2]) \wedge \text{Subtyping}(\Gamma, [v: b \mid \phi_2], [v: b \mid \phi_1]) \implies \phi_1 = \phi_2$$

Lemma E.9 (Disjunction judgement can be simulated by the [Disj](#) Function). For all type context Γ , type τ_1, τ_2, τ_3 , $\Gamma \vdash \tau_1 \vee \tau_2 = \tau_3 \implies \Gamma \vdash \tau_3 <: \text{Disj}(\tau_1, \tau_2) \wedge \Gamma \vdash \text{Disj}(\tau_1, \tau_2) <: \tau_3$.

Lemma E.10 ([Ex](#) Function is identical when well-formed). For all type context Γ, Γ' and type τ , $\Gamma \vdash \tau \implies \forall e, \Gamma, \Gamma' \vdash e \implies \tau \iff \Gamma, \Gamma' \vdash e \implies \text{Ex}(\Gamma', \tau)$.

We also have the corresponding lemma about the subtyping judgement.

Lemma E.11 (Subtyping judgement iff the [Ex](#) Function). For all type context Γ , and type τ_1, τ_2 , $\Gamma \vdash \tau_1 <: \tau_2 \iff \emptyset \vdash \text{Ex}(\Gamma, \tau_1) <: \text{Ex}(\Gamma, \tau_2)$.

Now we can prove the completeness theorem of our typing algorithm with respect to our declarative type system.

Theorem E.12 (Relative completeness of typing algorithm). For all type context Γ , term e and coverage type τ , $\Gamma \vdash e : \tau \implies \Gamma \vdash e \leftarrow \tau$.

PROOF. We proceed by induction of $\Gamma \vdash e : \tau$. In the cases for typing rules of rule TErr , TConst , TOP , TVarBase , TVarFun , TFun , and TFix , the coverage typing synthesis rules in [Fig. 8](#) aligns exactly with these rules. By applying the rule CHKSUB to shift from the typing synthesis judgement to the typing check judgement, the completeness is immediate in these cases. For the same reason, in the case for the rule TSUB , the completeness also holds.

Case TLET , TAPP , TAPPFUN , TAPP , TMATCH : The coverage typing synthesis rules in [Fig. 8](#) aligns similar rules (SYNLET , SYNAPP , SYNAPPFUN , SYNAPPBASE , SYNMATCH) in these cases, which synthesis the type $\text{Ex}(\Gamma', \tau)$ instead of τ . This difference can be fixed by the [Lemma E.10](#) and the precondition that τ is well formed under type context Γ .

Case TEQ : The key idea of this case is to use the auxiliary term $\text{let } x = e \text{ in } x$ and the rule SYNLET to simulate the type judgment transformation. Notice that the auxiliary

2959 term $\mathbf{let} x = e \mathbf{in} x$ is equivalent to e with respect to the operational semantics, that
 2960 is,

$$2961 \quad \forall v, e \hookrightarrow^* v \iff \mathbf{let} x = e \mathbf{in} x \hookrightarrow^* v$$

2963 It also implies that

$$2964 \quad \forall \Gamma e \tau, e \in \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\Gamma} \iff \llbracket \mathbf{let} x = e \mathbf{in} x \rrbracket_{\Gamma}$$

2966 Thus, the goal of this case can be simplified as

$$2967 \quad \forall \Gamma e \tau_1 \tau_2, \Gamma \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau_1 \wedge \Gamma \vdash \tau_1 <: \tau_2 \wedge \Gamma \vdash \tau_2 <: \tau_1 \implies \Gamma \vdash \mathbf{let} x = e \mathbf{in} x \Rightarrow \tau_2$$

2969 According to the Lemma E.11, we know

$$2970 \quad \emptyset \vdash \mathbf{Ex}(\Gamma, \tau_1) <: \mathbf{Ex}(\Gamma, \tau_2) \wedge \emptyset \vdash \mathbf{Ex}(\Gamma, \tau_1) <: \mathbf{Ex}(\Gamma, \tau_2)$$

2972 According to the Lemma E.7 and Lemma E.8, we know $\mathbf{Ex}(\Gamma, \tau_1) = \mathbf{Ex}(\Gamma, \tau_2)$. On
 2973 the other hand, according to the rule SYNVARBASE (or, SYNVARFUN) and the rule
 2974 SYNLETE , we can infer the type of the auxiliary term $\mathbf{let} x = e \mathbf{in} x$ as $\mathbf{Ex}(\Gamma, \tau_1)$,
 2975 thus we know

$$2976 \quad \Gamma \vdash \mathbf{let} x = e \mathbf{in} x \Rightarrow \mathbf{Ex}(\Gamma, \tau_2)$$

2978 The according to Lemma E.11 and the type $\mathbf{Ex}(\Gamma, \tau_2)$ has no free variable, we know

$$2979 \quad \Gamma \vdash \mathbf{let} x = e \mathbf{in} x \Rightarrow \tau_2$$

2981 which is exactly what we needed to prove for this case.

2982 Case TMERGE : Similarly to the approach we used in the case TEQ , the key idea is to
 2983 use the auxiliary term $e \oplus e$ (non-deterministic choice between two e) and the rule
 2984 SYNMATCH to simulate the typing rule TMERGE . Notice that the auxiliary term $e \oplus e$
 2985 is equivalent to e with respect to the operational semantics, which implies that

$$2986 \quad \forall \Gamma e \tau, e \in \llbracket e \rrbracket_{\Gamma} \iff \llbracket e \oplus e \rrbracket_{\Gamma}$$

2989 Thus, the goal of this case can be simplified as

$$2990 \quad \forall \Gamma e \tau_1 \tau_2 \tau_3, \Gamma \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau_1 \wedge \Gamma \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau_2 \wedge \Gamma \vdash \tau_1 \vee \tau_2 = \tau_3 \implies \Gamma \vdash e \oplus e \Rightarrow \tau_3$$

2992 With the rule SYNMATCH , we can infer the type of the term $e \oplus e$ as $\mathbf{Disj}(\tau_1, \tau_2)$. On
 2993 the other hand, according to the Lemma E.9, we know

$$2994 \quad \Gamma \vdash \tau_3 <: \mathbf{Disj}(\tau_1, \tau_2) \wedge \Gamma \vdash \mathbf{Disj}(\tau_1, \tau_2) <: \tau_3$$

2996 Finally, it falls back to the same situation of the case TEQ , which can obviously be
 2997 proved in the same way.

2999 \square

3000
 3001 *Soundness of Extended Algorithmic Typing.* We present the proof for [Theorem 7.3](#) from
 3002 [Sec. 7](#). Besides the lemmas about the [Subtyping](#) subroutine, [Ex](#) and [Disj](#) functions which are
 3003 required by the proof of [Theorem 6.3](#), this proof additionally requires the following lemma
 3004 about the [Inst](#) subroutine.

3006 **Lemma E.13.** [Soundness of [Inst](#) subroutine] For all type context Γ and coverage type τ_1 ,
 3007 τ_2 and τ_3 , $\mathbf{Inst}(\Gamma, \tau_1, \tau_2) = \tau_3$ implies $\Gamma \vdash \tau_1 <: \tau_3$.

3009

3010 Similar with the proof for [Theorem 7.3](#), we prove the soundness theorem of our extended
 3011 typing algorithm with respect to our declarative type system. As the type synthesis rules are
 3012 defined mutually recursively, we simultaneously prove both are correct:

3013 **Theorem E.14.** [Soundness of the type synthesis and type check algorithm] For all type
 3014 context Γ , term e and coverage type τ ,

$$3016 \quad \Gamma \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau \implies \Gamma \vdash e : \tau$$

$$3017 \quad \Gamma \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau \implies \Gamma \vdash e : \tau$$

3018
 3019 **PROOF.** We proceed by induction of the mutual recursive structure of $\Gamma \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau$ and $\Gamma \vdash$
 3020 $e \Leftarrow \tau$ and focus on the extended rules shown in [Fig. 13](#). In addition, the rule `CHKPOLYTYPE`
 3021 and `CHKPOLYPRED` aligns exactly to declarative typing rule `TPOLYTYPE` and `TPOLYPRED`
 3022 shown in [Fig. 12](#), thus the soundness is immediate in these cases. Consequently, we now
 3023 provide the proof of two modified rules, `SYNAPPFUN` and `SYNAPPBASE`.

3025 **Case `SYNAPPFUN`:** This rule can be treated as a combination of `TAPPFUN` and `TEQ`. From
 3026 the induction hypothesis and the precondition of `SYNAPPFUN`, we know

$$3027 \quad \Gamma \vdash v_1 : \tau_1 \quad \text{since } \Gamma \vdash v_1 \Rightarrow \tau_1$$

$$3028 \quad \Gamma \vdash v_1 : a:\tau'_2 \rightarrow \tau_x \quad \text{since } \mathbf{Inst}(\Gamma, \tau_1, \tau_2) = a:\tau'_2 \rightarrow \tau_x \text{ and Lemma E.13}$$

$$3029 \quad \Gamma \vdash v_1 : a:\tau_2 \rightarrow \tau_x \quad \text{since } \Gamma \vdash \tau_2 <: \tau'_2 \text{ and TSub}$$

$$3030 \quad \Gamma \vdash v_2 : a:\tau_2 \quad \text{since } \Gamma \vdash v_2 \Rightarrow a:\tau_2$$

$$3031 \quad \Gamma, x:\tau_x \vdash e : \tau \quad \text{since } \Gamma, x:\tau_x \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau$$

3032
 3033 For the $\tau' = \mathbf{Ex}(x:\tau_x, \tau)$, according to [Lemma E.3](#), we know

$$3034 \quad \Gamma, x:\tau_x \vdash e : \tau' \wedge \Gamma \vdash \tau'$$

3035
 3036 Using the above conclusions, Since all the preconditions of `TAPPFUN` hold, applying
 3037 the rule `TAPPFUN`, we have $\Gamma \vdash \mathbf{let} \ x = v_1 \ v_2 \ \mathbf{in} \ e : \tau'$.

3038
 3039 **Case `SYNAPPBASE`:** From the induction hypothesis and the precondition of `SYNAPPBASE`,
 3040 we know

$$3041 \quad \Gamma \vdash v_1 : \tau_1$$

$$3042 \quad \text{since } \Gamma \vdash v_1 \Rightarrow \tau_1$$

$$3043 \quad \Gamma \vdash v_1 : a:\{v: b \mid \phi\} \rightarrow \tau_x$$

$$3044 \quad \text{since } \mathbf{Inst}(\Gamma, \tau_1, [v: b \mid \phi_2]) = a:\{v: b \mid \phi\} \rightarrow \tau_x \text{ and Lemma E.13}$$

3045
 3046 which leads the same precondition of original rule of `SYNAPPBASE` as shown in [Fig. 8](#),
 3047 thus the proof is the same as in the proof of [Theorem 6.3](#).

3048
 3049 □

3050
 3051 **Completeness of Extended Algorithmic Typing.** We present the proof for [Theorem 7.4](#) from
 3052 [Sec. 7](#). The theorem besides assumes “an oracle for all formulas produced by the Query
 3053 subroutine”, also assumes “**Inst** subroutine always succeeds” which can be stated as the
 3054 following lemma.

3055
 3056 **Lemma E.15.** [**Inst** subroutine always succeeds] For all type context Γ and coverage type τ_1
 3057 and τ_2 , if there exists a type $x:\tau'_2 \rightarrow \tau_{\text{ret}}$ such that $\Gamma \vdash a:\tau_2 \rightarrow \tau_{\text{ret}} <: \tau_1$ and $\tau'_2 <: \tau_2$, then
 3058 $\mathbf{Inst}(\Gamma, \tau_1, \tau_2) = x:\tau'_2 \rightarrow \tau_{\text{ret}}$.

3059
 3060

3061 Now we can prove the completeness theorem of our typing algorithm with respect to our
 3062 declarative type system.

3063 **Theorem E.16** (Relative completeness of typing algorithm). For all type context Γ , term e
 3064 and coverage type τ , $\Gamma \vdash e : \tau \implies \Gamma \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau$.
 3065

3066 **PROOF.** We proceed by induction of $\Gamma \vdash e : \tau$ and focus on the extended rules shown in
 3067 Fig. 13. In addition, the rule TPOLYTYPE and TPOLYPRED aligns exactly to rule CHKPOLYTYPE
 3068 and CHKPOLYPRED, thus the completeness also holds. The remaining proof for the modified
 3069 rules CHKAPPFUN and CHKAPPBASE can be simplified to showing that all terms type-checkable
 3070 under the original rules remain type-checkable under the modified versions.
 3071

3072 **Case CHKAPPFUN:** According to Theorem 6.4, we just needs to show the precondition of
 3073 original rule CHKAPPFUN can implies the precondition of modified rule CHKAPPFUN.
 3074 We know

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 3075 & \Gamma \vdash v_1 \implies \tau_2 \rightarrow \tau_x & \text{precondition of original CHKAPPFUN} \\
 3076 & \text{Inst}(\Gamma, \tau_2 \rightarrow \tau_x, \tau_2) = \tau_2 \rightarrow \tau_x & \text{since Lemma E.15} \\
 3077 & \Gamma \vdash v_2 \Leftarrow \tau_2 & \text{precondition of original CHKAPPFUN} \\
 3078 & \Gamma \vdash v_2 \implies \tau_2 & \text{since CHECKSUB} \\
 3079 & \Gamma \vdash \tau_2 <: \tau_2 & \text{since soundness of subtyping}
 \end{array}$$

3080 Then all preconditions of modified rule CHKAPPFUN hold, then the completeness
 3081 also holds.

3082 **Case CHKAPPBASE:** According to Theorem 6.4, we just needs to show the precondition of
 3083 original rule CHKAPPBASE can implies the precondition of modified rule CHKAPPBASE.
 3084 We know

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 3085 & \Gamma \vdash v_1 \implies a:\{v: b \mid \phi\} \rightarrow \tau_x & \text{precondition of original CHKAPPBASE} \\
 3086 & \Gamma \vdash v_2 \implies [v: b \mid v = v_2] & \text{since rule SYNVARBASE} \\
 3087 & \text{Inst}(\Gamma, a:\{v: b \mid \phi\} \rightarrow \tau_x, [v: b \mid v = v_2]) = a:\{v: b \mid \phi \wedge v = v_2\} \rightarrow \tau_x
 \end{array}$$

3088 Notice that $a:\{v: b \mid \phi \wedge v = v_2\} \rightarrow \tau_x$ is equal to $a:\{v: b \mid \phi \wedge v = v_2 \wedge v = v_2\} \rightarrow \tau_x$,
 3089 then all preconditions of modified rule CHKAPPFUN hold, then the completeness also
 3090 holds.

3091 \square

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